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Young people's attitudes to condom use in the UK: a rapid systematic review

Final report

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Requests for access to data should be addressed to the corresponding author.

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Guarantor of the review

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Abbreviations

AMAB	Assigned Male at Birth
AFAB	Assigned Female at Birth
DHSC	Department of Health and Social Care
LGBTQ+	Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender Plus
MSM	Men who have sex with men
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
NIHR	National Institute for Health and Care Research
PPI	Patient and public involvement
PROSPERO	Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews
SES	Socioeconomic status
STI	Sexually Transmitted Infection
UK	United Kingdom
UKHSA	United Kingdom Health Security Agency
WSM	Women who have Sex with Men
WSW	Women who have Sex with Women

Glossary

Dental dam	A thin, flexible, rectangular sheet—usually made of latex or polyurethane, used as a barrier to prevent the transmission of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) during oral-vaginal or oral-anal sex. It covers the genitals or anus.
Gender	Non-binary, spectrum-based aspect of personal identity influenced by social and cultural forces, including gender identity, expression, and modality. ¹
Heteronormative	Presents heterosexuality as the normative human sexuality and male vs female gender roles as fixed.
Internal condoms	Barrier method of contraception, worn inside the vagina or anus to prevent pregnancy and STIs.
Intersex	People with biological attributes, such as chromosomes, hormones, or reproductive organs, that do not fit typical binary biologically-based definitions of male or female. ¹
LGBTQ+	Acronym which encompasses all individuals who identify with one or more of the following sexual orientations and/or gender identities: lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer/questioning, intersex, asexual and other identities. ¹
Man	A person born male, determined based on biological sex as defined within the UK Equality Act 2010. ²
Non-binary	People with identities that fall outside of or across the traditional gender binary of "man" and "woman". ¹
Sex	Biological attributes that differentiate males and females, including chromosomes, hormone profiles, gene expression, and reproductive organs. ¹
Woman	A person born female, determined based on biological sex as defined within the UK Equality Act 2010. ²

¹ Consistent with the National Institute for health and care research Sex and Gender in Research Policy.

² Equality Act 2010, c. 39. Available at <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2010/15/contents>

Report structure

This report is divided into three sections with the aim of making the most relevant information about the findings easily accessible:

- **Executive summary:** An overview of the background, methods and findings of the report.
- **Main report:** Includes the background to the report, methods, a summary of the search results and study identification process alongside a detailed narrative description of the characteristics of included studies, findings from the framework synthesis and discussion, with accompanying recommendations for future policy, practice and research.
- **Appendices:** Include (1) the search strategies, (2) a list of the studies excluded at full-text screening with reasons for exclusion (3) table of key characteristics of included studies; (4) table of methods used in included studies; (5) table of key characteristics of interventions in included studies; (6) quality appraisal scores of the included studies.

Executive summary

Background

Globally, condom use is declining amongst young people. A World Health Organisation (WHO) report found that condom use across Canada, Central Asia and Europe declined among sexually active fifteen year olds by 9% for males and 6% for females between 2014 and 2022.(1) The United Kingdom (UK) is one of 42 countries included in the WHO report; in particular, Scotland was identified as the country where boys were least likely to have used a condom at last sexual intercourse.(1) Rates of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) amongst young people are increasing: a report from the UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA) indicated that within the UK, young people aged 15-24 years are disproportionately likely to be diagnosed with an STI.(2) If not diagnosed and treated early, STIs have the potential to cause serious health consequences for both men and women. There has also been an increase in unplanned pregnancies and an increased risk of pregnancy complications due to the prevalence of STIs.(3)

It is important that health care providers and decision-makers can identify ways to counter the declining use of condoms amongst young people. The Department of Health and Social Care (DHSC) has published the first Men's Health Strategy for England which seeks to improve the health and wellbeing of all men in England.(4) The Strategy includes tangible actions to provide the right support to enable men to make healthier choices and to prevent and tackle the biggest health problems affecting men of all ages. It recognises the importance of good sexual health and the links between alcohol and drug use and sexual behaviours which increase a person's risk of harm, such as condomless sex. It is important that health care providers and decision-makers can identify ways to counter the declining use of condoms amongst young people. However, whilst evidence suggests that provision of better sexual health services can help with condom use, it is also important to understand the underlying views of young people about condom use, in order that influencing factors can be adequately addressed.

There is an abundance of research on factors influencing condom use amongst young people, but relatively little research which draws together evidence from UK-based studies. Several systematic reviews have considered factors influencing condom use globally(5, 6) and in specific countries, including USA,(7, 8) Nigeria and Rwanda,(7) and 11 countries in Southern Africa.(9) Furthermore, we are aware of a pool of studies published in the last 10 years which use qualitative and quantitative methods (e.g. surveys) to explore young people's perceptions of factors

influencing condom use in the UK. Thus, there is a need for an up-to-date review which addresses this question.

What did we want to know?

We were asked to identify factors that influence the use of condoms amongst young people in the UK. To this end, we developed the following aim and research questions:

Aim

To identify factors that influence condom use amongst young people (aged 15-24) in the UK, and to identify where these factors are different for groups within this population group.

Groups included those associated with health inequities, such as sex, gender, ethnicity, socio-economic status and age, as well as groups who face specific challenges in avoiding unplanned pregnancy and/or STIs, including men who have sex with men, sex workers and trans people. Health inequities are differences in health opportunities and outcomes which are systemic, unfair and avoidable.

Research questions:

- 1. What factors influence condom use among young people within the UK?**
- 2. How do these factors vary for different groups of young people including those associated with health inequities, and groups who face specific challenges in avoiding unplanned pregnancy and/or STIs?**

How did we do it?

We carried out a rapid systematic review which followed established conduct⁽¹⁰⁾ and reporting guidance.⁽¹¹⁾ Rapid systematic reviews aim to use pre-specified and rigorous methods to exhaustively identify and draw together evidence from studies which answer a research question, whilst also accelerating this process to meet the needs of a decision-maker.⁽¹²⁾ This first involved developing a protocol which set out the aim, research questions and methods we would use, which we prospectively registered on PROSPERO – a publicly accessible registry.⁽¹³⁾ The protocol also described the type of studies we would search for and include in the review, which were defined as qualitative studies that collected and analysed data on factors which influence condom use amongst young people.⁽¹³⁾ Typically, qualitative studies use interviews, focus groups, or surveys with open-ended questions to collect data.

After registering the protocol, we undertook the following steps:

- Searched four bibliographic databases (MEDLINE ALL (including MEDLINE In-Process), Embase and APA PsycInfo (all via Ovid), and CINAHL (via EBSCO) which provide coverage of the relevant health-care literature. These searches were supplemented by citation chasing of included studies and relevant websites, alongside asking review interest holders for recommendations of known studies.
- Titles and abstracts of all the identified studies were independently screened by two reviewers using EPPI-Reviewer v6.17 software (EPPI Centre, UCL Social Research Institute, University College London) and we retrieved the full-texts of any studies which met our inclusion criteria.
- Full-texts were screened using the same method as title/abstracts to identify the studies eligible for inclusion in the review. Inclusion criteria for this review were follows:
 - Population: young people of any gender aged 15-24 years,
 - Phenomenon of interest: factors influencing use/non-use of condoms,
 - Context: any health, social, educational or third sector settings within the UK,
 - Date cut-off: 2014
 - Language: English language only.
- Critical appraisal was undertaken using the Wallace Checklist.(14)
- Synthesised the findings in the identified studies using the best-fit framework synthesis method.(15)

What did we find?

Studies included in the review

We identified 25 studies reported across 29 study reports which addressed our research question.(16-44) All of the studies used qualitative research methods. Ten studies reported qualitative data which specifically relates to an intervention that aimed to improve condom use amongst young people (n=12 study reports).(18, 19, 21, 24-26, 29-32, 39, 42) The remaining studies collected data on young people's attitudes to condom use without focusing on a specific intervention relating to increase condom use, although interventions were still sometimes mentioned in these studies (n=15 [17 study reports]).(16, 17, 20, 22, 23, 27, 28, 33-38, 40, 41, 43, 44)

We used the Wallace checklist to critically appraise the methods used in the included studies.(14) All the studies were considered to have a clear research question, and all but one were considered to have an appropriate study design to answer the research question. The

quality of methods used for data collection and analysis were more mixed, with around half of the included studies scoring 'No' for whether data collection and/or analysis was rigorously undertaken.

Framework synthesis

We mapped the data in the included studies onto four overarching themes which were derived from a socio-ecological model of health proposed in a previous qualitative evidence synthesis of factors influencing condom use in Southern Africa.⁽⁹⁾ These themes are as follows:

1. Social and community norms which may influence condom use (supported by 20 studies, 21 articles),
2. Institutional factors associated with sexual health services and school education which may support or hinder condom use in young people (supported by 19 studies, 24 articles),
3. Inter-personal factors associated with condom use (supported by 15 studies, 17 articles),
4. Intra-personal factors associated with condom use (supported by 26 studies, 30 articles).

Theme 1: Social and community norms

In summary, theme one highlights how various factors relating to social and community norms influence young people's attitudes towards condom use. These factors include the *stigmatisation of sexual behaviour, different standards of acceptable sexual behaviour, communication and peer-pressure, and the media*. Specifically, the findings showed that:

- Disapproval of sexual behaviour in the wider society can lead to young people disengaging with sexual health services (including schemes for accessing condoms), and a lack of understanding about sexual health within communities where sexual health is not openly discussed (e.g. conservative religious communities).
- Disparity in gender norms may impact young people's condom use through the perception that women who obtain condoms are seen negatively (e.g. as promiscuous), whereas men who are sexually active, including men who use condoms, are perceived positively (e.g. as demonstrating 'prowess').
- Peer-influence amongst some male groups (including socially excluded groups) can lead to not using condoms as an affirmation of their gender identity within their social group, which is dismissive of women's needs and preferences; and a desire to hide sexual activity from family can lead to sex in spaces with more limited accessibility to condoms (e.g. outside).

- The media was seen to reinforce derogatory attitudes towards women, and within pornography, condomless sex is seen as the norm.

Theme 2: Institutional factors associated with sexual health services and school education

In summary, theme two highlights institutional factors relating to *sexual health care services* and *school education* influencing condom use amongst young people. Specifically, the findings showed:

- Young people expressed a need for supportive sexual health services where young people do not feel judged for engaging in sexual activity, or overlooked in the provision of relevant information, particularly for young women, Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Trans Plus (LGBTQ+) and neurodivergent groups.
- A lack of leadership figures in school settings who are respected or trusted on issues relating to sex and limited in-depth or relevant information provision about condom use; this included the need for more information around how to negotiate safe sex, rather than only emphasising the need for this.

Theme 3: Interpersonal factors

In summary, theme three highlights how interpersonal factors influence condom use amongst young people. These factors include *heteronormative gender dynamics*, a *'spectrum of communication'* and *trust and familiarity*. Specifically, the data showed that:

- Male preference for whether a condom is used in heterosexual relationships often took priority over female preferences.
- Issues relating to communication between partners during sexual activity were on a spectrum from *not knowing when or how to communicate* the option of using a condom during sexual activity, to *feeling that communication about using a condom is being shut down deliberately*, including during coercive sexual activity, and in the context of 'stealth' where the condom is removed without telling the partner.
- Condomless sex was more common in long-term relationships, which was sometimes a mutual decision between both partners, but also showed (specifically in heterosexual relationships) that women's voices are sometimes dismissed by the male partner in long-term relationships.

Theme 4: Intrapersonal factors

In summary, theme four highlights how intrapersonal factors influence condom use amongst young people. These factors include *psychological characteristics*, *behavioural capability*,

knowledge and skills, attitudes and outcome expectancies, and decision-making effort.

Specifically, the data showed that:

- Young people reported reluctance to purchase condoms or use sexual health clinics to obtain them due to embarrassment, or in some cases feeling ashamed about their sexual activity; amongst men who have sex with men (MSM) shame arose from perceived judgemental attitudes towards their sexual behaviours in wider society – conversely, heterosexual young men appeared to view their sexuality more positively, but this could also lead to not using condoms if this would support their perception of “masculine” identity.
- Young people, including those from ethnic minorities and LGBTQ+ groups specifically, wanted more signposting to sexual health services and better provision of sexual health information, including visually appealing forms of advertisement, and engaging websites; opportunities to experiment with condoms and associated items such as lubricant were viewed positively for building knowledge and skills.
- Attitudes to condom use were closely related to young people’s perceived risk of an STI, but some young people still reported preferring the relative risk of an STI to using a condom, e.g. due to reported lack of sensation when using a condom.
- Impulsivity associated with some sexual behaviour was perceived to limit peoples’ decision-making ability – however, there was also a strong perception that condoms are too much of a ‘hassle’, and in young heterosexual men a tendency to expect women to make provision for avoiding pregnancy, e.g. emergency contraception.

What are the implications?

Policy

This review was commissioned by the DHSC and has the potential to inform multiple policy areas, including the Men’s Health Strategy for England, (4) the Women’s Health Strategy for England, (45) the HIV Action Plan for England, (46) LGBTQ+ Health Evidence Review and the UK 5-year action plan for antimicrobial resistance 2024-29. (47, 48) Our synthesis identifies factors influencing condom use in young people, and highlights how these factors may disproportionately impact on men, individuals living with HIV and the LGBTQ+ communities where appropriate.

Our findings highlight how factors influencing condom use vary across different groups of young people, meaning different approaches will be needed for different population groups. Government policy to encourage condom use will need to consider all socio-ecological factors

presented in this review. Our synthesis highlights how condom use, or non-use, is heavily influenced by society and gender norms around sexual behaviour, which can disproportionately impact on certain communities including socially excluded young men or those from some ethnic minority communities. Government policy can encourage development of strategies to support health and social care services to deliver sexual health care which promotes sex within healthy, consenting relationships (whether casual or otherwise). Acknowledgement of the role that sex plays in young men's developing sexual identity and status among peers is needed, with further consideration of how their views of sex and relationships can be changed to support male responsibility for their own and their partner's sexual health, including condom use and respect of their partners needs/wishes. Consideration of the impact of societal/community expectations in terms of sexual behaviour on men from certain ethnic minority and socially-excluded backgrounds is key.

Policy can also play a role in supporting and empowering women to access sexual health services and within their sexual relationships to ensure they can access the care they need and have their wishes respected. Limited data from this review indicates that consideration of the needs of women from certain ethnic minority and religious communities is required to ensure their educational and service access needs are met.

Policies impacting on health and education provision within religious and cultural communities which encourage an abstinence focused sexual-risk reduction approach needs to be carefully considered, to ensure that young people can access comprehensive education and health services whilst still respecting their religious and cultural views/background.

School education

Implications arising from the synthesis relevant to schools and health services are presented separately.

Implications for education regarding condom use delivered in schools:

- Schools should consider the environment young people need to be able to engage with learning about sexual health and condom use.
- Sexual health education should:
 - Encompass comprehensive facts about the potential unwanted consequences of sex, particularly STIs and the risks associated with oral sex.

- Tailor content to consider the needs of diverse groups, which may include individuals identifying as lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans or queer/questioning, intersex and asexual.
- Go beyond an abstinence or risk prevention approach, to incorporate learning and discussion on:
 - How sex can be a pleasurable activity.
 - Encouraging young people to talk about sex, condoms and other contraceptive methods with their sexual partners through role play.
 - Identifying, planning for and navigating potentially risky situations, including issues relating to consent and alcohol/drug use.
 - Addressing societal views and expectations around sex, including gendered norms for acceptable behaviour.
- Provide opportunities for young people to learn from the experiences of role models, scenarios or role play of situations to which they can relate.
- Raise awareness of places young people can go to for further support outside of and within school, including increased promotion of the availability of school nurses (where relevant).
- Support young people to develop critical thinking skills to evaluate and counteract information and material they access online and via social media.

Health services

Health services delivering advice or support regarding condom use should:

- Consider the range of accessibility needs of young people living within specific communities (e.g. rural, certain ethnic minority, conservative religious) in relation to accessing free condoms and sexual health advice.
- Ensure clear guidance on how to use condoms is included alongside free condoms and where young people can go to access further advice. Free condom schemes should also encompass provision of internal condoms and dental dams.
- Consider how best to advertise sexual health service availability to young people, including relevant social media sites and school nurses, depending on the individual needs and context of the young people within that setting.
- Develop an online national 'go-to' resource for advice and support on sexual health issues. Content should be up to date, friendly and fun, and accessible, with labelling of content which may be too sexually explicit for younger audiences. Young people may

appreciate opportunities to learn from other people's experiences to which they can relate.

- Consider of how best to engage with communities who may distrust or find it hard to access health services e.g. some ethnic minority or traveller communities.

Further research needs

- Further qualitative research to explore the experiences and support needs of all groups within LGBTQ+ communities and in relation to managing healthy relationships and sexual-health.
- Further qualitative research to consider of the specific needs of sex-workers in managing their sexual health.
- Qualitative and quantitative research to develop and evaluate interventions to promote condom use as a typical part of enacting a healthy masculine identity.
- Consider how participant age may contribute towards their likelihood and experiences of using condoms.

Conclusions

This is the first systematic review to synthesise qualitative evidence from the UK on young people's attitudes towards condom use. Our synthesis identifies factors at the policy, institutional, inter- and intra-personal level which may influence reported condom use in young people and provide opportunity for intervention. We highlight how these factors may disproportionately impact the condom use behaviour of certain groups of young people, potentially increasing their risk of unwanted pregnancy and STIs. Whilst the factors influencing condom use are likely to vary between different groups of young people, our findings highlight the importance of addressing stigma surrounding sexual behaviour in young people and the difficulties young people experience relating to the differences in acceptable sexual behaviour between young men and women.

Main report

Background

Globally, condom use amongst young people is in decline.⁽¹⁾ A recent World Health Organisation (WHO) report on adolescent sexual health in Europe, Central Asia and Canada found that condom use had declined among sexually active fifteen year olds by 9% for males and 6% for females between 2014 and 2022.⁽¹⁾ In particular, the report found that boys in Scotland, United Kingdom (UK), were the least likely to have used a condom at last sexual intercourse compared to boys in any other country in the report (52% did not use a condom).⁽¹⁾ The average rate of condomless sex at last sexual intercourse across the countries in the report was 36% for boys and girls, and the lowest rate was 14% amongst boys in Armenia, and 14% amongst girls in Serbia.⁽¹⁾

The reduced rate of condom use has implications for prevalence of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) in young people.⁽³⁾ A report from the UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA) indicated that within the UK young people aged 15-24 years are one group who are disproportionately more likely to be diagnosed with an STI, highlighting a “substantial rise” in diagnoses of gonorrhoea, which almost doubled in 15-24 year olds between 2021 and 2022, and chlamydia.⁽³⁾ Whilst the number of new STI diagnoses in young people in 2024 reduced by 18.5% in comparison to 2023, including a 36.4% decrease in gonorrhoea diagnoses, young people still continue to experience a high rate of STI diagnoses.⁽²⁾ If not diagnosed and treated early, STIs such as syphilis, gonorrhoea and chlamydia have the potential to cause severe and dangerous short- and long-term health consequences for people of all genders, which may not be immediately observable.⁽³⁾ STIs also increase the risk of pregnancy complications and risk to the child, including ongoing disability .⁽³⁾

Condom distribution schemes are one possible way to address the reduction in condom use. In 2017, the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) published guidelines on the effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of condom distribution schemes.⁽⁴⁹⁾ These guidelines were informed by findings from a quantitative evidence synthesis, where the majority of included primary studies were conducted within the United States, with no UK-based comparative studies on condom schemes being identified.⁽⁵⁰⁾ The guidelines highlight the effectiveness of both single and multi-component condom distribution schemes at reducing rates of STIs i.e. provision of free condoms and lubricants in public spaces with or without other components such as information, training or support. To ensure the cost-effectiveness of condom distribution

programmes, NICE recommendations highlight the importance of advertising condom distribution schemes to populations at higher risk of contracting STIs.(49) This includes ensuring that schemes for young people aged up to sixteen years are tailored to their individual needs, with consideration of extending such tailored schemes to those aged 25 and below, and integrated within existing young people's services and support for sexual/reproductive health, alcohol and drug, mental health and partner violence.(49) Guidelines also suggest services should consider extending tailored condom schemes to young people aged twenty-five and below.(49) In addition to the benefits to reducing prevalence of STIs, the NICE report highlights how condom use can help prevent unplanned-pregnancy, thus improving the cost-effectiveness of condom distribution schemes.(49)

Current policy context

It is important that health care providers and decision-makers can identify ways to counter the declining use of condoms amongst young people. The Department of Health and Social Care (DHSC) has published the first Men's Health Strategy for England which seeks to improve the health and wellbeing of all men in England.(4) The Strategy includes tangible actions to provide the right support to enable men to make healthier choices and to prevent and tackle the biggest health problems affecting men of all ages. It recognises the importance of good sexual health and the links between alcohol and drug use and sexual behaviours which increase a person's risk of harm, such as condomless sex. It is important that health care providers and decision-makers can identify ways to counter the declining use of condoms amongst young people. However, whilst evidence suggests that provision of better sexual health services can help with condom use, it is also important to understand the underlying views of young people about condom use, in order that influencing factors can be adequately addressed. Integral to the effectiveness of sexual health services, and advice and guidance, for ensuring men's sexual health is the provision and promotion of condom use. This is particularly the case amongst young men, where evidence shows declining use over the last ten years.(1)

This research also relates to the new HIV Action Plan for England which DHSC, UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA) and National Health Service England (NHSE) published on 1st December 2025.(46) The Plan sets out 5 key objectives to end HIV transmissions in England by 2030, including ensuring equitable access and uptake of HIV prevention programmes. To ensure that interventions to improve provision and awareness of condoms are effective, it is important to understand what factors influence condom use amongst young people in England.

Better understanding of attitudes to condom use among young Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Trans Plus (LGBTQ+) people could also support the LGBTQ+ Health Evidence Review.⁽⁴⁷⁾ This review is seeking to understand the barriers to healthcare for LGBTQ+ people; the health inequalities that LGBTQ+ people face; LGBTQ+ access, experience and outcomes; and evaluate solutions that address LGBTQ+ health inequalities. It aims to provide expert insight and recommendations and build a foundation for future action on health inequalities.

Finally, the research supports the UK 5-year action plan for antimicrobial resistance 2024 to 2029, by improving the evidence for effective interventions which reduce the need for, and unintentional exposure to, antimicrobials.⁽⁴⁸⁾ It directly contributes to the Plan's research priorities, which include preventing the spread of antimicrobial resistance.

Existing research

There is an abundance of research on factors influencing condom use amongst young people, but to date there has been relatively little research which draws together evidence from UK-based studies. Several systematic reviews have considered factors influencing condom use globally^(5, 6) and in specific countries, including USA,^(7, 8) Southern Africa⁽⁹⁾ and Nigeria and Rwanda.⁽⁷⁾ Although not specifically focused on condom use, one systematic review considers young people's perceptions of contraception service delivery in the UK (n=59 studies), which describes embarrassment and limited accessibility via pubs and nightclubs as barriers to obtaining condoms.⁽⁵¹⁾ However, this evidence is derived from only two of 59 studies included, which are the only mention of condoms in the review.⁽⁵¹⁾ Furthermore, the review is now 14 years old (published in 2011).⁽⁵¹⁾ From our scoping of the evidence base, we are aware of a pool of studies published in the last 10 years which use qualitative and quantitative methods (e.g. surveys) to explore young people's perceptions of factors influencing condom use in the UK. Thus, there is a need for an up-to-date review which addresses this question.

Aim and Research Questions

Aim

The aim of this rapid systematic review is to identify what factors influence condom use amongst young people (aged 15-24) in the UK, and to identify where these factors are different for groups within this population group. These groups may include those associated with health inequities, such as sex, gender, ethnicity, socio-economic status and age, as well as those who face specific challenges in avoiding unplanned pregnancy and/or STIs, including men who have sex with men, sex workers and trans people.

Research questions:

1. What factors influence condom use among young people within the UK?
2. How do these factors vary for different groups of young people including those associated with health inequities, and groups who face specific challenges in avoiding unplanned pregnancy and/or STIs?

Methods

This review was conducted and reported in accordance with established guidance on the conduct(10) and reporting of systematic reviews.(11) As this was a rapid systematic review, we accelerated the process of the review by ensuring we only extracted data which was directly relevant to the review findings,(12) and by adapting a pre-existing framework for use in the synthesis.(15) The review protocol was registered prospectively on PROSPERO prior to completion of full-text screening.(13)

Inclusion criteria:

Population

Young people of any gender (aged 15-24 years) as reported in the abstract of the study.

Subgroups may include, but are not limited to:

- Sex/gender;
- Ethnicity;
- Index of multiple deprivation (IMD);
- Age (e.g. under 18s and 18+);
- Men who have sex with men (MSM);
- Sex workers;
- Trans people.

Phenomenon of interest

Include:

Factors influencing condom use/non-use as represented by the population discussing:

- Their direct experiences of condom use;
- Experiences of interventions which aim to increase condom use.

Use/non-use could encompass: Condomless sex, including but not limited to:

- Unsafe sex;

- Risky sexual behaviour;
- “Stealthing” (removal of condom before/during sex without partner knowledge).

Possible factors influencing condom use, including but not limited to:

1) Social norms:

- Community/Societal norms, including gender/power imbalance.

2) Service-level factors:

- Organisational e.g. service accessibility;
- Relevance to intended target population.

3) Inter-personal factors:

- Specific situations (e.g. type of partner;
- Non-consensual sex;
- Duration of relationship.

4) Intra-personal factors:

- Awareness of benefits of/risks of not using condoms (e.g. pregnancy prevention, STI and HIV prevention);
- Ability to access and use condoms;
- Willingness/attitudes/beliefs towards condom use.

Exclude:

- Studies exploring relationship between population characteristics and frequency/prevalence of condom use.

Context

Any health, social, educational or third sector setting within the UK.

Study design:

Include:

- Qualitative studies including (but not limited to) those based on interviews, focus groups, ethnographic approaches, case studies;
- Studies based on surveys/questionnaires which include open questions;
- Experimental studies with a qualitative component.

Exclude:

- Experimental studies without a qualitative component;

- Survey based studies which use closed questions;
- Cost-effectiveness studies;
- Modelling studies;
- Systematic, scoping and mapping reviews;
- Abstracts or conference proceedings;
- Research protocols;
- Letters, comments, editorial or discussion pieces;
- Book chapters.

Date limit

2014 to date of search.

Country limit

UK studies only.

Language limit

English language studies only.

Search strategy

We searched the following bibliographic databases MEDLINE ALL (including MEDLINE In-Process), Embase and APA PsycInfo (all via Ovid), and CINAHL (via EBSCO). The search strategy combined the search term “condom*” and synonyms for condomless sex/intercourse (e.g. “unsafe sex”) with search terms for young adult. We used the NICE UK geographic search filter for databases where this was available (MEDLINE and Embase).(52) For databases where there is no UK geographic filter available (APA PsycInfo and CINAHL), we used a study type filter for qualitative and survey studies. A combination of free-text terms (i.e. title and abstract terms) and indexing terms (e.g. MeSH in MEDLINE) were used. The search was date limited from 2014 to 10th September 2025 and to English language studies only. The search strategies for each database are reproduced in full in [Appendix 1](#), along with the number of hits retrieved for each database in Table A1 also in [Appendix 1](#).

We also undertook backward and forward citation searches of included studies via the automated function in EPPI-Reviewer v6.17 (EPPI Centre, UCL Social Research Institute, University College London), and searched the following websites:

- Brook <https://www.brook.org.uk/>
- Natsal <https://www.natsal.ac.uk/>

Additionally, we asked stakeholders for recommendations of any known studies for consideration for inclusion.

Study selection

All reviewers (LS, SB, CMP, NO) applied our initial inclusion criteria to a sample (n=158) of title and abstracts to check clarity and applicability within EPPI-Reviewer v6.17. Decisions on this sample were discussed in a group meeting to ensure consistent application of criteria. Following this, two reviewers applied the inclusion and exclusion criteria to the title and abstract of each identified citation. The priority screening function was activated in EPPI-Reviewer v6.17 whilst screening but all records were still screened by two reviewers. Disagreements were resolved through discussion. Full texts of each record were also independently screened by two reviewers, with disagreements resolved through discussion or referral to a third reviewer as required.

EPPI-Reviewer v6.17 was used to support record management and screening, and a PRISMA-style flowchart was produced to detail the study selection process, and reason for exclusion of each record retrieved at full text reported.

Data extraction and critical appraisal

A standardised data extraction coding set was developed in Excel and used to collect the following descriptive data from each included study:

- First author;
- Date of publication;
- Title of publication;
- Study location;
- Study aims and summary of findings;
- Context;
- Target population;
- Recruitment method;
- Participant characteristics;
- Inclusion criteria;
- Study setting;
- Data collection method;
- Data analysis performed;
- Intervention characteristics (where applicable);
- Quantity of text available for synthesis.

First and second-order construct data (participant quotes and author interpretation, respectively) relevant to the phenomenon of interest for this review from the results and discussion sections of all included studies was coded using NVivo (see below for a description of this process).(53)

Critical appraisal was undertaken by one reviewer and checked by a second on all included studies using the Wallace Checklist, with any disagreements settled through discussion or referral to a third reviewer.(14)

Synthesis

Descriptive characteristics of all included studies were tabulated and summarised narratively. This descriptive data were used to categorise studies into three groups, 'High', 'Medium' or 'Low'³ according to the quantity and richness of data available for synthesis relevant to the aims of the review. This process informed the order in which studies were entered into the framework synthesis.

For the first stage of the framework synthesis, one author (LS) entered the first and second-order data from studies with the highest quantity of interpretative and/or descriptive data (n=11 articles) using NVivo, into a framework informed by the socio-economic framework proposed by Aventin et al.(9) This framework was chosen as the initial starting point for the best-fit framework synthesis as it reflects the findings of a systematic review of qualitative evidence examining determinants of condom use in adolescents living in South Africa.(15, 54) Whilst the context was South Africa, the themes generated were sufficiently high-level and general enough to be applicable to the UK context.(9) Studies which included the views and/or experience of potentially vulnerable groups were also included in this initial stage. Following the deductive application of the framework to the data, LS inductively coded the data within these overarching, a priori themes, grouping conceptually similar descriptive codes together within preliminary subthemes.

For the second stage of the framework synthesis, we applied the revised framework to the second group of studies containing a high/medium quantity of descriptive data relevant to the aims of this review (n=11 articles). During this stage, we added further descriptive codes to the framework and iteratively revised subtheme labels as appropriate to ensure they reflected the content. The position of both descriptive codes and subthemes changed within the framework as coding progressed to reflect our understanding of the data. This was to ensure we maintained

³High=over one page, Medium=two paragraphs, Low<two paragraphs.

conceptual consistency within themes and conceptual differentiation across themes. We applied the second version of the framework to the third and final group of studies (n=7 articles) which contained a lower quantity of descriptive data relevant to our review aims. During this stage, a second-reviewer (SB) checked the coding of a sub-sample of 7 studies, where the boundaries of the phenomenon of interest for this review (factors influencing condom use) were less clear, to ensure all relevant data had been incorporated into the framework. Throughout inductive and deductive coding, LS checked the content of previously coded papers against any newly identified descriptive codes in an iterative process.

Following coding of all included studies, the preliminary themes and subthemes were discussed with two members of the review team (SB, RG). These discussions informed revision of the labelling of themes and sub-themes and how these were grouped, drawing on existing theory from the Health Beliefs Model.⁽⁵⁵⁾ These were revised again through further discussion with the wider team (JTC, CMP, LA).

Patient and public involvement

After several months of outreach to potential collaborators, we established a partnership with a London-based charity addressing sexual health inequalities among Black, Brown and Global Majority, and LGBTQ+ communities through culturally specific interventions. Despite existing demands on their time, the charity agreed to support engagement with young people and advised that in-person sessions would be most appropriate.

The charity approached several schools within their network, one of which expressed interest. However, it took several additional months of negotiation with the school to build sufficient trust to enable on-site engagement, pending sign-off by senior management. The intention was to conduct a series of in-person group sessions with young people aged 16 and over. This age threshold was selected in line with local policies at the University of Exeter, which require parental consent for individuals under 16 to participate in PPIE activities. In consultation with the charity, it was agreed that requesting parental consent for discussions relating to condom use preferences would be inappropriate and potentially prohibitive to participation.

In preparation, we met with a youth worker from the charity to co-design an interactive, group-based session to explore key findings from the report, and travel arrangements to London were made. However, by the time the report had been completed and submitted for peer review, final approval from the school's senior management team had not yet been granted. Although the

charity indicated willingness to identify an alternative community group, the additional time required for this process extended beyond the duration of the project.

Subsequently, our patient and public involvement lead (LA) met with two young people aged approximately 19 years for a single 1-hour online meeting to gather their feedback on the main findings from this review. This feedback supported us to sense-check our findings and will support further development of the synthesis for publication in future journal articles.

Protocol deviations

We were unable to include PPI in the development of the protocol or subsequent review processes prior to discussion of the synthesis due to the rapid time frame for this review. This was further complicated by the preparatory work required to identify a suitable group of individuals with lived experience, and challenges of arranging a time and location to meet to talk about a sensitive topic.

Findings

Study identification

The bibliographic database searches identified 8119 records. This reduced to 6297 following de-duplication. Of these, 91 records were included at title and abstract screening. Full-texts (i.e. study reports, which included journal articles, theses, grey literature reports and monographs) were successfully retrieved for all 91 records. Of these, 67 were excluded for the following reasons: wrong country (n=14); population (n=9); phenomenon of interest (n=9); study design (n=13); date (n=1); conference abstract (n=18); duplicate record (n=3). Additionally, 1065 records were identified via backward and forward citation searching of the 24 included full-texts from bibliographic database searches. Of these, 21 were included following title and abstract screening. Full-texts were successfully retrieved for all 21 records. Of these, 18 were excluded for the following reasons: wrong country (n=4); population (n=3); phenomenon of interest (n=5); study design (n=2); date (n=1); duplicate (n=2). We also identified two relevant full-texts from searching websites, one of which was also recommended by stakeholders.(21, 44)

In total, 29 full-texts were included in the review, comprising 25 individual qualitative studies.(16-44) This process is represented in the PRISMA flow diagram in Figure 1. A table with reasons for exclusion for each individual full-text excluded is presented in Table A2 in [Appendix 2](#).

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram

Key characteristics of included studies

The key characteristics of included studies are presented in Table A3 in [Appendix 3](#). In the following section, we narratively summarise the detail presented in Table A3. The 29 full-text study reports included three grey literature reports (including one in slide show format),(21, 33, 44) one thesis,(40) one monograph(30) and 24 journal articles.(16-20, 22-29, 31, 32, 34-39, 41-43) The earliest publication date was 2014 (n=4)(22-24, 31) and the most recent was 2025 (n=1).(41)

All studies were conducted in the UK. Sixteen studies were set solely in England (n=17 study reports),(16-18, 23, 24, 27-31, 35, 37, 39-43) four studies were set in Scotland(22, 33, 34, 36, 38) and four studies were set across the UK, albeit the Safetxt study, which included a UK wide survey, also included interviews with participants from England only.(19-21, 25, 26, 44) One study did not report the specific setting other than it was clear that it was a UK-based study.(32)

All of the studies used qualitative research methods to collect data, including semi-structured interviews (n=13 [n=16 study reports]),(16, 18-20, 22, 23, 25-30, 35, 40-42) in-depth interviews (n=1),(43) conversational interviews combined with ethnography (n=1),(37) unspecified interviews (n=4)(17, 24, 32, 44) and focus groups (n=8 [n=9 study reports])(17, 21, 25, 26, 31, 35, 36, 38, 43). Qualitative data were also collected through open survey questions (n=6 [n=7 study reports]),(19, 21, 22, 31, 33, 34, 44) a Think Aloud study (n=1),(39) workshops (n=1 [n=2 study reports]),(33, 34) interactive activities (n=1)(17) and small group discussions (n=1) (see Table 1).(30) Eleven studies (14 study reports) combined multiple qualitative research methods.(17, 19, 21, 22, 25, 26, 30, 31, 33-35, 37, 43, 44) Additional detail on the methods used, including recruitment and analysis methods, is available in Table A4 in [Appendix 4](#).

Ten studies reported qualitative data which specifically relates to an intervention that aimed to improve condom use amongst young people (n=12 study reports).(18, 19, 21, 24-26, 29-32, 39, 42) The remaining studies collected data on young people's attitudes to condom use without focusing on a specific intervention relating to increase condom use, although interventions were still sometimes mentioned in these studies (n=15 [17 study reports]).(16, 17, 20, 22, 23, 27, 28, 33-38, 40, 41, 43, 44) A summary of the key characteristics of interventions is presented in Table A5 in [Appendix 5](#).

Five studies included only male participants (n=6 study reports)(18, 22, 35, 40-42) and one study included only female participants.(32) The remaining studies include both male and female participants, including two which also reported trans male, trans female or trans gender

participants (n=3 study reports).(21, 33, 34) Two studies included non-binary participants, (19, 25, 26, 33, 34) with no studies including intersex participants. Ten studies only included participants within the age range specified in our inclusion criteria (i.e. 15-24 years) (n=13 study reports).(19, 22, 25-27, 29, 33-39) Nine studies included participants who were framed as young people, but whose ages spanned a greater range than our eligible population (i.e. ranging from aged 11 to 26 years), or where the range was not specified in sufficient detail (e.g. participants under the age of 19).(16-18, 24, 28, 31, 40-42, 44) The remaining study included young people as well as participants who were significantly older than our eligible population, including up to the age of 70.(43) In the latter study, we were able to identify data which related to young people. Ethnicity was reported in 15 studies (n=17 study reports).(17-20, 22, 27, 28, 30, 33-35, 37, 38, 40-43) One study included only White participants (all male).(35) Two studies included only Black participants (n=3 study reports)(40, 41, 43) one with all male participants,(40, 41) and one with both male and female.(43) One study included only women of Indian origin.(37) Other studies which reported ethnicity included a mix of ethnicities.

Sixteen studies reported the sexuality of participants (n=19 study reports).(16, 19-21, 25, 28, 30, 32-38, 40-44) Seven studies included only heterosexual participants (n=8 study reports).(16, 28, 35, 37, 38, 40, 41, 43) One study included two separate cohorts, one of which included only young heterosexual participants (aged 16-25); the other cohort included only MSM with no upper age limit.(30) An additional nine studies included participants which were not limited to heterosexual participants, including homosexual, bisexual, gay/lesbian, pansexual, asexual, queer and omnisexual participants (n=11 study reports).(19-21, 25, 26, 32-34, 36, 42, 44) The remaining studies did not report the sexuality of participants (n=9).(17, 18, 22-24, 27, 29, 31, 39)

Critical appraisal

The quality appraisal scores for each individual study are presented in Table A6 in [Appendix 6](#). All the studies were considered to have a clear research question, and all but one (which was rated 'Can't Tell') were considered to have an appropriate study design to answer the research question.(16) In the study assessed as 'Can't tell' the focus of the study was changed after commencing, without clearly changing the study design.(16) The theoretical perspectives of the researchers were rated as clear in fewer than half of the studies (n=9). In all but one study (marked as 'Can't Tell') the findings were clearly substantiated by the data,(42) and in all the studies where an intervention was the focus of the study the intervention was considered to be clearly described. The quality appraisal scores for data collection and analysis were more mixed. Data collection was considered not clearly described or 'Can't Tell' in seven studies.(17, 21, 24, 32, 36-

38) Evidence that data collection was rigorously conducted was considered either absent or not clear in 12 studies (n=13 study reports).(16, 18, 21, 24, 28, 31-34, 36, 37, 42, 44) Evidence that the analysis of data was rigorously conducted was also considered to be absent or not clear in 12 studies.(16, 21, 24, 28, 31, 33, 34, 37, 39, 42, 44) Limitations in the data were self-reported in all but three studies (n=4 study reports).(21, 28, 33, 34, 39)

The median number of items on which studies scored positively was 10, with ten studies scoring below this (range four to nine).(16, 21, 24, 28, 31-33, 36, 37, 44)

Framework synthesis

This section of the report details the findings arising from the framework synthesis. (15, 54) The four themes are informed by the socio-ecological model proposed by Aventin et al., 2021:(9)

1. Social and community norms which may indirectly influence condom use;
2. Institutional factors associated with sexual health services and school education which may support, or hinder condom use in young people;
3. Inter-personal factors between individuals in a sexual relationship;
4. Intra-personal factors.

The inter-relationship between these themes is illustrated in

Figure 2. This conceptualisation of condom use in young people proposes that young people’s personal views of condom use, and their ability and decision to use them reflects complex interactions with, and learning from, sexual partners and health and educational services. These interactions are in turn informed by wider societal and community behavioural norms associated with sex, gender and peer and romantic relationships.

Each of the four themes is divided into contributing subthemes. The key factors which may influence condom use are summarised in a table at the start of each subtheme and then explored

narratively. Within each table, references to studies which scored positively on nine or lower Wallace checklist items (median score: 10 of a possible 15) are highlighted in red to provide an overview on the quality of the conduct/reporting of studies supporting each subtheme. Reference to the views and experiences of potentially vulnerable populations captured within specific studies are highlighted within this narrative synthesis. An overall summary is provided at the end of each theme.

Figure 2. Conceptual model

Theme 1: Societal and community norms

Twenty studies (21 articles) contribute towards this overarching theme which examines how societal and community norms can indirectly influence reported condom use in young people.(16-19, 22-24, 28, 29, 31-33, 35-38, 40-44) This theme contains four inter-related subthemes. 1.1 Stigmatisation of sexual (n=15) behaviour explores how stigmatisation around sex can impact on young people's sexual behaviour and risk taking. 1.2 Different standards of acceptable sexual behaviour illustrate how disparity in gender norms may impact young people's reported condom use, and how this can be observed within different social and cultural contexts. 1.3 Influence of peers and family explores the role these two groups play in shaping young people's attitudes towards sex and the necessity of condom use. 1.4 Media highlights the role of pornography, social media and popular culture in shaping societal views towards sex and as a source of information for young people.

1.1 Stigmatisation of sexual behaviour

Sixteen studies (17 articles) contained data relating to the stigmatisation of sexual behaviour at societal level,(16-18, 22, 23, 28, 29, 32, 33, 35-38, 40-42, 44) seven of which scored positively on nine or fewer items on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist.(16, 28, 32, 33, 36, 37, 44) Table 1 summarises how indirect factors such as the stigmatisation of sex, association of promiscuity with sexually transmitted diseases (STIs), the fear of young people's sexuality and the impact of religious communities can influence reported condom use in young people. These factors are then summarised narratively below, supported by direct participant quotes.

Table 1. Stigmatisation of sexual behaviour - potential impact on condom use

Factors indirectly influencing reported condom use (n studies)	Included concepts	Related themes/subthemes
Stigmatisation of sex (n=9) (16-18, 22, 28, 36-38, 40, 41)	Accessing sexual health services(28)	2.0: Institutional factors
	Accessing knowledge(38)	2.0: Institutional factors and 4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills
	Accessing peer/family support(38, 40)	1.3: Influence of peer and family
	Reported condom use in causal relationships(16)	3.3: Trust and familiarity
	Fears over young people's sexuality (see below)	
Stigmatisation of STIs (n=4) (16, 22, 28, 35)	STI risk minimisation(22, 35)	4.3: Attitudes towards condoms and outcome expectancies
	Reinforcement of masculine identity through derogation of women and/or MSM(22, 35)	
	Fear of negative consequences(16, 22)	4.3: Attitudes towards condoms and outcome expectancies
Female sexual pleasure (n=2) (32, 37)	Knowledge and skills re: condom use, empowerment (see 1.0: Intrapersonal factors)(32, 37)	2.0: Institutional factors & 4.2 Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills
Ethnicity (n=1) (42)	Acceptability of accessing learning opportunities regarding condom use(42)	4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills
Fears over young people's sexuality (n=3) (17, 36, 38)	Heteronormative, skills-focused sex education based on prevention, avoidance and abstinence messages(17)	2.2: Inadequate school education
	Barriers to accessing services(36)	2.1: Health services
Religion (n=5) (23, 29, 33, 37, 44)	Parental support(38)	1.3: Influence of peers and family
	Protective factor against engaging in risky sex(23)	4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills
	Knowledge and skills relating to sex and condom use(23)	4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills
	Engagement with health/educational services(29)	2.1: Health services
	Exclusion of educational content in faith-based schools(33, 37, 44)	2.2: Inadequate school education

Red text: Studies which scored positively on ≤ 9 items on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist.

Nine studies (10 articles) contained data emphasising societal stigmatisation of sexual behaviour.(16-18, 22, 28, 36-38, 40, 41) Six of these studies (seven articles) reported data which highlighted stigmatisation of sexual behaviour at a societal level,(16, 18, 22, 28, 38-40) with three studies specifically referencing fears relating to young peoples' engagement with sex across different types of community.(17, 36, 38) Such stigma was expressed amongst both young men and women as a reluctance to talk about sex, with some regarding it as a taboo topic:(18, 38)

Sexual health is quite a funny one, it's quite a silent mentality towards it. So, let's talk about other people's opinions. I reckon some people would prefer it online [Male, 21 yrs, proHIS intervention] (Beford et al., 2024)(18)

You Americans are always talking about sex. Blah, blah, blah, it doesn't matter who you're with, you keep going on about it." And a girl chimed in, "It's always all about that. It is in every bloody movie, video, and song. Is that all you ever think about?" A male in another group laughed when he said, "You just aren't going to find that here, all that open sex talk. We are way more private, even with our friends. The topic just doesn't come up with us like that." Several teens chimed in agreement when one girl said, "All these details...it's really a taboo topic. No one is gonna be chatting with their friends about using protection or getting tested. Too personal (Morrison-Beedy et al., 2019)

As we be saying, no one is talking about how to talk about all this sex stuff [Male] (Morrison-Beedy et al, 2019)(38)

"Promiscuous" behaviour was viewed negatively by young people, particularly with regard to women (see 1.2: Different standards for acceptable sexual behaviour) and viewed as a behaviour associated with increased risk of STIs.(16, 22, 28) Thus, at a societal level there appears to be a perception of sex and by extension those who engage in "too much" of it as "dirty". The above quote illustrates that the shame associated with sex may make it a "taboo" topic. Below, three quotes illustrate how such stigma can cause young people difficulty when trying to access sexual health services:(28, 36)

I think people are a bit scared to do so... I've tried to go to a sex clinic to get free condoms but was a bit scared like I always want someone to come with me... I don't know, it's embarrassing. It's embarrassing like people might be judging you or the nurses might look at you and like "ah is she the type that does this sort of thing?"... I actually haven't. I've just gone there then walked out [Female university student, British] (Jaspal et al., 2020)(28)

I remember when I had to do that once I felt quite uncomfortable personally going to a clinic. It's not my environment but I didn't know where I could find one I had to google it and things like that before I could find somewhere to go [Female university student, British] (Jaspal et al., 2020)(28)

But I think the main issue is the people in the community rather than there being a lack of services, I think if there was services people still probably wouldn't use them because of the way people would think about them [Male, Outer Hebrides] (MacGilleEthain et al., 2023)(36)

These two studies illustrate how embarrassment of the topic and lack of awareness on how to find appropriate services may hinder young people's access to sexual health services (see 2.0: Institutional factors and 4.1 Psychological characteristics). They also highlight that even among communities with more 'liberal' social attitudes, fear of the perceived stigma associated with sexual activity still remain.(28, 36)

Societal stigma may also be reinforced by the views of parents, which may also reduce the likelihood of young people turning to them for advice and support on sexual health (see 1.3:Communication and peer pressure):(38, 40)

My mum wasn't going to explain it to me. As I got older my dad has expressed he would have been calm with everything like that. All I had to do was explain it to him. I just didn't so he just didn't say anything. It was one of those ones [Black heterosexual male, 24] (Nwaosu et al., 2023)(40)

I don't know anyone who is talking to their parents about this. They'll just be like, 'Just, if you do, be safe about it, but don't tell anybody.' Really just don't talk about it (Morrison-Beedy et al., 2019)(38)

Parental reluctance to discuss condom use may reduce young people's access to information regarding how to access and use condoms and increase their reluctance to engage with sexual health services through fear of their parents finding out.

Young people in five studies reflected on how some religious and faith-based communities can influence sexual behaviour, potential engagement with sexual health services and delivery of sex education.(23, 29, 33, 37, 44)

Yeah, I think some people might be, may be offended if they were asked you know, people who never had sex or whatever, or like people who are religious [Male, age 20, Bournemouth and Poole] (Jones et al., 2017)(29)

Schools need to have better sex education, regardless of religion. I went to a catholic school and did not receive proper, accurate sex education. They spoke about the devil and the teacher did not use scientific language, he said "lady parts" because he was too uncomfortable [Survey participant, 19] (Winters et al., 2024)(44)

The first quote illustrates how some services may be reluctant to offer advice on condoms through fear of offending young people from religious backgrounds.(29) The other quote indicates the influence that some faith-based communities have over the content of sex education,(44) with young people from one study perceiving the deliberate exclusion of content relating to contraception in faith based schools.(33, 34) One study indicated that cultural norms may act as a protective factor against condomless sex, through encouraging sexual abstinence before marriage.(23) However, one study conducted with Sikh women of Indian heritage indicated that encouragement of sexual abstinence before marriage meant that when they did engage in sex, they were less well equipped to do so safely.(37)

1.2 Different standards of acceptable sexual behaviour

Eleven studies (11 articles) highlighted disparity in gender norms between how sexual behaviour, particularly "promiscuity", was perceived in men compared to women,(16, 22, 23, 28, 31-33, 35,

37, 40, 43) six of which scored positively on nine or fewer items on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist.(16, 28, 31-33, 37) Below we describe how these gender norms varied depending on cultural and societal contexts and how these sexual norms influenced certain sexual behaviour in young people trying to establish their own identity in relation to their peers (see 4.1: Psychological factors and 1.3: Influence of peers and family). Table 2 summarises how wider societal norms can be linked to intra-, inter- and institutional factors related to reported condom use.

Table 2. Different standards for acceptable sexual behaviour - potential impact on condom use

Factors indirectly influencing reported condom use (n studies)	Included concepts	Related themes/subthemes
Disparity in gender norms (n=11)(16, 22, 23, 28, 31-33, 35, 37, 40, 43)	Sex with a number of partners perceived more positively in men(16, 28, 31, 32, 35, 43)	
	Identifying “risky” partners (16, 22, 35)	4.3: Attitudes towards condoms and outcome expectancies
	Protecting, challenging and reinforcing masculine and feminine identities (28, 35, 37, 40, 43)	See 4.1: Psychological characteristics
	Denigration of women seen as “promiscuous” Perception of risk(35)	
	Heteronormative gender dynamics)(35, 43)	See 3.1: Heteronormative gender dynamics
	Access to social support(28, 33)	See 1.3: Influence of peers and family
	Access to services(31, 33)	See 2.0: Institutional factors
	Unequal burden of contraception on women(33)	See 3.1: Heteronormative gender dynamics
Setting: University context (n=4)(16, 23, 28, 30)	Heteronormative sex education (see 2.0: Institutional factors)(33)	
	Emancipation/empowerment, knowledge, decision making effort	See 4.0: Intrapersonal factors
Ethnicity/culture (n=4)(23, 28, 37, 43)	Knowledge of safe sex)(23, 28, 37)	See 4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills
	Negotiating safe sex(23, 37)	See 3.1: Heteronormative gender dynamics
	Knowledge of own preferences(37)	See: 4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills
	Emancipation, empowerment and rebellion(37)	See 1.0: Intrapersonal factors
	Acceptability of concurrent relationship-use of condoms in casual/side relationships (43)	See 3.3: Trust and familiarity

Red text: Studies which scored positively on ≤ 9 items on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist.

All eleven studies contributing to this subtheme contained data illustrating disparity between how sexual behaviour was viewed in men compared to women.(16, 22, 23, 28, 31-33, 35, 37, 40, 43) Six of these studies indicated that amongst heterosexual men, a higher number of sexual partners was viewed positively, with perceived sexual prowess being linked to social status

amongst male peers (see 1.3: influence of peers and family), whilst they labelled the same behaviour by women as “promiscuous” or “dirty”:(16, 28, 31, 32, 35, 43)

The typical view of guys is that they are like boasting to their guy friends about what they have done but there is certain amount of exaggeration in that I am sure [Female university student, 18-19yrs] (Chanikra et al., 2014)(23)

If she has been with loads of people she’s more likely to have a disease isn’t she? (Male, 17yrs; socially excluded) (Limmer et al., 2016)(35)

Boys seem better when they get them [condoms], girls get called slags but it’s good for the boys.’; ‘You always hear boys going round saying that they’ve got one making themselves look big but lasses don’t say nowt (Kinsella et al., 2014)(31)

The second quote illustrates how women, but not men, were seen as "vectors of disease" despite similar behaviour, with the final quote suggesting that women who engage in sex are seen as “promiscuous”, which may interfere with their access to or engagement with services intended to promote condom use (see 2.0 Institutional factors).(31, 33) This in turn may negatively impact their knowledge around how to engage in safe, consensual sex (see 3.1: Heteronormative gender dynamics) as illustrated by a Sikh woman describing her first sexual encounter with her partner, during which they did not use a condom:(37)

Interviewer: How did that [virginity] make you feel?

Female participant: Felt a little bit inferior to be honest that he had all these experiences and I had none and yeah it was the inferiority thing really that’s it. He didn’t say anything about taking my virginity. I am guessing he is a little bit smug. It’s quite an achievement from him. I have many male friends that they like having a virgin. It’s quite a big deal so I am sure he was quite happy about it [Female, Sikh-Indian heritage] (Mahendru et al., 2020)(37)

This illustrates that women can also experience shame in having little experience of sex, which can make them vulnerable when they begin navigating sexual relationships. Data from three studies indicated how this could be a particular issue for women from cultures with expectations that women “preserve” their virginity until marriage:(23, 28, 37)

he made his intentions very clear from earlier on and I kept saying no, no, no. He said that I find you very attractive and you know is there any possibility of having sex. I said no at first and then I was curious because especially in the western world sex is everywhere and I wanted to see what the big deal was, so out of curiosity so it wasn’t [pause] he enjoyed it more than I did. He pushed me in to it a little bit. But not really. I did regret it afterwards I had to admit but yeah I was a virgin then [Female, Sikh-Indian heritage] (Mahendru et al., 2020)(37)

This illustrates how some young women may be particularly vulnerable to male coercion (see 3.2: Spectrum of communication) and can agree to sex for which they were practically and

emotionally unprepared as a form of exploration or rebellion against strict cultural and parental norms (see 4.1: Psychological factors).(37) Data from three studies indicated that for both young men and women attending university, a period of sexual liberation outside of the parental and societal constraints was generally perceived as the norm:(23, 28, 30)

I think going uni is, yeah, like a big changer... There's a lot more nightlife, do you know what I mean? There's a lot more that goes on like especially like its like you're free from, like from what your parents, like you've got your own place, like you're free, and you can like do whatever you want in that place and also like you might not be able to go back on nights out and stuff, so it's a lot more relaxed. You can do more of what you want. (Male, White British) (Jaspal et al., 2020)(28)

Yeah, yeah, I don't know if this makes me sound like a predator innit but like at the start of the year like girls don't really like have any boyfriends or anything like that. They come to uni more free and it's easier to like sleep with 'cos during the year like they might be seeing someone or get boyfriends or whatever so it gets harder as times go on [Male, British South Asian] (Jaspal et al., 2020)(28)

...the culture here [UK] is also supportive for this type of behaviours [risky sex]...which is not really possible in some other areas of the world (Chanikra et al., 2014)(23)

Before uni I've been like really like blocked in, not being able to go out a lot so like being at uni kinda like excited me I thought "ohhhh [laughing] I get to mess about a bit [Female, White British] (Jaspal et al., 2020)(28)

I think because at home I've been restricted too much I kinda like acted rebellious on things and now I have that freedom it's like "oh maybe it's time for me to like act upon it because I'm independent [Female, White British] (Jaspal et al., 2020)(28)

Such liberation was associated with increased opportunities for meeting potential sexual partners and freedom from parental rules and societal norms, although the perceived peer pressure, particularly among men and use of alcohol increased the risk of condomless sex (see 4.4: Decision making effort).

However, despite the commonly held view that views of sex were more liberal at university where increased sexual exploration was expected by all genders, some people still wished to distance themselves from the stigma they perceived associated with sexual behaviour (see 1.1: Stigmatisation of sex):(23, 28)

For me, it's not me. I knew it wasn't me. I'm not the person to be having sex every single day and all that stuff. I'm not that person. I've realized I'm not that sorta... University shows your true colours for a certain period of time. You've got to realize that's not you and it's not right at all (Female 1, White British) (Jaspal et al., 2020)(28)

I have looked back and I was like "Why did I do this?" "Why was I like this?" and people would assume "oh she's this, she's that" when really there a valid reason behind it (Female 2, White British) (Jaspal et al., 2020)(28)

...I don't really feel that there is that much of a dividing line between how boys act and how girls act. I don't think you can really say right boys are out to get as much as possible and girls are like, they just wait until they get drunk and are taken advantage of. I think it works both ways...I think there are some girls who are just as promiscuous as boys and feel just as good about it and I think that guys sometimes go out and sleep with people and feel slutty as well [Female, 20-24yrs] (Chanikra et al., 2014)(23)

1.3 Communication and peer-pressure

Seventeen studies (18 articles) supported this subtheme, which explores how young people's wider family and peer networks influence their views on sex and condom use,(16, 17, 19, 22-24, 28, 29, 31, 33, 35-38, 40, 41, 43, 44) eight of which scored positively on nine or fewer items of the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist.(16, 24, 28, 31, 33, 36, 37, 44) First, this subtheme explores the challenges young people face in talking to their parents about their sexual relationships and sexual health, before examining the impact peer-relationships can have on the pressures to engage in sexual activity and the acceptability of condom use. Table 3 indicates how indirect social and community factors may be linked with reported condom use.

Table 3. Communication and peer-pressure – potential impact on condom use

Factors indirectly influencing reported condom use (n studies)	Included concepts	Related themes/subthemes
Parents (n=11) (16, 17, 28, 29, 33, 35, 36, 38, 40, 41, 44)	Fear of parents finding out – Access to information and free condoms and desire for privacy(16, 17, 29, 33, 36)	1.3: Communication and peer pressure 2.0: Institutional factors
	Unable to talk about sex with parents-limited knowledge(28, 38, 40, 44)	4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills
Siblings (n=4) (22, 35, 38, 41)	Masculine values and source of sexual educators and role models(22, 35, 38, 41)	1.0 Intrapersonal factors
Peer group views (n=11) (16, 19, 22-24, 31, 33, 38, 41, 43, 44)	Peer-pressure to engage in sex(23, 24, 38, 43)	2.0: Institutional factors 4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills
	Encouraging condom use-Information sharing (16, 19, 22, 24, 31, 44)	
	Culture of reported non-condom use(22, 23, 35, 38)	4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills
Social inclusion/exclusion (n=6) (24, 35-37, 41, 43)	Source of knowledge and support(16, 19, 33, 41)	
	Defining acceptable behavioural norms when it comes to sex (24, 35, 43)	1.2: Different standards of acceptable sexual behaviour
	Social or geographical isolation and help-seeking behaviour(36, 37, 41)	2.0: Institutional factors

Red text: Studies which scored positively on ≤ 9 items on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist.

Data from five studies highlighted young-people’s desire for privacy related to the fear of their parents finding out that they were having sex.(16, 17, 29, 33, 36) This impacted on young people’s ability to access information and advice and free condoms (see 2.0: Institutional factors), particularly for those living in rural communities where young people were dependent on parents for transport.(36) Two studies highlighted that a lack of a private space outside of the parental home was also associated with not using condoms, with young people not using condoms at home for fear of parents finding them afterwards,(33) with some having unsafe sex in outside spaces instead, which led to issues regarding coercion and lack of condom availability (see 3.0 Interpersonal factors and 4.4: Decision making effort).(33, 38) First and second-order construct data from four studies highlighted how young people regardless of gender felt they could not discuss sexual health decision making with their parents:(28, 38, 40, 44)

It would like change the way they looked at you [Female 1, Heterosexual](Morrison-Beedy et al., 2019)(38)

I mean it’s never been openly spoken about before [Female 2, Heterosexual] (Morrison-Beedy et al., 2019)(38)

They could react negatively to it, but you don’t know that...you just don’t want to take the chance [Male] (Morrison-Beedy et al., 2019)(38)

These illustrate how young people may find it difficult to discuss issues relating to sex with parents, through fear of damaging their relationship.(38) Young people highlight the culture amongst some communities of “not talking about sex” (see 1.1: Stigmatisation of sex), to which older generations may be particularly susceptible.(40) Two studies provided data which highlights this issue among some ethnic minority families or conservative rural communities.(36, 40, 41) One participant highlights how she did not feel that her mother would be able to relate to the participant’s experience as a member of the LGBTQ+ communities:(44)

I wouldn't have spoken to my mum... she's lovely but it's not the same lived experience. it's just a difference of experience [Female, LGBTQ+] (Winters et al., 2024,)(44)

This has implications for where LGBTQ+ youth access sex education and support which is relevant to their needs (see 2.0: Institutional factors).(36) Data from one study indicated siblings were a valued source of information on sex and relationships for some young Black men.(41)

When I speak to my brother, he's been there, done that, so he knows [about sex and relationships]. Even though, obviously my parents have been there, he's [my brother] a couple of years older than me so he understands where I'm coming from [Black heterosexual male, 20yrs] (Nwaosu et al., 2025)(41)

Data from four studies highlighted the societal pressure for young people to engage in sexual behaviour.(23, 24, 38, 43)

...so there is this burden on people to lose it [virginity] while they are at university... [and if you] have not lost it then you have this huge thing to lose [Male, 20-24] (Chanikra et al., 2014)(23)

[I] think it's just vanity like “oh my god I need to go out I need to have a good time I need to show I'm good or whatever I'm attractive” and it's like I think it sometimes clouds anything real really [Male, White British] (Jaspal et al., 2020)(28)

These quotes highlight the dilemma young people experience, particularly young men, to engage in heterosexual sex. This pressure to have sex often occurred alongside alcohol and drug use, (23, 38) which has potential implications for unsafe sexual practices (see 4.4: Decision making effort). For young men, sexual prowess was inextricably linked to social status and performance of a masculine identity (see 4.1: Psychological characteristics). Two studies highlighted that this was an issue for men from lower socio-economic and education backgrounds or from black Caribbean communities where concurrent relationships were part of the societal norm.(35, 43) Nine studies highlighted how peer relationships shaped attitudes towards sexual risk and reported condom use (see 4.3: Attitudes towards condoms and outcomes expectancies), as indicated by these quotes:(16, 19, 22-24, 31, 35, 38, 44)

We aren't that type. We don't care about anything like that [contraceptive use] [Male, Scottish young offender institution, 18yrs] (Buston et al., 2014)(22)

No news is good news. If none of your chums brings up something bad about the girl, she must be clean [Male] (Morrison-Beedy et al., 2019)(38)

The second quote indicates how some young people who do not use condoms rely on peer-knowledge of prospective sexual partners to inform their risk assessment and subsequent decision to engage in sex.(35, 38) This appears closely linked to the phenomena, identified in four studies, that men felt able to identify partners at risk of STIs based on superficial characteristics alone. This involved drawing on social stereotypes of socially excluded groups, including women viewed as promiscuous and subsequently labelled “dirty girls”,(35) and men who have sex with men (MSM) who were seen at increased risk of STIs.(30, 33, 41)

you can kinda tell, you know what I mean, hair at the side an' short skirt an' just that sort of stereotype. It's funny, you see people walking around and they just fit your stereotype of that sort of person exactly, an' it's just a bit . . . I wouldn't say it was right for everyone, but the majority of people who are like that tend to be like, easy and stuff, you know what I mean? [Male, aged 15; socially included] (Limmer et al., 2016)(35)

You can tell by the way they speak, the way they act [Male, aged 16; socially excluded] (Limmer et al., 2016)(35)

If I'm hitting on a chick at a library, that's a different scenario, if you're hitting on a chick at the club . . . I mean, it's an assumption that girls at the club sleep around a lot more [Male, University student] (Alam et al., 2021)(16)

These illustrate how the belief some young men held on being able to identify individuals with an STI based on looks and personal characteristics was held across groups with different socio-economic and educational status.(35))(16) For some social groups, this belief appeared to facilitate reported condom use with people they perceived as risky, but in others this was not the case (see 3.0: Interpersonal factors, 4.3: Attitudes towards condoms and perceived outcomes).(16, 35)

Four studies highlighted how peers were an important source of knowledge regarding sex and condom use for young people, as illustrated by two quotes below:(16, 19, 33, 41)

some things you're taught in school, but others you learn over time by hearing about them from friends [Male student] (Alam et al., 2021)(16, 19)

Although I, myself did not use protection due to only being with my long-term partner. This study has helped me pass on vital info to my friends to make sure they stay safe when sleeping with multiple people [Women who has sex with Men (WSM), 18yrs] (Berendes et al., 2023)(19)

The second quote illustrates how often both young men and women taking part in interventions to improve condom use passed on the knowledge they gained to their peers. Data from six studies indicated that young people could encourage condom use through sharing information and resources with their peers,(16, 19, 22, 24, 31, 44) although data from one study highlighted concerns that this could place young people at risk of unwanted consequences such as pregnancy or STIs through incorrect storage of condoms.(44) Overall, studies included in this subtheme indicated that peer-relationships play an important role in defining acceptable behavioural norms in relation to sex and/or condom use,(22, 23, 35, 38) with both social and geographical isolation having an influence on help-seeking behaviour in relation to condom use.(36, 37, 41)

1.4 Media

Six studies (7 articles) contained first- and/or second-order data highlighting how young people's exposure to pornography, music or social media exposed them to and reinforced societal norms regarding sexual relationships and heteronormative gender roles and condom use within these,(23, 33, 35, 40, 41, 43, 44) with two of these scoring positively on nine or fewer items on the Wallace Critical Appraisal checklist.(33, 44) These indirect structural level determinants may be linked to factors which may be more directly related to reported condom use, as illustrated in Table 4. They may also reinforce the different standards of acceptable behaviour held for different population groups (subtheme 1.2) and influence the views and behaviours of peer and family networks (subtheme 1.3). The direct and indirect influence of the media on reported condom use in young people is explored further below.

Table 4. Media - potential impact on condom use

Factors indirectly influencing condom use (n studies)	Factors directly reported condom use	influencing	Related themes/subthemes
Pornography (n=3)(33, 35, 40)	Lack of normalised condom use(33)		4.3: Attitudes towards condoms and outcome expectancies
	Reinforcement of gender norms(35, 40)		1.2: Different standards for acceptable behaviour 3.1: Heteronormative gender dynamics 4.1: Psychological characteristics
	Knowledge of sex/anatomy(40)		2.3: Trust and familiarity
Exposure to/reinforcement of societal norms (n=3)(23, 40, 41, 43)	Attitudes towards concurrent sexual partners(43)		
	Sexual attitudes, perceptions and behaviours (40, 41)		1.2: Different standards for acceptable sexual behaviour 2.1: Heteronormative gender dynamics
	'Risky sex' during university		1.2: Different standards for acceptable sexual behaviour
Exposure to relatable experiences (n=2)(41, 44)	Motivation to buy/use condoms(44)		
	Source of information(41, 44)		
	Affordability/Access to free condoms (44)		2.1: Health services

Red text: Studies which scored positively on ≤ 9 items on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist.

Three studies explored how pornography may influence non-use of condoms and reinforce gender norms in men.(33, 35, 40) One study presented second-order construct data based on workshops with young people stating how porn can eroticise “barebacking” (visualisation of ejaculating on partner) among men who have sex with men and how condom use was not typically seen in pornography.(33) For frequent viewers of pornography, especially those with limited access to alternative views through formal education or peers, this may encourage non-use of condoms to pursue the sexual pleasure and real-life experience of the “fantasy” presented to them.(33) This, combined with the lack of normalisation of condom use may reinforce the focus on the pleasurable aspect of sex, which the use of condoms was perceived to inhibit (see 4.3: Attitudes towards condoms and outcomes expectancies). Participants from two studies indicated that they discovered porn through relatives or friends at a young age:(33, 40)

I would say I discovered porn when I was like 10. Porn was important from the age of 10 probably [Male, 24yrs] (Nwaosu et al., 2023)(40)

Whilst pornography may be an important source of knowledge regarding the mechanics of sex and female anatomy for some men (see 4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills),(40) it may also reinforce heteronormative gender norms and differential standards for acceptable

sexual behaviour through introducing a derogatory view of women (see 1.2 Different stands for acceptable sexual behaviour and 3.1 heteronormative gender dynamics).(35, 40) (40)

This promotion of negative views of women was also seen in rap music and on social media.(40, 43) with Participants from one study with people of black Caribbean ethnicity felt social media could be used to “applaud and encourage” other men and “name and shame women perceived to have multiple partners”.(43) Whilst two studies with black participants indicated that having concurrent partners was viewed as the norm,(40, 43) disparity between the genders regarding the acceptability of having “side” partners could exist (see subtheme 1.2) and be perpetuated by social media use.(43)

One study highlighted how social media was also viewed as a useful way of hearing about other people’s experiences relating to sex by both young men and women:(44)

Social media is much better for hearing people’s experiences. They can tell the truth; their experiences aren’t being controlled by an organisation. I feel much safer looking it up on the internet from reputable orgs, but for experiences I go to social media [AMAB] (Winters et al., 2024)(44)

This illustrates the tension between young people’s desire to obtain trustworthy information relating to sex from health and educational services and their need to hear of experiences to which they could relate. The quote below illustrates how young people from the study found social media to be both helpful and unhelpful in promoting condom use and awareness of services to young people:(44)

I remember almost buying a pack of condoms for like £20 because I thought ‘they’re so good, they have this’ and that’s crazy, you can get them for free. I think it’s easy to do that. Often now influencers get partnerships and people think oh this person is good I’ll do it with them [Forum member] (Winters et al., 2024)(44)

Here the power of social influences in promoting condom use was highlighted through challenging the perception of condoms as “not being cool” (see 4.3: Attitudes towards condoms and outcomes expectancies). However, young adults’ lack of awareness of the availability of free condom schemes and how to access these may make them vulnerable to financial exploitation. Data from one study highlighted that some black young men relied on media sources such as film, music and pornography as an informal source of sex education because of difficulty in talking about sex with their parents due to its stigmatised nature.(41) Data from this study suggested this evidences a particular gap for sex education tailored to the needs of young black boys beginning sexual relationships (see 2.0: Institutional factors).(41)

Summary: Societal and community norms

This theme highlighted how the stigmatisation of sexual behaviour, different standards of acceptable sexual behaviour, communication among family members and peer-pressure, and the media, can influence reported condom use amongst young people. Studies showed how the stigmatisation of sex can impact on young people's sexual behaviour and risk taking, specifically, drawing attention to how young people's perception that sexual activity is met with disapproval from family, peers and wider society, leads to reluctance to engage with support services (including accessing condoms), or may lead to gaps in understanding about condom use where there is unwillingness to speak about sex within certain communities, e.g. within religious communities. Disparity in gender norms may impact young people's reported condom use through the perception that women who obtain condoms are seen negatively (e.g. as "promiscuous"), whereas men who are sexually active, including men who use condoms, are perceived positively (e.g. as demonstrating 'prowess'). The role of peers and family in shaping young people's attitudes towards sex included how male groups may choose not to use condoms as a type of dismissiveness of their sexual partners' needs or wishes – including the perception that men only need to wear condoms if they think a prospective sexual partner was likely to have an STI. Separately, the desire for young people to hide that they are sexually active from their family could lead to sex in spaces with more limited accessibility to condoms, e.g. outside. Pornography was perceived to show condomless sex as the norm, influencing condom use amongst young people. Other media can reinforce derogatory attitudes towards women among some young men and may reinforce societal expectations that sexual behaviour in men is linked to masculine identities and their social status.

Most factors identified within this theme as influencing reported condom use among young people were supported by an approximately equal number of studies scoring above and below the median Wallace checklist score of 10.

Theme 2: Institutional factors

This theme concerns the institutional factors which may influence reported condom use and is supported by 19 studies (24 articles). (16-19, 21, 23-26, 28-34, 36-42, 44) It contains two subthemes, 1) Health services (n=18) and 2) Inadequate school education (n=11). The content of this theme is influenced by the societal and community factors described in theme 1.0 and in turn has implications for inter- and intra-personal factors influencing reported condom use, discussed in themes 3.0 and 4.0.

2.1 Health services

Eighteen studies (22 articles) contributed data to this subtheme which explores how health services can influence reported condom use in young people,(17-19, 21, 23-26, 28-34, 36, 38-42, 44) with seven of these studies (9 articles) scoring nine or lower on the Wallace Critical Appraisal checklist.(21, 24, 28, 31-34, 36, 44) The subtheme explores the importance of a safe, non-judgmental environment, provision of free condoms and trustworthy information, alongside discussion of issues which may impact on the accessibility to sexual health care. Table 5 summaries the key issues discussed and how these may differentially impact on specific groups who are vulnerable to experiencing health inequity.

Table 5. Health services - impact on condom use

Factors directly influencing reported condom use (n studies)	Included concepts	Related themes/subthemes
Safe service environment (n=14) (17, 21, 23-26, 28, 30-34, 36, 40, 41, 44)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Desire for privacy and anonymity(17, 21, 33, 34) 	1.1: Stigmatisation of sex 1.2: Different standards for acceptable sexual behaviour
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Confidentiality(23, 25, 26, 28, 31, 36) 	1.1: Stigmatisation of sex
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Freedom from judgement(21, 24, 28, 30, 32, 40, 41, 44) 	1.1: Stigmatisation of sex
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Friendly, welcoming(24) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No invasive questioning(24, 25) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Easy and discreet access(21, 33) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fear of racism(40, 41) 	
Service access issues (n=11) (18, 21, 25, 29-31, 33, 34, 36, 39, 42, 44)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maintaining young people's independence/agency(34) 	1.1: Stigmatisation of sex 1.3: Communication and peer pressure
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Need to provide up to date and accessible service information online(21, 39) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regional variation in service provision(21, 44) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Young people's need for convenience (e.g. access to free condoms, appointment time(18, 21, 25, 29-31) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Impact of travel time(33, 34, 36) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Online technology issues(44) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consideration needed of people with specific access needs(18, 21, 42) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Impact of COVID(34) 	
Provision of free condoms (n=8) (18, 21, 29, 31-34, 42, 44)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Desired/key motivator for accessing sexual health services(18, 21, 29, 31, 33, 34, 42, 44) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stigma regarding free condoms(33, 34, 44) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of diversity in condoms and lube provided/associated information(21) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Variety of ways to access important(18, 21, 25, 29-31, 34, 44) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Different requirements for packaging: discreet vs not dull and boring(21, 32) 	
Tailoring of intervention content (n=5) (18, 19, 25, 26, 32, 38, 39)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Age(19, 25, 26, 39) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attention span(18, 39) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pre-existing knowledge(18, 26) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Topic of interest(19) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relatable to young people's experience/situation(25, 38, 39) 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application of knowledge/skills to different contexts(38) • Tone: Friendly, natural and non-patronising(26, 32, 39)
Health services a trustworthy source of information (n=5)(21, 25, 33, 34, 38, 39)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of knowledge of marginalized groups(21) • Consideration of needs of specific groups(21, 25, 33, 34)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include development of skills(38, 39)
Service resources (n=4)(18, 21, 29, 39)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sign up of services to provide c-card(21) • Costs(18, 39) • Limited appointment time(21, 29)

Red text: Studies which scored positively on ≤ 9 items on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist.

Data from 14 studies (16 articles) provided data which illustrates young people’s appreciation of a warm and welcoming sexual health service environment, which respected their privacy through maintaining confidentiality and anonymity.(17, 21, 23-26, 28, 30-34, 36, 40, 41, 44) The three quotes below illustrate how the perceived stigma around sex means that young people can find it intimidating and embarrassing to attend sexual-health services (see 1.1: Stigmatisation of sexual behaviour), which can impede access:(24, 28)

I think people are a bit scared to do so... I’ve tried to go to a sex clinic to get free condoms but was a bit scared like I always want someone to come with me...I don’t know, it’s embarrassing. It’s embarrassing like people might be judging you or the nurses might look at you and like “ah is she the type that does this sort of thing?”... I actually haven’t. I’ve just gone there then walked out [British female, university student] (Jaspal et al., 2020)(28)

Often if you go in, it’s embarrassing. You have to talk to a receptionist and you’re worried other people can hear you [British female, university student] (Jaspal et al., 2020)(28)

I think it was just to have a C-Card ‘cos all my friends did really I think, but it was like, I felt really welcome here as well, I don’t think, if I didn’t feel welcome, I wouldn’t have got one, I think I would’ve just left it [Female, 14yrs] (Cheetham et al., 2014)(24)

These indicate young women may be particularly susceptible to accessing sexual health services due to gendered bias in accepted sexual behaviour (see subtheme 1.2) One study indicated that fear of experiencing racism from staff; expressed as judgements of sexual behaviour based on racial stereotypes, was a potential barrier for young heterosexual Black men engaging with sexual health services.(40, 41) Young people indicated a friendly, non-judgemental atmosphere with non-invasive questioning supported them to overcome their fears:(21, 24, 25, 28, 30, 32, 40, 41, 44)

I have received free condoms from a young people's sexual health clinic, the nurses were very friendly and non-judgemental (Brook report 2024)(21)

It [experience at the sexual health clinic] was a positive experience. The woman came to me, she was friendly, told me what the deal is and what's gonna happen. It [the experience at the clinic] was very friendly, very open and helpful to be honest [Black heterosexual male, 18yrs] (Nwaosu et al., 2023)(40)

No shame or judgement. A lot of the time adults can come across as judging or deciding that they know what's best for a young person and that doesn't always help when you're trying to develop your own agency (Winters et al., 2024)(44)

The last quote illustrates the importance of health service staff respecting and supporting young people's agency regarding their sexual health (see 4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills). Data from eight studies (nine articles) indicated young people valued convenient access to advice and condoms, which they could choose to access independently and discreetly. (18, 21, 25, 29-31, 33, 34, 44) Preferred method of access depended on the needs of the young person, with some preferring the anonymity and convenience of accessing advice or ordering condoms online, (17, 21) whilst other young people who lacked private internet access, space for online-appointments, or worried about parents opening their packages, preferred to pick them up in person. (20) This latter option was more challenging for young people in rural communities who relied on their parents for transport. (20, 33, 36) The following quotes illustrate the importance of convenient access to free-condoms for young people: (21, 31)

You get free condoms whenever you need them [and] you can get them from quite a few places as well... there are quite a lot of places (Kinsella et al., 2014)(31)

RE: C-Card scheme: You have to register in person and that's always been the biggest inhibitor to me, seems like it will take a while (Brook report 2024)(21)

Young people shouldn't have to go out of their way to access condoms. They should be able to easily pick them up from somewhere nearby if they need them immediately and be able to order online for them to be delivered as well (Brook report 2024)(21)

Postal services for condoms less viable if live with parents, but ordering via Amazon is practical if you can pick up at another location (Lewis 2021a)(33)

Whilst provision of condoms was valued by young people and often a key motivator for accessing sexual health services, (18, 21, 29, 31, 33, 42, 44) one study highlighted the perceived stigma associated with free condoms provided by services suggesting that certain brands were of lower quality, (33) whilst another indicated young people may worry that condoms in public spaces had been "tampered with". (44) Some young people felt that the range of free condoms and lubricant provided by services was limited and/or lacked appropriate information on how to use appropriately, (21) which has implications for the knowledge and skills required for appropriate

condom use (see 4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills). Two studies highlighted how the information needs of LGBTQ+ individuals could be overlooked,(21, 25) with some young people from LGBTQ+ communities unable to access information or protection (e.g. femidoms and dental dams) relevant to their needs,(21) or being provided with information that was not relevant to them.(25) However, some young people were overwhelmed when there was too much choice available.(33) One young person highlighted that advertisement of free-condom schemes was vital to ensure awareness:(44)

I think there needs to be more publicity of the free condom scheme. Too many young people are embarrassed to buy condoms and end up going without as they cannot access them, or end up using ones from a friend that could have been stored incorrectly, could be expired etc. Too many young people are avoiding condom use due to accessibility issues, this needs to be addressed!! [Survey participant, 16yrs] (Winters et al., 2024)(44)

Online-services were seen as a way to preserve anonymity or provide a safe-environment,(17, 18) with one study suggesting that online services may support hard-to reach groups such as some ethnic minority and traveller communities or those with disabilities.(18) However, data from two studies highlighted the role for face-to-face appointments,(18, 21) with one of these suggesting face-to-face appointments may reduce distractions and improve information retention amongst young people.(18) One study highlighted that some young people with specific access needs, including those who were neurodivergent, those requiring disabled access (where this information was not provided online) or those from religious communities who required additional discretion may find it more challenging to access sexual health service:(21)

When you don't know the process... it's a real barrier for neurodivergent people and people with anxiety (Brooks report, 2024)(21)

Overall, sexual-health services were perceived as a trustworthy source of information,(44) though young people tended to look to social media to access other people's experiences to which they could relate (see 1.4: Media). However, three studies highlighted that care was needed to ensure that individuals with more complex health needs (e.g. women and trans individuals) were listened to and provided with appropriate information provision, and that there was a need for material to support skills development related to condom use in addition to information to support knowledge (see 4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills):(21, 33, 39)

I am a female and have always used condoms with partners but the GP was dissatisfied with this and was keen on me using other contraception methods. I have to take into account that other methods could make my cluster migraines worse. The GP did not think this was an issue. They also did not fully talk me through my options and why condoms

are seen, in their eyes, as not good enough [Woman, 24yrs GP surgery appointment] (Brooks report, 2024)(21)

This illustrates the importance of health service staff listening to and respecting young women's concerns and requests for further information.

Table 5 draws on first and second-order construct data from five studies (seven articles) to highlight how sexual-health services can tailor the content of interventions/service targeting use to young people's specific needs.(18, 19, 25, 26, 32, 38, 39) We discuss two particular issues of note here; the 'tone' of messages and the applicability of content to young people's situation. Young people preferred that information, both online or face-to-face, was presented to them in a friendly and natural way, which did not 'try too hard' and was not patronising.(26, 32, 39) Content which was perceived as too sexually explicit or focused on avoidance of risk was unappealing to some young people,(32) although others wanted more statistics or '*scary facts . . . to make kids think*' [Male, 22 years old-Safe txt intervention].(25, 26) Three studies also highlighted how young people valued information which related to their own living situation and experiences, and could be applied flexibly to different scenarios:(25, 38, 39)

Regarding real-life videos: "...nice to see sex and condoms so openly discussed and it felt really real, so easier to apply to real-life situations (Newby et al., 2019)(39)

Participants in this study also indicated they felt it was important for more sexually explicit content online material to be accompanied by a content warning, to prevent younger audiences being exposed to an inappropriate level of information.(39)

Four studies recognised the importance of appropriate resourcing of health services to ensure they were able to provide tailored contraceptive advice or resources such as condom packs to young people.(18, 21, 29, 39) Two of these studies recognised that time-pressures could impact on staff availability,(Brook, Jones) with one highlighting conflicting views regarding the appropriateness of incorporating questions and advice on sexual health into GP appointments as standard practice.(29) Advantages of this approach include reducing pressures on staff time and the need for young people to visit the surgery more than once, and having the potential to reduce stigma associated around sexual health.(29) However, young people worried that this would take time away from discussing the reason for the original visit, with one person suggesting:(29)

So I think it should just be added on, obviously deal with the problem first whatever it may be, cold, flu, whatever it is, and just add it on [Female, 18 yrs, Islington re: chlamydia screening and contraception] (Jones et al., 2017)(29)

2.2 Inadequate school education

Eleven studies (12 articles) support this subtheme which details how young people perceive sexual health education in schools as inadequate,(16-19, 31, 33, 36-38, 40, 41, 44) with six of these studies scoring nine or lower on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist.(16, 31, 33, 36, 37, 44) Young people desired sexual health education which goes beyond a heteronormative, risk avoidance approach and encompasses skills development on how to negotiate safe sex drawing on real world examples which they can relate to.

Table 6 below summarises young people’s experiences in relation to the sexual-health education they received.

Table 6. School education - impact on condom use

Factors directly influencing reported condom use (n studies)	Included concepts	Related themes/subthemes
Need for a safe space (n=7) (17, 18, 31, 33, 36, 38, 44)	• Need for a separate space(36, 38)	1.1: Stigmatisation of sexual behaviour 1.3: Communication and peer pressure
	• Privacy to ask questions away from group setting(17, 18, 44)	1.1: Stigmatisation of sexual behaviour
	• Fear of judgement from teachers(33, 36)	1.1: Stigmatisation of sexual behaviour
	• Visible source of external and knowledgeable support(17, 31, 36, 44)	
Current sexual health education not comprehensive enough (n=11) (16-19, 31, 33, 36-38, 40, 41, 44)	• Completely absent(36)	1.1: Stigmatisation of sexual behaviour 4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills
	• Overlooking STIs(16)	
	• Issues relating to consent/legalities(17)	
	• ‘Facts based’: Relationship issues not covered(18, 33, 38)	3.1: Heteronormative gender dynamics
	• Lack of information regarding ineffectiveness of pulling out method(33)	
	• Information on condom use basic(33)	
	• Abstinence focused(36)	
	• Need for information on managing situations where young person at risk of engaging in unsafe or unwanted sex, including need for ‘real life’ examples(19, 37, 38)	3.2: Spectrum of communication

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Desire to develop skills via role play(38) 	3.2: Spectrum of communication 4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Counteracts messages black men receive from media(40) 	1.4: Media
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Signposting to alternative information/resources/services(17, 31, 44) 	4.2 Behavioural capability knowledge and skills
Heteronormative focus to contraceptive education (n=6)(17, 19, 33, 36, 37, 44)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assumption males vs females need separate information(33) 	1.2: Different standards for acceptable sexual behaviour 2.1: Heteronormative gender dynamics 2.2: Spectrum of communication
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Challenges to women in negotiating safe sex: need for real life examples(37) 	2.1: Heteronormative gender dynamics
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of coverage of other contraceptive options(17, 33) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> LGBTQ+ identities/relationships deprioritised(19, 33, 36, 44) 	
Other issues affecting acceptability to young people (n=4)(17, 18, 33, 36)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased focus on pleasure requested(18, 33) 	4.3: Attitudes towards condoms and outcome expectancies
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Current focus on 'scare tactics'(33) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Timing of delivery: sometimes delivered too late(36) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Too minimal (17) 	
Impact of religion (n=3)(33, 37, 44)		1.0: Societal and community norms

Red text: Studies which scored positively on ≤ 9 items on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist.

Data from seven studies highlighted that, similar to health service settings, young people may benefit from sexual health education delivered within a setting which feels 'safe'.(17, 18, 31, 33, 36, 38, 44) Features of a 'safe' setting include options for young people to ask follow up questions afterwards via in-person follow up, email or text,(17, 18, 44) a private 'wellbeing room' or delivery of sexual health information from an external, knowledgeable and non-judgemental source.(17, 31, 33, 36, 44) A young man illustrated how delivery of sexual health education by someone from their everyday school setting was not perceived seriously by young people:

I felt it was ridiculous because it was funny, a counsellor should be employed not our teacher, my maths teacher, it was ridiculous [AMAB](44)

One study identified an ambivalence towards the role of the school nurse in supporting sexual health in young people, indicating that some people were unaware that the school nurse had this role, with others unwilling to talk about their sexual relationships due to the perceived lack of privacy (see 1.1: Stigmatisation of sexual behaviour):(17)

My friend, she was really worried about it and the nurse asked her loads of questions and I was next to her, I could hear them and one of them was, are you pregnant and if she was it would be hard to her to tell them in front of everyone [Female, Yrs 8–9] (Aranda et al., 2017)(17)

One study indicated that women in particular may value receiving sexual health education in groups separated according to gender, although this may risk reinforcing the assumption that young men and women require, and thus receive, different information.(33) This in turn may strengthen existing gender norms with regard to responsibility around contraception and condom use (see subtheme 3.1) and overlook the particular educational needs of LGBTQ+ individuals, as illustrated by a non-binary young person:(33, 44)

Me and my friends we were all in the [special support] department and they put us in the room with mainstream pupils and then they started talking about people who were biologically AFAB and how sex worked... some of the boys were asking questions and the teacher couldn't reign them in but didn't want to leave questions unanswered. It was confusing (Winters et al., 2024)(44)

Four studies highlighted how LGBTQ+ identities and relationships could be deprioritised due to a heteronormative focus to contraceptive education, which some young people perceived as focusing mainly on condom use with a lack of coverage of other contraceptive options.(17, 33) As Table 6 illustrates, the comprehensiveness of the sexual health education young people received varied considerably, but was widely perceived to be inadequate.(16-19, 31, 33, 36-38, 40, 41, 44) The quotes below illustrate how sexual health information was commonly 'fact based', focused on ensuring condom use through 'scare tactics', although often overlooking key information: (16, 33, 36, 44)

I remember from my sex education at school (...) they didn't really teach us about the pulling out method and how it's actually not effective because you can still get pregnant even if they pull out. And I think that maybe that would be like helpful to talk about that method maybe more [Female, 19-21yrs) (Lewis et al., 2021)(33)

honestly feel like, growing up with the sex ed that I had, if they put an emphasis on the STIs you can get, I would have been definitely more scared . . . if they had taught us like, 'Yeah, you can [get pregnant], but you can also get Gonorrhoea or Herpes', I would have been like, 'Oh, shit. Really?'. Yeah, it was only emphasised how you can get unwanted pregnancies [Female](Alam et al., 2021)(16)

My friends weren't told about anything other than condoms and the pill and [RSE] was very shame based [Forum Member] (Winters et al., 2024)(44)

The promotion of abstinence and stuff like that... It's just 'do this, don't do this' a set of rules and just the legalities of it rather than help or guidance [Male] (MacGilleathain et al., 2023)(36)

The final quote illustrates how some young people desired a more supportive approach to their sexual education. Three studies indicated young people have a need for how to manage situations where they are at risk of engaging in unsafe or unwanted sex, (19, 37, 38) including a desire to learn skills via roleplay, which for women included how to negotiate safe sex prior to the event:(38)

In our school they should've done that with us. I would like to know how you can actually bring it up without getting in a jam because you did. I think about maybe saying something before but then he might think I'm dropping my panties easy just cause I brought it up [Female] (Morrison-Beedy et al., 2019)(38)

"No," like they tell you at school to do. What we really need is how to say it other than just, "N—O," like to both the drugs and the sex, not just hope for the best [Female] (Morrison-Beedy et al., 2019)(38)

The second quote highlighted the need for education around condom use to reflect the 'real-world' circumstances young people were likely to encounter when having sexual relationships. This quote is from a study where young people discuss having sex in public places due to a lack of privacy at home, and typically do not have access to a condom (See 4.4: Decision making effort).(38) Similar to the education provided by health services described in subtheme 2.1 above, young people highlighted the need for 'real life' examples of how to navigate safe and healthy sex,(37) which may include acknowledgement of factors such as alcohol and drug use or 'chem sex' among men who have sex with men (MSM).(38)

Young people involved in studies evaluating interventions to promote condom use appreciated content which focused on highlighting how condom use can be associated with sexual pleasure, especially when condom size, type and thickness was tailored to the individual (see 4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills).(18, 32, 33, 42) A comprehensive sexual education focusing on supporting young people to engage in and enjoy healthy relationships may help counteract pressures to engage in unsafe sex (see 3.2: Spectrum of communication) and societal and community norms about appropriate sexual behaviour transmitted via the media, as illustrated by one study conducted with heterosexual black men.(40, 41) Two studies highlighted the need for schools to promote sexual health services available within schools and the wider community:(17, 31)

Get it out in public so people can see it and see what it's about. While another said: 'I think you shouldn't have to go through [name of organisation] I think it should just get handed out through your year group [in school]' (Kinsella 2014)(31)

Having awareness of the health and educational services available to support them played a key role in supporting young people to gain confidence, knowledge and skills regarding condom use (see 1.0 Intrapersonal factors).

Summary: Institutional factors

This theme has drawn attention to how issues with the accessibility of sexual health care and school education may influence reported condom use amongst young people. The former showed the need for supportive sexual health services, where young people did not feel judged for engaging in sexual activity, particularly young women (linking to theme 1.1: stigmatization of sex; theme 1.2. gender norms). This was not always achieved. Furthermore, some groups, including women, LGBTQ+ and neurodivergent groups, felt that their needs were sometimes not catered for in sexual health services, and people from rural areas faced specific challenges in accessing services. Some young people considered online services for guidance and information were better for ease of access and preserving anonymity, although others lacked private space or internet access. School settings were similarly not always perceived as supportive spaces for learning about condom use, including a lack of leadership figures who are respected or trusted on issues relating to sex, and limited in-depth or relevant information provision about condom use. The latter included the need for more information around negotiating safe sex, rather than only emphasising the need for this.

Most factors identified within this theme were supported by an approximately equal number of studies scoring above and below the median Wallace checklist score of 10.

Theme 3: Inter-personal factors between sexual partners

This theme is supported by 15 studies (17 articles). (16, 19, 21, 22, 25, 27, 28, 30, 32, 33, 35, 37, 38, 40, 41, 43, 44) and contains three subthemes, 1) Heteronormative gender dynamics (n=13), 2) Spectrum of communication (n=11) and 3) Trust and familiarity (n=14).

3.1 Heteronormative gender dynamics

Thirteen studies (14 articles) support this subtheme which explores how stereotypical gender roles and power imbalances can influence the relationship dynamics within heterosexual relationships (16, 21, 22, 27, 28, 32, 33, 35, 37, 38, 40, 41, 43, 44) with six of these studies (seven articles) scoring nine or lower on the Wallace Critical Appraisal checklist. (16, 21, 28, 32, 33, 37, 44) Table 7 summarises the concepts discussed within this subtheme.

Table 7. Influence of heteronormative gender dynamics on condom use

Factors influencing reported condom use (n studies)	Included concepts	Related themes/subthemes
Stereotypical gender roles (n=5) (21, 22, 33, 38, 44)	Women take on more risk through condomless sex (33) Responsibility for contraception (21, 22, 33, 37, 38, 44)	2.2: Inadequate School education
Power imbalance (n=12) (16, 22, 27, 28, 32, 33, 35, 37, 38, 40, 41, 43, 44)	Prioritisation of male pleasure (16, 22, 28, 32, 33, 35, 37, 38, 44) Women demonstrate less control in sexual relationships (37, 43) Dehumanisation of women (22, 35, 40)	1.2: Different standards for acceptable sexual behaviour 2.2: Spectrum of communication 1.3: Communication and peer pressure 4.1: Psychological characteristics
	Use/Non-use of condoms to please partner or preserve relationship (16, 22, 27, 37, 41)	

Red text: Studies which scored positively on ≤ 9 items on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist.

Four studies highlighted the increased risk borne by women because of condomless sex within heterosexual relationships. (21, 22, 33, 38, 44) This appeared to have an impact on the perceived responsibility for deciding to use a condom, which again was disproportionately taken on by women: (21, 22, 33, 38, 44)

...a lot of the time the boys don't quite think [i.e. about using condoms] because they're not going to get pregnant. So they're not thinking 'I'm going to get pregnant' - it's the girl that's at that risk. I don't think they always understand that or understand where the girl's coming from [Female, 16-19yrs] (Lewis et al., 2021a)(33)

I've had a similar experience of, like, you're about to...when you put the condom on, I guess, and I was like, let's use one. And he was like, what, you're not on the pill? [Female, 19-21] (Lewis et al., 2021a)(33)

If your partner says 'use something' then OK but if nothing is said then fuck it, just plow through [Male] (Morrison-Beedy et al., 2019)(38)

This quote illustrates that some young men may be vulnerable to overlooking the risk of STIs (see 4.3: Attitudes towards condoms and perceived outcomes), potentially because of a gap in the sexual health education they received (2.2: Inadequate school education). However, data from three studies contradicted this, with two indicating that young people assigned male at birth (AMAB) are perceived as being responsible for condom use,(33, 37) whilst people assigned female at birth (AFAB) were assumed to take a more active role in discussions with healthcare professionals regarding contraception.(44) The other study found that young men who self-reported being higher users of condoms were more likely to take responsibility for their use during heterosexual sex:(22)

It's my decision [to use a condom] 'cause I don't know where these birds have been [Male, 18yrs](22)

This illustrates how some young men may identify reducing the risk of STIs to themselves as a motivator for condom use but did not acknowledge the potential risk they themselves may pose to a sexual partner. Another quote highlights how some young men prioritised minimising the risk of pregnancy over STI risk (see 4.3: Attitudes towards condoms and outcome expectancies):(22)

I just told her it would probably be easier [if she went on the pill] and safer and better [Male] (Buston et al., 2014)(22)

Together, these quotes may also indicate how it can be possible for men to integrate engaging in healthy sexual behaviours into masculine identity (see 1.2: Different standards for acceptable sexual behaviour and 4.1: Psychological characteristics).(22) Young people in one study suggested that educating young men and women together about sexual health issues would develop a shared understanding and empathy regarding the issues relating to contraception and women's health, and how to make joint-decisions within sexual relationships:(33)

...like if you were to move forward from this I think it's important to start looking at how you could teach people together, if that makes sense? Taking both like males and females and teaching them responsibilities of things together rather than separately, so it's very much like we're kind of separated in that sense where like women are taught this one thing, and men are taught this other thing about how to protect themselves, but never taught how to like mutually do it together in like a partnership. And I think that if kids were...or young adults were to be taught that it could probably help a lot with that [Female, 19-21yrs] (Lewis et al., 2021a)(33)

Because a lot of the time the boys don't get...all they think about is 'oh sex won't feel good if I use a condom' and they don't think well the girl then has to put her body through different things in order to stop her getting pregnant. Because they don't really have to do

anything, it's the girl that has to go to the clinic and take things or get an injection or whatever to stop her...because then if the girl ends up pregnant a lot of the time the boys would then take it out on them even if it was them from the beginning [Female, 16-19yrs] (Lewis et al., 2021a)(33)

Twelve studies (13 articles) highlight the presence of a power imbalance between men and women.(16, 22, 27, 28, 32, 33, 35, 37, 38, 40, 43, 44) Nine of these explored how, in heterosexual couples, male pleasure appeared to be prioritised over female feelings of safety, ignoring potential risks to sexual health of both partners:(16, 22, 28, 32, 33, 35, 37, 38, 44)

We just casually cos me and him just messed around and joked around a lot and we was talking and I was like I am not a virgin. I know more about sex too and I was taking the piss and he was like you don't actually cos you don't know how sex really feels because you had it with condoms and I was like so he was like try without condoms and so and I thought okay [...] so that's kind of pushed the whole decision for not using condoms forward so it's much better without a condom [Female, Sikh] (Mahendru et al., 2020)(37)

There's nae feeling to it or nothing [sex with a condom]. You last longer, but that's not a thing for me [Male, 20yrs] (Buston et al., 2020)(22)

It's quite nice to be asked about your experience, rather than just how it feels for the man – empowering.... [Female, experience of HERS UK intervention] (Knights et al., 2021)(32)

This focus on male pleasure was a key motivator for non-use of condoms (see 4.3: Attitudes towards condoms and outcome expectancies), predominantly but not exclusively among young men,(33) and was also linked to the use of coercion within heterosexual relationships, as explored in subtheme 3.2: Spectrum of communication. Two studies highlighted how women from some ethnic minority communities may demonstrate less control within heterosexual relationships,(37, 43) with one study highlighting that black-Caribbean women were more likely to be in “closed from-one-end” relationships, or “passive concurrency, where it was their male partner and not themselves with a concurrent partner, potentially reflecting unequal standards for the sexual behaviour of men and women (see subtheme 1.2).(43) The other study included experiences of Sikh women of Indian heritage with very little prior knowledge or experience of engaging in sexual relationships, and how this placed responsibility for decision making regarding condom use in the hands of their male partner:(37)

Boys always have condoms with them, don't they? Yeah he did. Actually, I never thought about it. He had this whole tray under his bed, so I never quite actually thought that. Honestly, condoms didn't even cross my head and then when he went to get the condoms everything and stuff. I was sitting there thinking oh yeah condom kind of thing [...] so yeah, he did it he put it on, he strapped on [Female, Sikh] (Mahendru et al., 2020)(37)

Three studies indicate that the unequal societal standards for sexual behaviour in men compared to women were reflected in how some young men, including (but not exclusively) those from

certain black or socially excluded communities, can use derogatory language e.g. “dirty girls” to refer to women perceived as being sexually “promiscuous” (see subtheme 1.2).(22, 35, 40) As previously discussed, this social narrative played a role in supporting certain male groups to maintain their perceived ‘masculine’ identity in relation to their peers (see 4.1: Psychological characteristics) and may also have contributed to their pursuit of sexual encounters at the expense of their partner’s sexual health and undermined their female partner’s confidence and ability to negotiate safe-sex (see 3.2: Spectrum of communication):(16, 22, 37)

...fear of being rejected or made fun of [by] her male partner being a good reason as to why a lot of women do not say no to unprotected sex. Hearing what friends say or what the media portrays, I sense that it’s a common response [Female] (Alam et al., 2021)(16)

However, two studies highlighted how young men would use condoms to increase opportunity to engage in sex or preserve relationships with existing partners:(22, 41)

Don’t get caught cheating first of all because if I catch something then she’ll definitely know that I’ve had sex with another girl [Male, 20yrs) (Nwaosu et al., 2025)(41)

I think they [condoms] were all in my drawer and whenever I went to one of the parties I’d always take one with us just in case because I think a lot of the girls that I hang about with would say ‘put one on [Male, 19yrs] (Buston et al., 2014)(22)

One study highlighted how young men and women living with HIV used to condoms to circumvent the need to discuss their HIV status with sexual partners:(27)

...maybe that’s why I don’t think about having a proper relationship, cos it’s always in the back of my mind sometimes, I think I’m going to tell a girl the situation, she won’t be interested anymore [Male] (Greenhalgh et al., 2016)(27)

Here the unequal power dynamic is illustrated between those living with HIV and those without, with the stigma associated with the diagnosis causing people to fear exposure, with some restricting their sexual relationships to others living with HIV or those who already knew about their diagnosis.(27)

Issues related to relationship dynamics within the LGBTQ+ populations are not represented within this synthesis.

3.2: Spectrum of communication

Eleven studies (12 articles) support this subtheme which explores how the various communication issues which can exist between sexual partners lie on a spectrum of severity, from finding it hard to talk about sex and condoms, through different types of methods of coercion to engage in sex with/without condoms and sexual assault(16, 19, 25, 27, 30, 33, 35, 37, 38, 40, 43, 44) with four of these studies scoring nine or below on the Wallace Critical Appraisal

checklist.(16, 33, 37, 44) These factors are summarised in Table 8 below. Table 8. Spectrum of communication - potential impact on condom use in young people

Factors influencing reported condom use (n studies)	Included concepts	Related themes/subthemes
Hard to talk about sex and condoms (n=10) (16, 19, 25, 30, 32, 33, 35, 37, 38, 44)	Saying no to unwanted or condomless sex(19, 32, 35, 37, 38)	
	Female vulnerability(16, 33)	
	Lack of confidence negotiating condom use(16, 19, 25, 30, 33, 34, 38, 44)	1.1: Stigmatisation of sexual behaviour 1.2: Different standards of acceptable sexual behaviour
Coercion (n=5) (16, 25, 33, 37, 43)	Wishes to use condom not respected by partner(25, 37)	
	To have sex(34, 37, 43)	1.3: Communication and peer pressure
	Not to use a condom: emotional manipulation(16, 33, 37) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of guilt(16) • Persuasion(37) • Pressure(33) 	
Trust violation (n=8) (16, 27, 33, 35, 37, 38, 40, 43)	Sexual assault(16, 37, 38, 40)	
	Women trying to 'trap' men(33, 35, 43)	1.2: Different standards of acceptable behaviour
	Cheating/Concurrency(16, 43)	1.3: Trust and familiarity
	Lack of informed consent: STI/HIV status(16, 27)	

Red text: Studies which scored positively on ≤ 9 items on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist.

Five studies highlighted that young people can experience difficulties with proactively discussing sex and/or reported condom use with prospective partners:(19, 32, 35, 37, 38)

We never talk about how to “talk about” sex and all these things. If you pull out a condom and the girl says, “OK,” then that’s as much as you’re going to say. You be in the middle of things but for sure not bringing it up before [Male] (Morrison-Beedy et al., 2019)(38)

What we need are communication skills. Just to be comfortable and not be afraid to speak up if you want to use a condom or whatever. Also consent to make sure they’re (partners) OK with it as well (Morrison-Beedy et al., 2019)(38)

It’s kind of like weird because it’s definitely like if you are flirting, if it’s flirty [...] I’ve found that means there’s a fear of being assumptive, like, oh, we are going to have sex, we should have this conversation. So it removes all the nuance and flirting from it if you’re like, will we use condoms, if we do, if we do have sex? And it’s like that’s not flirty, that’s not sexy, but also that’s why I have found the best time to have it is basically when you are getting into it and there is a point where you need to put on a condom [Non-binary person, 19-21yrs] (Lewis et al., 2021a)(34)

The final quote illustrates how some young people worry about appearing “too presumptuous”, which relates to wider concerns amongst young people that condoms can “spoil the mood” and

increase risk of partner rejection (subthemes 3.1 and 4.3: Attitudes towards condoms and perceived outcomes). This increases the risk that discussions relating to consent to the sex itself are not explicitly discussed, with a spectrum of communication challenges from uncertainty, through pressure and coercion to sexual assault or rape. Three studies highlighted the issue of female vulnerability in negotiating condom use, with some young women highlighting that their perception of their own safety influences their likelihood of discussing condoms with their partner:(16, 33, 38)

For me, I think it is a matter of personalities. If I felt that they would be okay with me telling them to put on a condom, I would feel comfortable voicing that. But if they had a bolder or aggressive personality, I don't think I would [Female student] (Alam et al., 2021)(16)

I know quite a few lads that have like bullied my friends into not using condoms. When you're like me you're vulnerable and already like ready and raring to go, it's kind of like a consent thing as well, I think a lot of lasses that once they've already started and you might have done bits of foreplay and stuff or you've already kind of indicated that you might want to have sex, if a lad says to me like I'm not going to have sex with you if you want to use a condom, a lot of lasses that I know and have done have just been a bit like, oh well, okay, I'm sure it'll be fine, do what you want, just because you're like vulnerable when you're like about to have sex (Woman, mixed gender group aged 19-23) (Lewis et al., 2021a)(33)

I would say as a woman, I would feel safer having the conversation before anything happens. And it mightn't be easy, like especially if someone didn't want to use a condom you'd completely respect that. But as a woman, you just don't know if you get into that situation and then you say, oh, we need a condom. And then they're like, no, and then you're like, am I completely powerless here? Is the situation going to change? I think I would feel a lot safer speaking about it beforehand, but again, it's that fear of bringing it up and ruining the moment or the dynamic changing [Female, 19-21yrs] (Lewis et al., 2021a)(33)

The last quote illustrate how, in some circumstances, some women can feel powerless in influencing the decision to use a condom (see subtheme 3.1), which can influence their feeling of safety and perceived ability and appropriateness to pursue the issue.(33) Five studies contained data which embellish on how young women may lack the confidence to negotiate condom use or be undermined by their sexual partner:(19, 25, 30, 33, 38, 44)

My partner don't like them so I've never used them before, yeah. Whenever I tell him to use them, he's like no, you're my wife, I'm not going to use them. You know how . . . [laughs] . . . African men are like, no [laughs] . . . they're like, you're my wife so I'm not going to use it. We're not married but that's what he always says, oh you're going to be my wife so there's no point of you using them. Yeah, so and I like him, I love him, so I'm like, okay, I'm not going to use it then [Female, 23yrs, intervention, chlamydia positive] (Free et al., 2016)(25)

...it would be a big rarity if a girl basically asked me to put on a condom. [Male, 21-25 years] (King et al., 2019)(30)

...empower girls to stand up to boys who refuse to wear condoms, and hammer home the potential consequences to boys who don't want to use condoms (hetero issue mainly) (Winters et al., 2024)(44)

The second time was I have had a lot of alcohol that was the time when it was unprotected, the third time it was friend of mine and it was out of pity to be honest because he was pursuing me a lot and so I thought okay why not [...] He would say that he has never actually had penetrative sex with anyone. He has had oral sex with women not penetrative sex and then for months he would say go on give me a try what's the big deal and stuff but then I was finally yeah [...] I did ask, you know, where is the condom and he said oh it doesn't matter and then, I did feel unsafe then after that never [Female, Black Sikh] (Mahendru et al., 2020)(37)

The last quote highlights how some men may use emotional manipulation such as persuasion, guilt and pressure to coerce women to not to use a condom.(16, 33, 37) Data representing this phenomenon focused mainly on the experiences of young women, but not exclusively so, with one young person acknowledging that women can pressure men not to use a condom through implying that use of one would negatively impact their masculine identity (See 4.1: Psychological characteristics):(33)

I think there can be pressure on both sides. I think sometimes women can also pressure men into feeling it's almost like emasculating if they don't want to have sex without a condom [...] I definitely have friends where like guys have said no [i.e. to sex without a condom] and the girls have like ridiculed them for not wanting to have sex and thought they were really weird for not wanting to have sex without a condom [Woman, 19-23yrs] (Lewis et al., 2021a)(33)

The same study also acknowledged that coercion to not to use condoms can be implemented from either person in the sexual relationship, whether the relationship be a same-sex or mixed-sex relationship.(33)

Eight studies provided data which explored the more severe communication issues relating to sex and/or condom use; those associated with violation of trust of one partner.(16, 27, 33, 35, 37, 38, 40, 43) The majority of data in studies which explored coercion to have sex focused on the impact of this behaviour from men on women.(16, 37, 38)

I was like I need to stop because I was tired because I just come back from work as well. I really could not be bothered so I'm like I started and hurt but afterward it started really hurting in my waist and stuff and I was like I need to stop, I need to stop then he was like no let me cum let me cum let me cum first so we carried on till he cums, he did cum but before that I did have pain in my stomach [Female, Sikh] (Mahendru et al., 2020)(37)

One quote from a young woman talking on the topic of sex in outside spaces illustrated how young people may find themselves in circumstances where they are vulnerable and alone, placing them

at risk of sexual assault.(38) As she indicates, clearly in these circumstances, the priority is not condom use:(38)

You can end up somewhere back in the trees and the next thing you know he's pushing you down and there's not a body around. So what are you supposed to do then....It was so scary, who's thinking about pregnancy or other stuff then, not me [Female] (Morrison-Beedy et al., 2019)(38)

Data from this study highlights the importance of educating young people regarding the risks of sex in open places, and the risks to sexual health and personal safety associated with alcohol and drug use.(38) It also needs to be acknowledged that women can also be perpetrators, with second-order construct data from one study highlighting that women can also use blackmail, coercion, application of pressure and spreading of lies and rumours to pressure men into having sex.(Weare, 2018b In: Nwaosu et al., 2023)(40, 56) Other perceived forms of female coercion relate to non-condom use, with three studies containing data that some young men perceive that women as wanting to 'trap' men into a relationship by becoming pregnant.(33, 35, 43)

One study contained data on young women's experiences of being raped, when her partner removed the condom during sex without their consent:(16)

This one guy was my friend. We were on-and-off fuck buddies, and I always wore a condom with him. Last time, I literally handed him the condom and midway through, I noticed [it felt] a little different, and he was like 'Don't worry about it'. It turns out he took off the condom in the middle of sex, and I got so mad. I was like 'What the fuck, I don't know what the hell's happening with you, but I want to stay protected . . . that's the only reason why I asked you to wear a condom'. And, he was like, 'Oh, but I like being defiant. I like not listening to you'. I'm like, that's not the fucking point. When you take it off during sex without my knowledge, I feel violated. It was the weirdest situation I've ever been in, but it just made me like realize like some guys just don't give a shit if I am trying to be protected [Female] (Alam et al., 2021)(16)

Other issues raised which relate to young people's ability to consent to sex without, or inform their decision to use, a condom included knowledge of a partners STI status, (16, 27) or knowledge of whether a partner had cheated or had a side-partner, issues which are discussed further in subtheme 3.3 below.(16, 43)

3.3: Trust and familiarity

Twelve studies (14 articles) support this subtheme which describes how trust and familiarity in relationships may inform condom use in young people's sexual relationships,{Alam, 2021 #30;Berendes, 2023 #33;Buston, 2014 #34;Free, 2016 #37;Greenhalgh, 2016 #39;Jaspal, 2020 #63;King, 2019 #42;Knights, 2021 #44;Lewis, 2021 #46;Limmer, 2016 #47;Mahendru, 2019

#49;Nwaosu, 2023 #52;Nwaosu, 2025 #53;Wayal, 2020 #56} with five of these studies scoring nine or below on the Wallace Critical Appraisal checklist.(16, 28, 32, 34, 37) Table 9 describes the concepts covered in this section.

Table 9. Trust and familiarity between sexual partners - potential impact on condom use

Factors influencing reported condom use (n studies)	Included concepts	Related themes/subthemes
Trust and familiarity (n=5) (16, 28, 30, 40, 43)	Informed by perception partner is faithful/monogamous(16, 40)	
	Facilitated discussions around sex/condom use(16)	
	Associated with condomless sex(16, 40)	
	Informed by perception of sexual risk(16, 30)	4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills
	Informed by perceived knowledge of partner's perceived STI status(16, 28, 40)	4.3: Attitudes towards condoms and outcome expectancies
Reported condom use in casual relationships (n=9) (16, 19, 22, 32, 33, 35, 37, 40, 41, 43)	Reported condom use declines with familiarity in concurrent/non-main partners (40, 43)	
	Protection against STIs(32, 35, 40, 41, 43)	
	Non-use still influenced by trust(16)	
Non-use of condoms in committed relationships (n=7) (19, 22, 25, 27, 30, 33, 40, 41, 43)	Use in casual/new relationships(19, 22, 33, 37, 43)	
	Non-use is a sign of love(25, 27, 43)	
	Sign of exclusivity (40, 41)	
	Non-use in long term relationships(19, 22, 30, 33)	

Red text: Studies which scored positively on ≤ 9 items on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist.

Five studies highlighted that perceived trust and familiarity with sexual partners was related to reported condom use in young people, with greater levels of trust associated with greater openness to condomless sex.(16, 28, 30, 40, 43)

They [vignette characters] either could have talked about it, or she [knew] him long enough to trust him. I feel like when you have one partner, even if you don't know what they have, if you trust them enough, people fall into [condomless sex] (Alam et al., 2021)(16)

Trust was greater between partners in longer-term relationships who held the perception that their partner was faithful and the relationship was monogamous,(16, 40) and was informed by perceived knowledge of partners sexual risk, as illustrated by these quotes:(16, 28, 30, 40)

[Before we had condomless sex], we considered, in our relationship, our commitment and our trust in each other . . . our ability to trust that our partner hasn't had sex outside of our relationship, because that would pose a lot of risk to me and him, as well. I think people

tend to think that, in their situation, that risk might not be applicable or might be so minimal that it wouldn't matter if 'this once' they didn't use protection [Female] (Alam et al., 2021)(16)

I usually don't really think about a condom from the STI side, because usually the people that I am sleeping with like I know what's going on with them. So for us, [using condoms] would be more like a contraceptive type thing [Male student] (Alam et al., 2021)(16)

Obviously you know each other. You know that you're both clean so it's not risky... Everyone who is new I use protection with and when it's someone I've been with a few times who I know are clean then if it's agreed then I don't really need to [Male student, White British] (Jaspal et al., 2020)(28)

The final quote highlights how some men may conduct an unreliable risk assessment regarding STI risk in their partners based on their perceptions that they can identify women who may be at risk of STIs from their behaviour and other personal characteristics or information from their peers. Perceived trust and familiarity with their partner also informed young people's decision to use condoms in casual or new relationships. (16, 19, 22, 32, 33, 35, 37, 40, 41, 43) The quotes below illustrates how the main motivating factor appeared to be avoiding the risk of STIs: (22, 33)

Usually at the weekends you're pure steaming [drunk] and she was a slapper before. She could be shagging about, so obviously you wear condoms. You don't want to catch shit [Male, 18yrs] (Buston et al., 2014)(22)

I think that it depends on the situation. I think if you're like monogamous and stuff and it's a discussion that you can have together, and you want to look into other forms of contraception together, I think that's like a pretty fair thing to say. Like in a relationship, it's like you're going to be having sex with each other a lot and things, I think that's quite common and quite normal for that to be a reason why. But I think if I was just like having a one-night stand and the lad said, 'well, I don't want to use a condom because it doesn't feel as good' I would literally just be like, well, thank you for your time, but I think that's it [Woman, 19-23yrs] (Lewis et al., 2021 a)(33)

The second quote highlights that in addition to trust and familiarity facilitating conversations about sex and condom use within committed relationships, some young men and women would not proceed with sex without a condom, although others would go ahead anyway. (33) The latter may be related to young women's experiences of finding it hard to say 'no' to condomless sex (see 3.1: Heteronormative gender dynamics and peer-pressure amongst young men to gain sexual experience (1.2: Different standards for acceptable sexual behaviour, 1.3: Influence of peers and family).

Seven studies (nine articles) contained data indicating condom-less sex occurred in committed relationships. (19, 22, 25, 27, 30, 33, 40, 41, 43) In both new and longer-term relationships, condomless sex was perceived to signal being in love and commitment to the relationship: (25, 27, 43)

It was scary, cos, erm, like I moaned, I complained. He was saying “what’s there to worry about, like, we’re in love’ and all this... [Female, HIV+] (Greenhalgh et al., 2016)(27)

As well as indicating that young people may be more likely to engage in condomless sex when they perceive the relationship to be ‘safe’, these quotes could also be interpreted as examples of male coercion, with reference to the longevity of the relationship and love potentially being used as justification for requests for condomless sex or refusal to use condoms (see subtheme 3.2).

Two studies highlighted young people from some Black communities where concurrent partnerships are the norm can also rely on perceptions of trust and familiarity when navigating sexual risk.(41, 43) One male participant highlighted that condomless sex was reserved for ‘main’ relationships:(41)

You got a main person, then it’s alright to bareback and explore. Then if you have others that it might only be sexual, then you might be like “if it’s just that then let me protect myself [use a condom] [Male, 29yrs] (Nwaosu et al 2025)(41)

However, in contrast some young people may choose to engage in condomless sex even when they are aware of partner concurrency, overlooking STI risk due to feelings of love.(43) (43)

Young participants were more likely than the older participants to report experiencing non-main concurrent partnerships.(43)

Summary: Interpersonal factors

This theme has highlighted interpersonal factors, including heteronormative gender dynamics, the ‘spectrum of communication’ and trust and familiarity. Heteronormative gender dynamics revealed that, in heterosexual relationships, male preference for whether a condom is used often took priority over female preferences. This power imbalance appeared to be particularly acute in relationships involving ethnic minority or socially excluded young men. The impetus for this imbalance drew on male/female stereotypes, in which men perceive themselves as masculine by disregarding the preferences of women, and would typically only use a condom if they thought there was a risk to themselves of an STI. Issues relating to communication were on a spectrum from not knowing when or how to communicate the option of using a condom during sexual activity, to feeling that communication about using a condom is being shut down deliberately. The latter was often in the context of coercion and could also include deliberately not communicating in the context of ‘stealth’, where the condom is removed without telling the partner. In long term relationships, or where the relationship was not solely sexual, condomless sex was more common. This could be a mutual decision between partners, but the data indicated that there could be regrets about this afterwards (for example, if one partner later felt that their decision

was based on wanting to trust as an indicator of relationship status and not of actual risk/STI status). Furthermore, sometimes the male partner would express that condomless sex was preferable (particularly if they perceived a lower risk of catching an STI), but the women’s voice was either not heard or there was reluctance which was dismissed.

Factors identified within this theme as influencing reported condom use among young people were supported by an approximately equal number of studies scoring above and below the median Wallace checklist score of 10.

Theme 4: Intra-personal factors

Twenty-six studies (30 articles) supported this theme, which contains four subthemes: Psychological characteristics (n=17), Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills (n=18), Attitudes and outcome expectancies (n=20), and Decision-making effort (n=14).

4.1: Psychological characteristics

Seventeen studies (eighteen articles) support this subtheme, which explores how low self-esteem and perceived stigma associated with sexual behaviour, differential gender expectations regarding sex and influence of peers can contribute to feelings of embarrassment and shame associated with accessing condoms via shops and health services,(17-22, 24, 25, 28-33, 35, 36, 42, 44) with seven of these studies (eight articles) scoring nine or below on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist.(21, 24, 28, 31-33, 36, 44) Here we also highlight how condom use may be viewed by young men as promoting or compromising their masculine identity. Table 10 summarises the factors associated with reported condom use discussed within this subtheme

Table 10: Psychological characteristics - potential impact on condom use

Factors influencing reported condom use (n studies)	Included concepts	Related themes/subthemes
Feelings of shame associated with accessing sexual health services or buying condoms (n=14) (18-21, 24, 25, 28-33, 36, 42, 44)	Shame or feeling stigmatised(25, 28)	1.1: Stigmatisation of sex
	Fear of being judged(20, 21, 28, 32, 33, 36)	
	Feeling daunted(24)	
	Embarrassment(18, 21, 28, 29, 31, 33, 42, 44)	
Self-esteem and mental health (n=3)	(19, 28, 30)	
Preserving masculine identities (n=6) (17, 22, 24, 28, 33, 35)	Use of condom associated with social status for men(17, 24)	1.2: Different standards for acceptable sexual behaviour
	Engaging in sexual risk behaviour(28, 35)	
	Fear of being emasculated(22, 33)	

Red text: Studies which scored positively on ≤ 9 items on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist.

Two studies highlighted how young-people's self-esteem and mental health can impact on their engagement in condomless sex:(19, 28, 30)

I look back now and I realise that it definitely was a form of definitely like some sort of self-harming, of like I was just, the only way, you know, I'd have (unprotected) sex with so many people, to make myself feel bad about myself almost.(...)I just didn't really care, I had no self-respect, I didn't really care about myself, my body really, ... so I think the study definitely made me realise that [WSM, 23yrs] (Berendes et al., 2023)(19)

(30)The quote highlights the internalised stigmatisation around frequent and condomless sex with multiple partners (see 1.1: Stigmatisation of sexual behaviour), which young women may be particularly vulnerable to experiencing due to differences in societal expectations of different genders in relation to acceptable sexual behaviour (see subtheme 1.2) Whilst under-represented in the synthesis, it could be hypothesised that young people who engage in sexual behaviours which are viewed to deviate from societal norms, such as MSM, may also be more likely to experience shame associated with their sexual relationships. This may in turn increase their likelihood of engaging in condomless sex in line with the 'self-sabotage' narrative indicated by the quotes above. In addition to influencing judgemental reflection on their own behaviour, societies' views on sexual behaviours also meant young people feared judgement from health professionals and other members of society when accessing sexual health services.(20, 21, 28, 32, 33, 36) Fourteen studies (15 articles) contained data on young people's feelings of embarrassment, shame and intimidation associated with accessing health services or shops to obtain condoms (see subtheme 2.1: Institutional factors):(18-21, 24, 25, 28-33, 36, 42, 44)

Person 1: I found it quite embarrassing the first time going into a chemist and asking for condoms

Person 2: If I can't get to the nearest one [distribution point] I will go to a different one because it's usually the same person so you feel a little less embarrassed, so you're asking someone you've asked before (Kinsella et al., 2014)(31)

Would normally get them late at night at supermarket but nowhere's open and I'd be too embarrassed to get them anywhere or anytime else [Man, 19, bisexual] (Lewis 2021b)(34)

Young people generally find it embarrassing to buy condoms, which is something I've had to overcome but now doesn't phase me (Winters et al., 2024)(44)

Usually I come with mates 'cos I'd be a bit nervous if I came by myself... I dunno, it's just, I think on me own, like I don't want to be by meself when I do stuff, so usually I go with me friends (Emma aged 14) (Cheetham et al., 2014)(24)

As already discussed in theme 1.0, condom use can be viewed as a method men use to reinforce their identity and social status among peers when their masculinity is seen as based on

engagement in sexual relationships,(17) which may promote access to condom distribution services among some young men (see 2.1: Health service factors). The extent to which condoms were seen as aligning with masculine identity varied, with the desire to avoid feeling emasculated promoting both condom use and condom avoidance:(22, 33)

I'd rather put a condom on than fucking catch some dirty arse dose and that and have to go to the nurse with me cock out. I love me cock [Male, 18yrs] (Buston et al., 2014)(22)

4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills

Eighteen studies (20 articles) supported this subtheme which explores how learning new knowledge and skills can support the development of increased self-efficacy in young people with regard to condom use,{Alam, 2021 #30;Aranda, 2018 #31;Bedford, 2024 #32;Berendes, 2023 #33;Brook, 2024 #58;Free, 2016 #37;French, 2016 #38;Jaspal, 2020 #63;Jones, 2017 #41;King, 2019 #42;Kinsella, 2014 #43;Knights, 2021 #44;Lewis, 2021 #45;Lewis, 2021 #46;MacGilleEathain, 2024 #48;Mahendru, 2019 #49;Morrison-Beedy, 2019 #50;Newby, 2019 #51;Nwaosu, 2023 #52;Stone, 2018 #55;Winters, 2024 #57} with eight studies (10 articles) scoring nine or below on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist.(16, 21, 28, 31-34, 36, 37, 44) Table 11 summarises the different knowledge and skills young people find valuable.

Table 11: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills influence on condom use

Factors influencing reported condom use (n studies)	Included concepts	Related themes/subthemes
Awareness of services/products (n=12)(17, 18, 21, 28-34, 36, 39, 44)	Increased awareness of sexual health services needed(17, 21, 28, 29, 31, 33, 34, 36, 44)	1.4: Media
	Processes to access(17, 21, 28)	2.0: Institutional factors
	Appealing and functional advertisement and/or condom packaging(29, 30, 32, 33, 39)	
	Clear packaging with information incorporated required(18)	
	Demand for discreet condom packaging(21, 32, 39, 44)	
Self-knowledge (n=8)(16-18, 21, 32, 33, 37, 42)	Familiarity with own needs and desires(33, 37)	
	Personal preferences/What works for me: condoms(18, 21, 32, 33, 42)	4.3: Attitudes towards condoms and outcome expectancies
	What feels good(18, 32)	4.3: Attitudes towards condoms and outcome expectancies
	What is acceptable to me-behaviour from others(16, 37)	
	Drawing on past experiences(16, 17, 37)	
Increasing knowledge of issues relating to sex (n=7)(17, 19, 25, 26, 29, 31-33, 38)	STIs(17, 19, 29, 31)	
	How to overcome problems with condoms(19, 25, 32)	
	Role of lubricants(19, 25)	
	Consent and other legal issues(17, 38)	
	How to talk to partner about condoms(19, 25, 26)	
Lack of knowledge (n=5)(28, 33, 36, 37, 40)	'Pulling out' ineffective contraceptive method(33)	
	Relating to STI risk(28, 33)	2.2: Inadequate school education
	Regarding other contraception methods (male)(33)	
	How to support sexual wellbeing(36, 40)	
Learning new skills (n=6)(17-19, 26, 31, 32, 42)	Risks associated with oral sex(37)	
	Learning how to put on condoms(17-19, 26, 31, 32, 42)	2.2: Inadequate school education
Self-efficacy/Empowerment (n=7)(16, 17, 19, 25, 26, 32, 33, 37, 44)	Identifying and managing unsafe situations(38)	
	Supporting young people to find and navigate new knowledge(16, 17, 33, 44)	1.4: Media
	Need for a trustworthy, national source of information(33)	
	Agency in asserting needs(19)	
	Positive views of self and/or sex(19)	
	Increased confidence in condom use(19, 32)	
	Learning about/engaging in sex(19, 25, 37)	
Confidence negotiating condom use with partner(19, 25, 26, 37)	3.2: Spectrum of communication	

Red text: Studies which scored positively on ≤ 9 items on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist.

Eight studies indicated that young people felt greater awareness of sexual health services was needed, with a particular emphasis on where and how to access free condoms. (17, 21, 28, 29, 31, 33, 34, 36, 44)

I think [condom distribution schemes] are hugely beneficial but are for the most part unknown or with little information about how young people can access them (Brook report 2024)(21)

Three of these studies highlighted how knowledge of the process surrounding how to access services/schemes was also particularly important,(17, 21, 28) with one study indicating this could be useful for neurodivergent young people and those living with anxiety:(21)

As an autistic person, I'm very anxious to get condoms for free as I can't find information available online about the process of getting them (Brook report 2024)(21)

This study also highlighted the role for media advertisement (see subtheme 1.4) on sites young people commonly access to raise awareness of services and how to access, so young people knew what to expect.(21) Another study evaluating the C-Card scheme (see Appendix 5: Key characteristics of interventions in included studies) highlighted young people also needed to be made aware of the range of services supported by the C-Card, beyond access to condoms.(21, 31) Another study evaluating the C-Card scheme (see Appendix 5: Key characteristics of interventions in included studies) highlighted young people also needed to be made aware of the range of services supported by the C-Card, beyond access to condoms.(31)

Young people emphasised the importance of using visually appealing forms of advertisement for condom and sexual health services,(29, 30, 32, 33, 39) including posters,(29) videos in GP waiting rooms,(29) and promotion in schools.(17, 31) However, one male participant involved in a study evaluating an intervention aiming to improve condom use and uptake of HIV screening indicated how such advertisement could easily be overlooked in GP surgeries:(29)

I think even like in a lot of surgeries, just waiting around I like to read everything on the wall and stuff, but there's never really much about things like that, there's never really anything about ... unless you go to a GUM clinic then it's everywhere [Male, 22yrs, Bournemouth and Poole] (Jones et al, 2017)(29)

Other reported barriers to accessing electronic links provided on posters for further information included a poor understanding of how to use them, and lack of the required technology.(30) Young people emphasised websites should be clear and fun and 'non-preachy',(39)with content being easily navigable so young people could find information relevant to their needs (See subtheme 2.2). Data from one study indicated that old fashioned websites reduced perceived trustworthiness of the information they intended to convey.(33)

The appearance of condom packaging was also important although young people's preferences varied, with some appreciating fun and colourful packaging and efforts made to appeal to a broad range of condom users (e.g. use of pride colours),(32, 33) and others preferring something more discreet:(21, 32, 39, 44)

Some people need to be able to get contraception without others (like parents) finding out, so it should be easier for people to discreetly get things... [Survey participant, 17yrs] (Winters et al 2024)(44)

One study highlighted the need for condom packaging to be cautious regarding the use of messaging which some young people would find irrelevant to their circumstances, such as the use of condoms labelled with phrases such as "love".(33) One young person highlighted that provision of condoms was insufficient, and that a booklet within condom kits to describe each condom would be useful:(18)

You're not sure which each one is meant to do... The magnum could be it tasted like ice-cream rather than extra-large [Male, 22yrs, proHIS intervention] (Bedford et al., 2024)(18)

A lack of knowledge of key issues relating to sex was identified by young people in three studies, including STI risk,(28, 33) contraceptive knowledge among men,(33) and the risks associated with oral sex.(37) These knowledge gaps may be informed certain topics not being covered at school (see 2.2: Inadequate school education) and perpetuated by the performance of heteronormative gender dynamics with sexual relationships (see subtheme 3.1) Two studies highlighted how people from LGBTQ+ communities and Black men were particularly unsupported with respect to maintaining their sexual wellbeing through not receiving information relevant to their needs, (36) or being in receipt of messages via popular media which distorted their perceptions of sex and sexual relationships, making them reflect negatively on their masculine identity. (40)

Table 11 highlights the knowledge and skills gaps which young people perceived interventions intended to support condom use and sexual health supported them to develop.(17-19, 25, 26, 31-33, 38, 42)

I learnt a lot more about STIs etc which I didn't know beforehand [MSM, 18yrs] (Berendes et al., 2023)(19)

'It educated me on other things I wasn't aware of and it was very nice to know I had support on my phone [WSM, 24yrs] (Berendes et al., 2023)(19)

Well, there was this one, yeah, that said how to put a condom on, the best . . . [laughs]. The quick and fresh way to put a condom on . . . [laughs]. Because I didn't know that much about condoms so I followed the link [to obtain further information] and I'm like, oh and it feels good when I learned how to put it on, you don't have to use something that got oil,

yeah, you don't have to use it because the condom might burst and something like that . . . oh I didn't know that's how you get it [chlamydia], I didn't know, I was like, oh I need to be more careful then, I need to use a condom mostly when I meet someone new (Free et al., 2016)(25)

The condom demonstration is useful... you learn how to use them [condoms] and that it's safer (Kinsella et al, 2014)(31)

The second quote illustrates that receiving education around risk of STIs and the role of condoms in preventing these, appears to counteract conditioning that not using condoms in a new relationship can indicate a commitment to that relationship (see subtheme 3.3). As already discussed elsewhere (2.2: Inadequate school education), young people also expressed a desire for support to identify and manage potentially risky situations,(38) and navigate conversations with potential sexual partners around condom use (see 3.2: Spectrum of communication).

They would show us videos but they didn't actually make us do it (practice with them); it was like 'cheers mate, carry on.' But actually how you would discuss such things with the person, no...not having it [Male] (Morrison-Beedy et al., 2019)(38)

Three studies evaluating the HIS and HERS-UK intervention indicated that young people particularly valued exposure to, and opportunity to try, different types of condom and lubricants:(18, 32, 42)

I definitely learned a lot more about the different types of condoms and how they can be more pleasurable for women [Female] (Knight et al., 2021)(32)

I didn't know what was important to me... now I do – heat transmission and thickness [Female] (Knights et al., 2021)(32)

(18)These quotes indicate how the opportunity to experiment with different types of condom/lubricant, both alone or with a partner, helped young people learn what felt good to them, and what their preferences were in terms of condom material, fit and thickness. (18, 21, 32, 33, 42) This supported the recognition that use of condoms could be pleasurable and support communication with partners, which may challenge negative assumptions that condoms are painful and spoil the mood (see 4.3: Attitudes towards condoms and outcomes expectancies). The HERS intervention explicitly focused on increasing understanding of female pleasure,(32) which may also challenge societal stigmatisation of sexual behaviour in women (see Theme 1.0). However, care needs to be taken that young people understand the potential relevance of intervention content to them to support them to engage with the content:(18)

I probably skipped the bit on how to use it because I'm not interested in lubricants [Male, 20yrs, eHIS intervention] (Bedford et al., 2024)(18)

Three studies also highlighted how young people's prior experiences with sex and condom use informed their knowledge on what they deemed as acceptable behaviour towards themselves and supported their condom use:(16, 17, 37)

After more sexual partners, I feel more comfortable saying how I want my body to be treated. As opposed to [being] very inexperienced and not knowing what to do, not knowing what to say, not knowing what's appropriate, and not knowing how the other person would react (Female student) (Aranda et al., 2017)(17)

The first time, I didn't use a condom . . . Your perspective changes as you grow older. I feel like once you make those mistakes, you don't really do it again when you're getting older [Female student] (Alam et al., 2021)(16)

Two studies indicated that the skills and knowledge gained through opportunities to experiment with different condom types increased the confidence of both young men and women in being able to use condoms and negotiate their use with partners:(19, 25, 26, 32)

I enjoyed using the dildo... it gave me a good chance to engage with the condom before trying it out with my partner... [Female] (Knights et al., 2021)(32)

I told him about that oh if I caught this again . . . I'd rather have a condom than catch an infection again. At first he was just like 'Oh, like I really don't like it' but after he's seen the [reference to texts relating to infection and risk to infertility] which made him think as well. So I think like when you look into it deeper it helps a lot [Female, 18yrs, intervention, chlamydia positive] (Free et al., 2016)(25)

These studies indicated that young people appreciated being able to refer to information sent via text, using it as a source of support to help them persuade partners to use condoms: (19, 25, 26, 32)

My partner asked if we can ditch the condom, but I didn't know how to say to him I don't want to. So I just nonchalantly showed him the message, pretending I just got a message and the message happened to be about condoms [WSM, 22yrs] (Free et al., 2016)(25)

I've got all of them on my phone so like sometimes I'm going through my text messages . . . and then I go back through and read the stuff that's come through and I do find it very helpful . . . but sometimes you want to go back on stuff, . . . if you are thinking about where your situation's gonna be, you're meeting a new partner and you're like, right, we're gonna have to have this conversation, . . . then you have a look and then you kind of, it helps you, it builds your confidence a bit with the tips and it's the reassurance. [Female, 21yrs, intervention, chlamydia positive] (Free et al., 2016)(25)

However, one study highlighted how difficult it can be for women to overcome the aversion of some young men to wearing condoms, particularly those working within the context of power imbalance and stigma against women having sex outside of marriage (See 3.2: Spectrum of communication):(37)

when we went to the hotel room and obviously we got really intense we were just about to do it I told him you have to gotta wear a condom and he was like no no no don't worry what's gonna happen I was like I don't care I'm not gonna do it and he was like take a [emergency contraceptive pill]. I said I don't care I will have the pill I am still not so I said listen if you are not gonna wear a condom I am not gonna do nothing with you, obviously got the condoms [...] then obviously in the morning when I woke up I go where is the money for the pill and he goes I haven't got it, I said EXACTLY you see that's why I told you to wear the condom so it's kind of good [...] so after that we only had a one skin [condomless sex] [Female, Sikh] (Mahendru et al., 2020)(37)

Exploration of different types of condoms also helped reduce the shame associated with sex and condom use, normalising discussions on safe-sex with partners and encouraging them to prioritise their own health:(19)

It was helpful, made me rethink how important safe sex is. How much risk we put ourselves in, as well as difficult situations. I put my health first rather than pleasing others or being irresponsible. You enjoy it more when you control the controllable and prevent any problems for the future [WSM, 23yrs] (Berendes et al., 2023)(19)

Four studies indicated that young people may require support to find and/or navigate new or conflicting knowledge relating to condom use:(44)

[My] research started off with what type of birth control I wanted, and there's a really good website called bedsider.org that I always refer to [which has a] comprehensive understanding of all the birth control available. It was there I realised that there's risk for all these different STIs . . . but what is out there? That's when I used to Google different STIs . . . How do you get Chlamydia? How do you get Herpes? What's treatable? What's not treatable? I just kind of went on to like my own rabbit hole with that [Female student] (Alam et al., 2021)(16)

When you speak to the doctor [...] even if what they were saying was the exact same thing that was on the internet, I'd like to find out myself, like, I want to double check everything. Which is probably the other way round, I should probably read it online, and then check with my doctor, but you know, it's 2020 [Female, 18-20yrs] (Lewis et al., 2021a)(33)

Being able to access support which is relevant to their needs may help young people to develop a sense of agency in managing their sexual health and reduce their vulnerability to being influenced by inaccurate or misleading information (1.4: Media).

4.3: Attitudes towards condoms and outcome expectancies

Twenty studies (23 articles) support this subtheme which explored how young people's appraisal of their susceptibility to risk of unwanted consequences as a result of condomless sex, as well as their appraisal of the severity of the risks themselves, informed their use of condoms, (16, 18, 19, 21-23, 25-28, 30-33, 35, 37-44) with eight studies (nine articles) scoring nine or below on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist. (16, 21, 28, 30-33, 37, 44). Table 12: Attitudes towards condoms and outcome expectancies - influence on condom use below summarises the different factors incorporated into this risk appraisal, alongside other motivators and barriers to condom use for young people.

Table 12: Attitudes towards condoms and outcome expectancies - influence on condom use

Factors influencing reported condom use (n studies)	Included concepts	Related themes/subthemes
Perceived susceptibility to risk (n=13) (16, 19, 22, 23, 25, 26, 28, 30, 33, 35, 37, 38, 40, 41, 43, 44)	Direct experience of negative consequences(16, 19, 22, 25, 26, 30, 35)	
	Overlooking risk of STI/Prioritising pregnancy prevention(16, 22, 23, 28, 30, 33, 40)	2.2 Inadequate school education
	Using other forms of contraceptive methods(16, 22, 33, 35, 38, 44)	
	Gay culture associated with increased STI risk(30, 33, 41)	
	'Knowing' sexual partner reduces risk of STI(16, 28, 38)	
	Belief could identify people with STIs(35, 40)	
	Trusting/familiarity with partner(16, 38, 40, 43)	3.3 Trust and familiarity
Perceived severity of risk (n=6) (16, 22, 28, 33, 40, 44)	Lack of understanding of risk of STIs relating to oral sex(37)	
	Risk is only hypothetical(22)	
	STIs don't matter(22, 28, 33, 40, 44)	
Motivation to use condoms (n=9) (16, 18, 22, 27, 28, 32, 33, 37, 40, 41)	Not minding idea of being a parent(22)	
	Prioritisation of STI risk increased reported condom use(16, 22)	
	Avoiding unwanted consequences(16, 22, 27, 28, 33, 37, 40, 41)	
Barriers to condom use (n=12) (16, 21, 22, 28, 31-33, 37, 39, 41, 42, 44)	Improving sex(16, 18, 22, 32, 33)	
	Increasing opportunity for sex(22)	1.3 Communication and peer pressure
	Perception condoms spoil sexual pleasure(16, 22, 28, 31, 33, 37, 41, 44)	
	Condoms spoil the mood(16, 22, 28, 32, 33, 42, 44)	
	Condoms reduce emotional and physical intimacy(16, 28, 33, 41)	
	Pain and discomfort(21, 32, 33, 44)	
	A hassle to use(22, 32, 39)	

Red text: Studies which scored positively on ≤ 9 items on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist.

Thirteen studies (15 articles) highlighted how young people's perception of the risks associated with condomless sex influenced the likelihood of using condoms. (16, 19, 22, 23, 25, 26, 28, 30, 33, 35, 37, 38, 40, 43, 44) Perceived susceptibility to risk appeared to be strongly influenced by exposure to negative consequences, either through direct experience or indirectly via friends: (16, 19, 22, 25, 26, 30, 35)

Female 1: I had a pregnancy scare and it really made me think about things. [Since] that situation, I insist 'Oh, can you please put on a condom?

Female 2: I got checked up . . . after him and yeah, he had given me Chlamydia . . . So after that, I was just kind of like, 'No, dude, I cannot do it without one (Alam et al., 2021)(16)

I have never wore a johnny in my life. I will be honest I have never and never caught nothing in my life. I have been with about 14 [girls] or something, it is not that much but it is in my eyes [Male, 17yrs, socially excluded] (Limmer et al., 2016)(35)

In contrast to content discussed in subtheme 2.3: Trust and familiarity data from seven studies suggested some young people may overlook the risk of contracting STIs through condomless sex, instead prioritising protecting against unwanted pregnancy. (16, 22, 23, 28, 30, 33, 40) This appeared to be compounded if young people believed other risk management strategies they perceived as being effective were already being used, as illustrated by young women discussing the use of the 'pull out' and contraceptive pill method: (16, 22, 33, 35, 38, 44)

I think a lot of the time people like see that [i.e. pulling out] as a viable and safe option, that that'll be okay because it's technically like you're not ejaculating inside. But obviously there are risks that come with pulling out as well. I think a lot of people either I think don't care or don't know, like just assume that it's going to be fine, because it's not happening inside of them unprotected [Female, 19-23yrs] (Lewis et al., 2021a)(33)

I was on top of the condom stuff, but now that I'm on birth control pills, I don't have to worry about it. But I still have to remind myself that it's not just pregnancy you have to worry about [Female student] (Alam et al., 2021)(16)

In one study, Sikh women described having unprotected oral sex as a way of preventing pregnancy and preserving their virginity until marriage (see 1.0: Social and community norms), indicating a lack of awareness that STIs can be passed on this way. (37) However, some young people did use reactive risk management strategies to protect against STI risk: (38)

Later, I get tested. I normally get tested after the relationship and ... (shows fingers crossed) (Morrison-Beedy et al., 2019)(38)

In line with this quote, six studies indicated it was not just perceived susceptibility to risk that informed young people's decision making, but also the perceived severity of said risk, as indicated by several quotes from young men: (16, 22, 28, 33, 40, 44)

Everybody catches it [chlamydia] one day in their lives, it's one of the easiest things to catch [Male, 20yrs-young offender] (Buston et al., 2014)(22)

Condoms just suck they don't feel good at all so no one uses them I definitely need to but I can also order an STI test and get results within a week so I don't think people worry too much [Survey participant, 20yrs] (Winters et al., 2024)(44)

... if I got a bird pregnant and she has the wean [baby], then the more the merrier ... Happy days for me [Male, 18yrs, young offender] (Buston et al., 2014)(22)

These quotes suggest that catching a STI can be normalised by some young people, and an occurrence which can be easily rectified through screening and treatment. (22, 28, 33, 40, 44) Interestingly, three of the studies which supported this viewpoint were undertaken with participant groups who may experience less stigmatisation by being seen to be having sex with multiple partners and who may prioritise sexual pleasure over some hypothetical future risk. (22, 28, 44) Gay culture was associated with increased STI risk in several studies:(30, 33, 40)

... with gay culture being so sleazy you just sort of expect to be high risk all the time [MSM, 16–25yrs] (King et al., 2019)(30)

Like HIV is still a very, very real possibility if you're having heteronormative [sic] sex, without a condom obviously. And I think like it's just completely glossed over. I feel like people definitely still think that HIV is something you can only get if you're having gay sex, which just isn't true [Female, 19-23yrs] (Lewis et al., 2021a)(33)

Yeah, like I've got a lot of gay friends...in our friendship groups there's a lot of 'you're more concerned about STIs than you are getting pregnant'. I think that's the number one concern for me, yeah. So I think it's just different friendship groups [Non-binary person, 19-21yrs] (Lewis et al., 2021a)(33)

These quotes indicate both a stigmatisation of sexual relationships within LGBTQ+ communities and an 'othering' of risk by heterosexual young people, who perceive that they cannot be at risk of STIs. Some young men believed that it was only "dirty girls" who were at risk of STIs, whom the socially included men in one study believed they would never encounter and socially excluded men believed they could avoid.(35)(Limmer)

I chill with my mates and that and the girls that I know, I know them, you know what I mean, and I have known them near enough all my life—gone to school with them and all that shit—but I wouldn't have sex with none of them because they have probably all got Chlamydia or some shit like that. I don't know, they are all slags aren't they? I don't want to shag a dirty girl or anything. It's just mad [Male, 16yrs; socially excluded] (Limmer et al., 2016)(35)

The belief that a potential partner's STI risk could be identified based on superficial characteristics is discussed elsewhere (see 1.0: Social and community norms) and appears

closely related to young people's belief that knowing their partner, and subsequent familiarity and trust (see subtheme 3.3) reduced the risk of catching STIs:(16, 28, 38)

I usually don't really think about a condom from the STI side, because usually the people that I am sleeping with like I know what's going on with them. So for us, [using condoms] would be more like a contraceptive type thing [Male student] (Alam et al., 2021)(16)

Obviously you know each other. You know that you're both clean so it's not risky... Everyone who is new I use protection with and when it's someone I've been with a few times who I know are clean then if it's agreed then I don't really need to [Male student, White British] (Jaspal et al., 2020)(28)

if a girl tells me their (her) sex history, I don't know. Every time they've told me about their history, I've trusted them. Even if I didn't, then a friend would know enough about them to tell me if they was lying about (it); they would tell me [Male] (Morrison-Beedy et al., 2019)(38)

Young people's perception of the potential risks informed their consideration of the perceived benefits of using condoms in terms of protecting themselves from unwanted consequences of pregnancy, STIs and HIV status discussions with sexual partners and negative impact on family reputation.(16, 22, 27, 28, 33, 37, 40, 41) Other perceived benefits of condoms included men lasting longer during sex,(16, 33) and increasing fun and pleasure for both partners. (18, 32) Young people needed to weigh up these potential benefits against the perceived disadvantage listed in Table 12. This decision-making effort was heavily influenced by context and 'being prepared' for sex, as discussed in subtheme 4.4.

4.4: Decision-making effort

Fourteen studies (15 articles) support this subtheme, which explores how factors such as a focus on pleasure, alcohol, and 'living in the moment' may reduce young people's decision making ability regarding condom use and how interventions promoting condom availability and message reinforcement may counteract these (see

Table 13: Decision-making effort - potential influence on condom use below).(16, 18, 19, 21-25, 28, 33, 35, 37-39, 43) six of these studies scored nine or below on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist.(16, 21, 24, 28, 33, 37)

Table 13: Decision-making effort - potential influence on condom use

Factors influencing reported condom use	Included concepts	Related themes/subthemes
Forgetting in the moment (n=10) (16, 19, 22, 23, 28, 33, 35, 37, 38, 43)	Not thinking of it(22, 28, 33, 37)	
	Alcohol and/or drugs(16, 19, 22, 23, 28, 33, 37, 38, 43)	1.0: Societal and community norms
	Too tired(33)	
	Consideration, or not, of consequences(16, 22)	
	Decision making passivity/rejection of responsibility(22, 33, 35, 37, 38)	3.1: Heteronormative gender dynamics 4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills
Pleasure focused(16, 35, 38, 43)	4.3: Attitudes towards condoms and outcome expectancies	
Living in the moment(35, 38)		
Being prepared (n=8) (16, 22, 24, 28, 33, 37-39)	Condom availability(16, 22, 24, 28, 33, 37-39)	2.1 Health services
Message reinforcement (n=4) (18, 19, 21, 25, 33)	Text messages(19, 21, 25, 33)	
	Repeated/refresh of knowledge(18)	2.0: Institutional factors

Red text: Studies which scored positively on ≤ 9 items on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist.

Ten studies contained data where young people talked about forgetting to use condoms “in the moment”.(16, 19, 22, 23, 28, 33, 35, 37, 38, 43) Young men in particular talked about getting caught up in the anticipation and pleasure of the moment,(16, 22, 28, 33, 35, 38, 43) although one young woman described getting caught up in the excitement of pursuing sexual encounters during freshers week at university (see 1.0: Societal and community norms): (28)

I never think about it [contraceptive use] at the time. It's always, you know, go for it [Male, 19yrs] (Buston et al., 2014)(22)

I think freshers' week is when everyone just goes crazy but then but then you just forget about it and you start realising “oh crap I need to stop... thinking straight [Female, White British] (Jaspal et al., 2020)(28)

Where it's a heat of the moment thing some people just succumb to their emotions and their hormones and, once they start, they can't stop [to consider anything] [Male] (Alam et al., 2021)(16)

The final quote illustrates how some young men may perceive themselves as being unable to manage the ‘hormonal rush’ preceding sex.(16) One study carried out with Sikh women of Indian

heritage highlighted how a lack of familiarity with their bodies and sensations associated with sex may place some women in a vulnerable position with respect to consenting to sex they do not want, or sex without a condom.(37)

Nine studies indicated that both young men and women felt that alcohol and drug use exacerbated the risk of condomless sex, and limited consideration of the potential consequences:(16, 19, 22, 23, 28, 33, 37, 38, 43)

It's 'cause you're drunk really, you're just not thinking about it. You're just an eager beaver, it's just you're wanting to get in about so I'm not really going to wait and fuck about [putting on a condom] [Male,19yrs] (Buston et al., 2014)(22)

Once all the drugs come out it's hard to say you'll end up any place good as far as sex is concerned [Male] (Morrison-Beedy et al., 2019)(38)

Lots of times you end up with someone you don't know and don't want to remember, much less remember to use protection [Female] (Morrison-Beedy et al., 2019)(38)

The first quote highlights the common view of condoms being a hassle, and 'spoiling the mood' (see subtheme 4.3).(22) Young people's experimenting with alcohol could be perceived as a societal norm within some communities, hence the impact of alcohol and drug use on young people's capacity to consent should be considered within formal sexual health education, alongside teaching strategies to support young people to manage the risk of condomless sex, whilst under the influence of capacity-impairing substances (see 2.0: Institutional factors)

Five studies highlighted that some young people may be relatively passive, or actively avoid responsibility, towards decision making relating to condom use, as illustrated by the quote below:(22, 33, 35, 37, 38)

... a lot of boys see the morning after pill as a kind of 'get out of jail free' card in terms of pulling out and just, one, not considering the physical effects on the girl after it, the side effects of the morning after pill, but also it does alleviate responsibility from the guy's side, and I think that there's a lot of 'do I really need a condom? Oh, we can just do this', and there are lots of sort of points where the guy can be like, look, that's where you [i.e. women] need to do something... [Male,19-23yrs] (Lewis et al., 2021a)(33)

Such passivity could be related to multiple societal, interpersonal and intrapersonal factors already discussed, including a lack of self-efficacy or knowledge on how to use condoms (subtheme 4.2), perceived societal norms relating to responsibility for contraceptive use and risk bearing in heterosexual sexual relationships (Theme 1.0 and subtheme 3.1). Two studies highlighted how some socially excluded young people, including those from lower SES, may find

it hard to envisage life in the future and thus be particularly vulnerable to ‘living in the moment’ and not considering the consequences of condomless sex.(33, 38)

Eight studies contained data where young people alluded to the importance of having condoms quickly available to them ‘in the moment’,(16, 22, 24, 28, 33, 37-39) with lack of condom availability being associated with condomless sex:(16, 38)

I’m not gonna lie. Each time, it was the same . . . like the scenario that you showed me where it is spur of the moment. There was no time for us to like get a condom, so I just did it (Alam et al., 2021)(16)

People are not naked for sex, it’s just a bit of trousers down and that’s enough. So being prepared for this quickie is just not on our minds (Morrison-Beedy et al., 2019)(38)

The second quote highlights how educators and developers of interventions need to consider the context in which young people may be having sex, and how these contexts may not always lend themselves to condoms being immediately available or considered.(38) Practically, young people appreciated messages which reminded them to restock on condoms and services which allowed them to do this privately,(33) and condom kits or carriers,(19, 25, 26, 32) as illustrated by a young person discussing how they could integrate a personalised condom kit into their sexual relationships:(39)

...would use next to bed in drawer—perfect for bedroom (Newby et al., 2019)(39)

Condom kits may encourage young people to take ownership and responsibility over their sexual health. Four studies indicated that young people also appreciated a refresh of existing sexual health knowledge,(18) or receiving text-message reminders about the importance of condom use:(19, 21, 25, 33)

The texts were a reminder to take better care of myself, something to refer to if I felt reckless. Whilst having sexual contact with someone they slipped their penis inside me for a few seconds without a condom+I made him stop due to the risks whereas previously I wouldn’t have objected [WSM, 23yrs] (Berendes et al., 2023)(19)

Such text messages acted as reinforcement to young people of the importance of safe-sex and kept consideration of the potential risks of condomless sex at the forefront of their minds, making reported condom use more likely.

Summary: Intra-personal factors

This theme has highlighted four subthemes: psychological characteristics, behavioural capability, knowledge and skills, attitudes and outcome expectancies, and decision-making effort. With respect to psychological characteristics, young people reported reluctance to

purchase or use sexual health clinics to obtain condoms due to embarrassment, or in some cases feeling ashamed. For some groups, including young MSM, feelings of shame may be related to a negative spiral of engaging in unsafe sex as a form of self-harm arising from judgemental attitudes towards their sexual behaviours in wider society. Relatedly, gay sex was perceived by both young MSM and heterosexual young people as more likely to lead to an STI, which may contribute to an overlooking of this risk among heterosexual couples. Conversely, heterosexual young men appeared to view their sexuality more positively, but this could also lead to not using condoms if this would support their perception of masculine identity (see 3.1: heteronormative gender dynamics). Behavioural capability highlighted that young people wanted more signposting to sexual health services and better provision of sexual health information, which included visually appealing forms of advertisement, and websites which are engaging and not moralising. Groups including ethnic minorities and LGBTQ+ communities highlighted the lack of information relevant to their specific needs. Opportunities to experiment with condoms and associated items such as lubricant in sexual health interventions were viewed positively for building knowledge and skills, particularly learning that using condoms could increase the pleasure and mutual enjoyment of sex. Attitudes to condom use were closely related to young people's perceived risk of an STI and were increased amongst some people with prior experience of an STI. However, some young people still reported preferring the relative risk of an STI to using a condom, e.g. due to reported lack of sensation when using a condom; and young people were also sometimes unaware that sexual behaviours without a condom that avoided penetrative sex could still lead to an STI, e.g. oral sex. Lastly, the decision whether to use a condom appeared to be hindered by the psychobiological features of sexual behaviour, which were perceived to limit people's decision-making ability. However, there was also a strong perception that condoms are too much of a 'hassle', and in young heterosexual men (who were often dismissive of STIs), a tendency to expect women to make provision for avoiding pregnancy, e.g. emergency contraception.

Most factors identified within this theme as influencing reported condom use among young people were supported by an approximately equal number of studies scoring above and below the median Wallace checklist score of 10. The exceptions to this were the factors "lack of knowledge" and "self-efficacy/empowerment" (subtheme 4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills), and "perceived severity of risk" (subtheme 4.3: Attitudes towards condoms and outcome expectancies).

Relation of findings to specific population groups

In this section, we summarise how the findings from the synthesis may relate to specific population subgroups as defined by the PROGRESS-PLUS criteria,(57) some of whom may be at increased risk of unwanted pregnancy and STIs. Certain issues raised for specific populations may be relevant to multiple PROGRESS-PLUS criteria, and these are highlighted within individual sections below as appropriate. The content of this section reflects the views of populations within studies included in this review. Where we don't have studies representing particular populations, we are not able to comment on whether or how these groups are also impacted. The number of studies relevant to each category below is also limited in some cases. Hence, caution should be applied to generalising these findings more broadly.

Place of residence/study location

Twenty-six studies (30 articles) reported participants' place of residence or site where the study was conducted, which represented the following geographical areas: the north of England (n=4),(23, 24, 31, 35) Scotland (n=4), (22, 33, 34, 36, 38) and across Scotland/England/Wales (n=2).(20, 21) Settings included urban areas (n=11),(16, 27, 28, 30, 37-44) and urban and rural areas (n=3).(17, 19, 25, 26, 29)

Particular issues for young people living in **rural communities** were highlighted in two studies.(33, 34, 36) Difficulties included challenges travelling to sexual health services,(33, 34, 36) and a lack of privacy and anonymity, which impeded access to services through fear of recognition and their parents discovering they were engaging in sexual relationships.(36) The latter may have been influenced by more conservative attitudes towards sex in some rural areas.(36) Young people in these studies appreciated services which were delivered in a variety of ways, including face-to-face and online, with options to pick up condoms in person or via delivery to their home or local locker.

One study indicated **university students** who have moved geographical area to attend university may be at risk of experiencing a health inequity associated with service access.(28) This may be due to being unaware of sexual health services which exist in their new area and of how to access them, and not having adequate social support to help them overcome the perceived stigma of using sexual health services.(28)

Gender/sex

Data regarding the gender/sex characteristics of participants within the studies included in this review is provided in the Key characteristics of included studies section above (see also Appendix 3. Key characteristics of included studies).

This stigma associated with sexual behaviours appears to disproportionately impact on women (see 1.2: Different standards for acceptable sexual behaviour),(16, 22, 23, 28, 31-33, 35, 37, 40, 43) with young women from across a variety of geographic areas and ethnicities reporting shame and perceived judgement from peers and family relating to behaviour which could be viewed as ‘promiscuous’.(28, 32, 37) This contrasted with society and community norms for men, where engagement in sexual behaviour was perceived as more acceptable, lending itself to increased social status amongst peers.(16, 28, 31, 32, 35, 43)

One study indicated engagement with some schemes aiming to promote condom use (e.g. C-Card) was as a ‘badge of honour’ amongst some young men,(31) which may suggest the perceived stigma associated with accessing sexual health services may be felt more by young women.(31) This stigma may be exacerbated for young people from some ethnic minorities, as explored in the next section.

Six studies highlighted the disproportionate allocation of risk and/or the burden of decision making with regard to condom use and/or other contraceptive methods borne by women.(21, 22, 33, 37, 38, 44) In these studies, it appears the disparity between how sexual behaviour was viewed and the perceived inequality in how risk of unwanted pregnancy was seen to disproportionately impact women, meant they felt they were responsible for negotiating condom use and making decisions regarding other contraceptive methods within their sexual relationships.

Society’s views of sexual behaviour for both genders appeared to promote a “risk adverse” stance to sexual education, reducing opportunities to learn relevant skills and undermining young people’s confidence in discussing sex and contraception with their partners. This may also disproportionately impact women, who may fear being labelled as promiscuous if they bring up safe-sex in advance and may be more vulnerable to not using condoms to please their partner when in heterosexual relationships.(16, 22, 27, 37)

For young men, heteronormative attitudes towards sex meant that for some population groups, being seen to have sex supported them to develop and maintain a masculine identity, relating to their own self-esteem and identity in the eyes of their peers (see 1.3: Communication and peer

pressure and 4.1: Psychological characteristics). For some men, the lack of perceived responsibility for condom use and absence of perceived susceptibility to adverse consequences arising from condomless sex, may mean they pursue the pleasurable aspect of sex, (16, 22, 28, 32, 33, 35, 37, 38, 44) without consideration of the risks to themselves or their partner. This may make some young men susceptible to trying to persuade or coerce their partner to have sex without a condom or directly ignoring their expressed wish to stop sex or use a condom via 'stealthing'. (16, 34, 37, 38, 40, 43) One study highlighted how young men may also be vulnerable to ridicule from female partners, where condom use was seen to threaten their masculine identity.(33)

The views and experiences of trans or non-binary individuals relating to condom use were poorly represented in the synthesis, with only one study noting how the educational needs of these groups could often be overlooked in educational settings. (33) No findings specific to the views and experiences of intersex people/people with sex variation were identified within the studies included in this review.

Race/ethnicity/ culture/ language

Data from two studies included in this review indicated that people from some minority race and ethnicity groups may experience greater disparity between the genders in terms of the perceived acceptability of sexual behaviour, particularly in cultures where young women were expected to wait until marriage to engage with sex.(23, 37) Sikh women of Indian heritage from one study said this left them unfamiliar with the bodily sensations evoked during sex and with a lack of knowledge regarding how to use condoms and negotiate their use with partners, leaving them vulnerable to coercion to have sex without a condom.(37)

Data from two studies, one conducted with black heterosexual men,(40, 41) and one with people of black Caribbean ethnicity, indicated that individuals from backgrounds where concurrent partnerships were the norm may be more vulnerable to STIs and unwanted pregnancy.(43) One of these studies highlighted that, for the people interviewed who were in concurrent relationships, trust and familiarity with a partner could lend itself to non-condom use, even if both parties were aware of other partners.(43) Both studies reported that societal norms promoted concurrent relationships among men in particular to preserve sexual status and their masculine identity.(40, 41, 43) One study indicated that messages from the media could reinforce heteronormative gender dynamics, derogatory views of women and distort perceptions as to what healthy sexual relationships with women look like, the latter negatively impacting on male self-esteem.(Nwaosu 23/25)

Religion

The influence of religion on factors relating to condom use appeared inter-related with the issues discussed in gender/sex and race/ethnicity in the studies included in this review, as indicated in the sections above. One study also highlighted how sexual-health education in faith-based schools, or schools within highly religious communities, could be extremely limited.(44) Another study highlighted how some young people felt it would be inappropriate for health practitioners to incorporate standard questions on sexual health into routine appointments for fear of offending people from particular religious or cultural backgrounds.(29)

Education

Subtheme 2.2 highlights how young people perceive the formal sexual-health education taught within school settings is inadequate, which may provide opportunities for intervention, some of which are highlighted in the Implications for policy, practice and research section below.

Socioeconomic status

Four studies (seven articles) explicitly sought to include, or reported inclusion of, young people from a range of economic backgrounds,(17, 19, 25, 26, 33-35) with one study acknowledging that participants came predominantly from impoverished areas.(38)

Three studies highlighted how young people may find it difficult to afford to buy condoms,(32-34, 44) which may make them reliant on the availability of free-condom schemes and disproportionately impact on those from more economically disadvantaged backgrounds. Two studies provided data which indicated that young people from lower SES may also find it challenging to envisage their future lives and thus be more likely to focus on immediate short-term gratification from sexual relationship rather than the potential longer-term consequences of condomless sex.(35, 38) This latter point could also be considered under social capital.

Social capital

Two studies explored the views and experiences of socially excluded young men on issues relating to reported condom use. One study was carried out at a Scottish young offenders' institution,(22) and the other in a post-industrial town in northern England across both affluent and deprived groups.(35) These studies highlighted that the socially excluded men in these studies, defined in the latter study as being of low SES and having a lower level of education, were more vulnerable to STIs due to their belief they can identify, and thus avoid, 'dirty' (i.e. 'promiscuous') women. These socially excluded young men reported that not using condoms was the norm amongst their peers, reinforcing non-use of condoms.(22, 35)

Personal characteristics associated with discrimination

Whilst six studies (nine articles) included young people who identified as belonging to one or more of the groups within the LGBTQ+ community,(17, 19, 20, 25, 26, 30, 33, 34, 42) specific content relating to these communities was poorly represented in the studies included this review and thus the overall synthesis.

Three studies indicated that MSM were perceived as being at increased risk of STIs,(30, 33, 41) and thus may be at increased risk of experiencing societal stigma and internalised shame as a result. Four studies highlighted how the informational needs of LGBTQ+ young people were often overlooked during school education,(19, 33, 36, 44) and when LGBTQ+ related topics were considered, the range of diversity issues covered was limited, with issues particularly relevant to WSM such as access to and use of femidoms and dental dams not being covered.(33) This has implications for young people appreciating that STI risk is still relevant to them and how this risk can be reduced. Services also need to ensure that free-condom provision ensures internal condoms/dental dams are available,(31) alongside guidance on how they are used. Young people more broadly expressed a desire for increased education on how to identify and navigate potentially risky situations, with one aspect of this being the impact of alcohol and drug use on ability to use a condom and consent to sex.(38) Consideration of how similar issues relate to 'chemsex' may be particularly relevant to MSM.(19) One study highlighted how being LGBTQ+ and residing in a rural area may increase the experience of inequality in sexual wellbeing support.(36)

There was minimal data on how young people's age may influence reported condom use or lead to health inequities; aside from the fact that one study highlighted that sometimes sexual health information was given to young people too late,(36) and two studies highlighted that care needs to be taken to ensure that interventions to support condom use are tailored to the information requirements of particular age groups and/or are not too sexually explicit for younger audiences.(19, 25, 26, 39)

One study highlighted how young people diagnosed as HIV+ were more likely to use condoms to avoid disclosing their status to sexual partners.(27) This has implications for their partner's ability to consent to safe-sex and may represent an educational need for young people living with HIV on how to negotiate discussions about their, although data to support this point is limited. In this study, HIV positive young people said that they were more likely to return to previous partners who already knew about their diagnosis than pursue sexual relationships with new partners, (27) which may keep young people in unhealthy or unsafe relationships.

Features of relationships

Subtheme 1.3 highlights in the influence of family and peers on young people's attitudes towards sex and condom use. It emphasises how young people, particularly those from certain ethnic/cultural or religious backgrounds may be reluctant to seek support for issues relating to contraception or sexual health. One study which included socially excluded young men reported that, even if their father figures were not very present in their lives, that they still looked to them as role models on what it meant to be a man.(35)

This subtheme also highlighted how peer norms can influence reported condom use and what is seen as 'acceptable' sexual behaviour. University students may be at increased risk of unwanted pregnancy and STIs due to it being more socially acceptable for university students to embrace freedom from parental rules and engage in more frequent sex with different partners, with alcohol use increasing the risk of condomless sex.(16, 23, 28, 37, 39)

Subtheme 3.3 highlights how young people are less likely to use a condom with partners with whom they are familiar.

Time-dependent relationships

Not supported by data from this review.

Patient and Public Involvement feedback

Below we summarise feedback on the findings from this review from two young people aged around 19 years of age.

Does the conceptual model make sense to you? What would you add or change (if anything)?

Both collaborators agreed that the conceptual model was intuitive to read and straightforward – the subheadings made sense and corresponded with the key findings from the review.

Help us prioritise: which issues from the literature do you feel are the most important or relevant to this topic? Feel free to draw on your own perspectives when justifying your choices.

Peer pressure

Peer pressure resonated the most as a subheading, particularly regarding teenagers in the cohort (15 – 19). The young people we met acknowledged that teenage years are an impressionable time for many – the opinions of one’s peers are paramount to one’s understanding of themselves, as well as of their position in the world and their relationships with others (romantic or otherwise).

Online communities influence peer pressure around sexual activity. The internet can intensify extremes through echo chambers, so certain narratives may be amplified more in digital spaces than in offline environments. Furthermore, digital platforms offer broad access to information, both accurate and misleading, which shapes perceptions of sex and reported condom use.

Further nuances regarding peer pressure and condom-use specifically include: gender roles (particularly masculinity, as the group commented that condom usage might be viewed as emasculating), false beliefs around condom usage (e.g., unprotected sex being viewed as superior), the increased accessibility of the contraceptive pill (as it is now available over the counter) might make young people less likely to seek out or use condoms.

Stigma

Young people may be less likely to protect themselves if there is any form of stigma related to their preferred sexual expression, e.g., people who are part of the LGBTQ+ community, or people who become sexually active or interested in sex at a younger age than their peers (being seen as “fast”).

Condoms are a single-use form of contraceptive, meaning you will need to find a new one each time you decide to have sex using one. Contrastingly with other contraceptives like the coil or the implant, finding condoms on a relatively regular basis is generally more conspicuous than discretely visiting your local walk-in sexual health clinic once every few months/years. Simply the act of seeking out condoms can therefore be stigmatising when you feel you must 'sneak around' due to your age or preference in sexual partnerships. This was thought to be particularly true for members of the LGBTQ+ communities who may not be fully open about their sexuality – opportunities (as well as the necessary privacy) for young people to be intimate with sexual partners may be scarce, so spontaneity may 'win out' over thoughtfulness about using protection.

Additionally, the general impression is that, if you are buying or otherwise seeking out condoms, you are intending to have sex. Obtaining other types of contraceptives like the pill or coil can be conveniently explained away in social circumstances ("I have heavy periods" or "I have acne and the pill/coil helps to control it"). The unambiguous use-case for condoms can be difficult to confront when you harbour some shame around being sexually active/around who you are sexually active with.

Use of health services

Regarding STIs, some people may be more prepared to risk not using a condom if they don't have one to hand, if they are under the impression that most of the possible health issues that may arise can be addressed with a relatively short course of antibiotics, for example.

'Health services' for sexual issues interestingly made both young people in the PPI group think immediately of Gynaecology, rather than of sexual health clinics more broadly.

Knowledge and Education

Knowledge of different types of condoms (and sex education in general) is still relatively variable within the overall demographic; certain subgroups of young people (e.g., same-sex attracted, those who did not attend faith schools, those who attended co-ed schools) appear to potentially have had greater exposure to (and depth of) sex education with regards to condom usage.

One PPI collaborator noted that a recent local Pride event aimed at younger people had a few stalls related to openly promoting safe sex – this felt surprising to him, as it felt a bit 'at odds' with the target age demographic for the event (early-mid secondary school-aged children, like his family member whom he was accompanying). Despite his initial surprise, it was also notable

to him that this meant that younger people now may have a better idea of where to go/what health services to seek if they have concerns that they would like support with. Equally, it was confronting for him to see that evidently, such initiatives are being needed to be talked about sooner in life than was his personal experience – at his school, the emphasis on ‘relationships’ in sex education classes was not brought in until he was in Year 10 at the earliest.

Both young people agreed that consent is now a more visible and nuanced conversation amongst young people than ever before, and young people are increasingly aware that to engage in sexual activities, it is a requirement that enthusiastic consent is to be given by both parties, and that this must include agreeing to all the conditions laid out by both parties. This includes agreeing to use a condom — and that it must remain in use throughout the encounter if that was the original agreement.

Media

Both young people felt that media portrayal of condom use is often unfavourable. ‘They’re a hassle, they get in the way, they’re seen as unreliable for preventing pregnancy due to media tropes of condoms breaking and resulting in characters getting pregnant unexpectedly’. Additionally, characters in media who carry condoms around with them (e.g., in their wallets) are seen as ‘desperate’.

Discussion

This report presents the findings of a rapid qualitative evidence synthesis which aimed to explore the factors which influenced reported condom use among young people aged 15-24 years within the UK. The synthesis also explores how these factors may vary according to different subgroups of young people, including those who may be more vulnerable to experiencing unplanned pregnancy and/or STIs.

Twenty-five studies (29 articles) met the inclusion criteria.(16-44) Ten of these studies(12 articles) focused on exploring young people's views of interventions intended to promote condom use,(18, 19, 21, 24-26, 29-32, 39, 42) including three studies focusing on the C-Card (increasing accessibility to free condoms),(21, 24, 31) and three studies with a more 'pleasure focused' approach that encouraged men,(18, 42) and women,(32) to explore different types of condom and lubricant and establish which type they preferred. The remaining studies explored young people's attitudes and experiences relating to reported condom use and other issues relating to sexual health more broadly.

Summary main findings

We used a best-fit framework approach to synthesise data relating to young people's views and experiences of condom use.(15, 54) We identified four overarching themes. The first theme, Social and community norms, highlights how stigmatisation of sex, particularly in young people, is associated with feelings of shame and fear of judgement in young people themselves, translating into a reluctance to access support and advice on condom use from parents and health or educational services. The evidence highlights an apparent gender difference in the acceptability of sexual behaviour between young men and women, reinforced through interaction with peer and family groups and the wider media.

The second theme, Institutional factors, explores issues young people may encounter when trying to access advice and support regarding sexual health and condom use from health services. Young people were concerned with maintaining their privacy and anonymity when accessing sexual health services, highlighting multiple ways free condoms could be made available (picking up in person, ordering online, delivery via collection points) improving convenience. They also highlighted the importance of the content of strategies to promote condom use being tailored to their individual needs and circumstances, such as considering the transport and privacy needs of young people living in rural locations. Lack of awareness of service availability, fear of judgement from staff and the wider community, and fear of racism hindered

access to health services. This theme also highlighted the inadequacies of school-based education relating to condoms. Reports of the balance of information regarding the use of condoms to prevent pregnancy and/or STIs varied considerably, although young people felt that information on STIs was commonly overlooked. They also indicated that current sexual health education is focused on risk prevention and not comprehensive enough. Suggestions for valuable content included using role play to navigate situations they might encounter in their own lives and opportunities to learn from others with relatable experiences.

The third theme, Interpersonal factors, explores issues related to the interpersonal dynamics between sexual partners. The theme highlights a power imbalance within heterosexual relationships, with young women perceiving they were at higher risk of unwanted consequences and, relatedly, felt they bore most of the responsibility for making decisions regarding condom use and other forms of contraception. Both genders reported finding it hard to talk about sex and contraception prior to sexual intercourse with their partner, often leading to such discussions/decisions happening ‘in the moment’ and increasing the risk of condomless sex. Women often reported feeling pressurised or undermined when they requested to use a condom, with some reporting experiences of stealthing and continuing with sex against their will to please their partner. Overall, trust and familiarity with sexual partners appeared to underpin reported condom use, with individuals in longer-term relationships less likely to use a condom than those seeking more casual relationships where the potential risks were perceived as more unknown.

The fourth and final theme, Intrapersonal factors, highlights how young people’s mental health and self-esteem may influence their likelihood of engaging in condomless sex. The theme explores how young people’s behavioural capacity and self-efficacy regarding condom use can be increased through opportunities to learn about and experiment with condoms, and how this may go some way to address negative perceptions regarding how condoms may reduce pleasure and improve young people’s risk appraisal regarding their susceptibility to unwanted consequences and the associated severity of these. Finally, the theme explores how decision-making regarding condom use “in the moment” may be influenced through encouraging young people to prepare in advance through keeping condoms available to them and better understanding how alcohol and drug use can impair their decision-making regarding condom use and ability to consent to sexual activity.

Relationship of findings to existing literature

This synthesis draws upon the socio-economic framework presented within the systematic review of qualitative evidence conducted by Aventin et al. (2021),(9) which narratively

synthesised the determinants of reported condom use of adolescents living in South Africa.(9) Findings from this review align closely with those reported by Aventin et al (2021), including societal and community stigmatisation of sexual behaviour, although our review does not consider policy and economic factors which may be associated with condom use due to a lack of primary data.(9) Both reviews highlight a lack of services tailored to the needs of young people, inadequate sexual health education, unequal power dynamics in sexual relationships and lack of support on sexual health matters from family.(9) Common findings also include the influence of peers on young people's likelihood to use condoms and the commonly held view that condoms were unpleasant and interrupted the pleasure associated with sex. Whilst the prioritisation of male pleasure was a consistent finding across both reviews, the role of men in sexual decision making differed. Whilst Aventin et al (2021) positioned young men as the sexual decision makers,(9) findings from this review indicate that whilst men may use some level of persuasion to initiate sex with young women, the responsibility for condom use and contraception is largely born by young women. However, seven studies included in this review suggests that young men were more likely to use condoms when sanctioned by their peers and/or family members,(17, 22, 24, 31, 35, 38) and when it aligned with their views on what it meant to be a man.(22, 35)

Interestingly, a recent YouGov survey indicates a low proportion of men who believe it is wrong for a woman to have lots of sexual partners, but do not say the same of men across different generations.(58) This contrasts with data from this study which highlights different societal norms for accepted sexual behaviour in men compared to women. These differences in views may be related to the nature of the questions asked or characteristics of the sample of young men surveyed.

Our synthesis also draws upon the Health-Belief model, which was used to refine the structure and content of theme 4.0: Intrapersonal factors, influencing the names and content of all the included subthemes.(55) The final synthesis also incorporates key concepts relating to "decision making effort",⁽¹⁶⁾ and "self-efficacy" from the primary studies included in our review.⁽³⁹⁾ Factors identified by this review related to "decision making effort" that contribute towards non-condom use included alcohol use, unplanned sex and the perception that condoms reduces both sexual spontaneity and pleasure; findings also mirrored in the National Surveys of Sexual Attitudes and Lifestyles-first iteration (NATSAL).⁽⁵⁹⁾ Over time, NATSAL indicate increasing reported condom use from 1990-2000,⁽⁶⁰⁾ with reported condom use over the previous year among sexually active 16–24 year old men increasing from 61.0% in 1990 to 82.1% in 2000 ($p,0.0001$), and from 42.0% to 63.2% ($p,0.0001$) among women of the same age.⁽⁶⁰⁾ However, reports of condom use declined relative to other methods between 2000 and 2010-2012, to 72%

and 55% for men and women aged 16-24 years respectively.(61) This potentially reflects a shift in how condom use was perceived within a national health contexts, from being something that was actively encouraged as providing essential protection during/post the HIV/AIDS pandemic during the 1990's,(60) to, in more recent years, a context-dependent negotiation at the level of the individuals involved between perception of potential risks and maximising sexual experience. The NASAL also indicate condom use reduces as participants entered more stable relationships and/or started using other forms of longer acting contraception,(59, 62) with participants suggesting the invention of the contraceptive pill transferred perceived responsibility for contraceptive use from men to women.(59) In addition, some of the findings from this review regarding the tendency of some young people to minimize the risk of contracting STIs and their belief they can identify people likely to carry STI's are also found in early iterations of the NETSAL,(59) highlighting the long-standing nature of these issues. That these findings from multiple iterations of a national survey reflect those from our review indicates the transferability of some our findings beyond the participants included in the smaller, qualitative studies included in this review.

Our review builds on findings from other systematic reviews in this area by identifying groups of young people who may be at increased risk of unwanted consequences through engaging in condomless sex. We explored how societal, institutional, inter- and intra-personal factors may contribute towards, or mitigate, this risk and used our findings to identify associated implications for policy, practice and research below. It should be noted that some of the potential implications we identify below may already have been considered within the statutory guidance from the Department for Education on relationships and sex education and health education, updated in July 2025.(63) These guidelines highlight the importance of supporting young people to develop healthy relationships through addressing sexual harassment and sexual violence, and also consider the needs of religious and LGBTQ+ communities.(63)

Strengths and limitations

This rapid systematic review is underpinned by a comprehensive search of the literature for qualitative research representing the views and experiences of young people relating to condom use published within the UK since 2014. Despite its rapidity, this review adheres to best practice conduct and reporting guidelines for qualitative evidence syntheses, with the findings from our syntheses aligning with and building on pre-existing syntheses in this area. Whilst the quality of primary research included in this review varied, most themes and subthemes we identified through the framework synthesis are supported by a sufficient number of studies to allow us to

feel confident in the key messages and implications. The exceptions to this were the media subtheme, which was only supported by six studies (seven articles). Most of the factors identified as potentially influencing condom use in young people were supported by an approximately equal number of studies scoring about and below the median score of 10 on the Wallace Critical Appraisal Checklist across all four themes. The exception to this were three factors across subthemes 4.2 and 4.3 (“lack of knowledge”, “self-efficacy/empowerment” and “perceived severity of risk”), where most supporting studies scored nine or below on the Wallace checklist. The number of studies supporting each of these factors ranged from five to seven. Thus, despite lower score on the Wallace Critical Appraisal checklist, these individual factors were supported by multiple studies conducted across different settings and population groups. Each of the four overall themes was supported by between 15 to 26 studies, highly relevant to the aim of this review, with each subtheme supported in turn by the theoretically related concepts included within them. Methodological limitations which may influence confidence in certain findings include that sample sizes in most of the included studies were quite small, as with most qualitative research, which may influence the perceived generalisability of findings amongst the wider population. Population age ranges in most included studies were quite broad, which made it hard to identify issues regarding condom use which may be more relevant to certain age groups than others.

Unlike other syntheses in this area,⁽⁹⁾ we do not explore potential policy or economic factors which may impact on condom use in young people due to a paucity of data reported in the primary studies included in this review. Due to our narrow focus on attitudes to condom use in young people, we explicitly searched for studies which referred to condom use in the title and abstract. Our inclusion criteria also required explicit mention of how societal/community factors may influence condom use in the full-text of included articles. Thus, it is possible we excluded studies containing data relevant to our first theme, Societal and community norms, where the link with condom use was not stated. We were unable to incorporate PPI into the development of our review protocol or conduct of the review due to the time-constraints and difficulties establishing a group due to the ethical implications of engaging with those under the age of consent. We plan to address this through seeking the views of a group of young people (aged 18 and above) on our findings and dissemination strategy as detailed in our protocol deviations section.

Our review incorporates the views of young people of a variety of ages, gender and sexual orientation from geographical locations across the UK, including England, Scotland and Wales, which represent a range of urban and rural locations, although experiences of young people from

Northern Ireland were not represented. Young people from a range of ethnic, cultural and religious backgrounds and socio-economic statuses were included within the synthesis. Nine studies (11 articles) took particular care to include young people across the gender spectrum, (19-21, 25, 30, 32-34, 36, 42, 44) or focused specifically on an in-depth views of specific groups of young people anticipated to have particular needs e.g. socially excluded young men, (22, 35) and communities of Black men or Sikh women of Indian heritage. (37, 40, 41, 43) However, specific findings relating to young people who were not heterosexual or did not identify as cis-gender were limited. In addition, the attitudes of heterosexual individuals towards the potential risks associated with anal sex was not represented in the studies included in this review. Views of sex workers who may be more at risk of STIs/unwanted pregnancy were also not represented in the synthesis. We included studies containing qualitative data exploring experiences of young people enrolled in interventions to promote condom use. It should be noted that most of these interventions were aimed at addressing intra-personal factors associated with reported condom use, with indirect implications for some inter-personal factors, although two interventions did aim to improve screening procedures in health service settings to identify young people at increased risk of condomless sex. (29, 30)

Implications for policy, practice and research

Please see Appendix 7 for details regarding the factors influencing reported condom use, and associated study references, which support each of the potential implications below.

Policy

This review was commissioned by the DHSC and has the potential to inform multiple policy areas, including the Men's Health Strategy for England, (4) HIV Action Plan for England, (46) LGBTQ+ Health Evidence Review and the UK 5-year action plan for antimicrobial resistance 2024-29. (47, 48) Our synthesis identifies factors influencing reported condom use in young people, and highlights how these factors may disproportionately impact on men, individuals living with HIV and the LGBTQ+ communities where appropriate.

Our findings highlight how factors influencing condom use may vary across different groups of young people, meaning approaches to support condom use in young people will need to consider the needs of different population groups. Government policy to encourage condom use will need to consider all socio-ecological factors presented in this review. Our synthesis highlights how condom use, or non-use, may be heavily influenced by society and gender norms around sexual behaviour, which may disproportionately impact on certain communities, including socially excluded young men or those from some religious and/or ethnic minority communities.

Government policy can encourage development of strategies to support health and social care services deliver sexual health care which promotes sex within healthy, consenting relationships (whether casual or otherwise). Acknowledgement of the role sex plays in young men's developing sexual identity and status among peers is needed, with further consideration of how their views of sex and relationships can be changed to support male responsibility for their own and their partner's sexual health, including condom use and respect of their partners needs/wishes, as a normal part of healthy masculine identity.

Policy can also play a role in supporting and empowering women to access sexual health services and within their sexual relationships to ensure they can access the care they need and have their wishes respected. Consideration of the needs of young people from certain ethnic minority and religious communities is required to ensure their educational and service access needs are met.

Policies impacting on health and education provision within religious and cultural communities which encourage an abstinence focused sexual-risk reduction approach needs to be carefully considered, to ensure that young people can access comprehensive education and health services whilst still respecting their religious and cultural views/background.

School education and health services

School education

- Consideration of the environment young people need to be able to engage with learning about sexual health and condom use. Factors to consider may include:
 - Opportunities to access to a private space to seek support or discuss issues relating to sexual health with same-gendered peers.
 - Delivery by a person knowledgeable about sexual health, who is non-judgemental and seen as 'separate' from the teachers delivering their education.
 - Tailoring of components delivered jointly across all genders, and topics delivered in separate gender groups.
 - Providing the opportunity for private discussions and follow-up questions either face-to-face, online or over text and raising awareness on where young people can independently access trustworthy sources of information.
- With regard to content of sexual health education:
 - Comprehensive facts about the potential unwanted consequences of sex, particularly STIs and the risks associated with oral sex.

- Tailoring of content to consider the needs of diverse groups, which may include individuals identifying as lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans or queer/questioning, intersex and asexual.
- Going beyond an abstinence or risk prevention approach, to incorporate learning and discussion on:
 - How sex can be a pleasurable activity;
 - Encouraging young people to talk about sex, condoms and other contraceptive methods with their sexual partners through role play;
 - Identifying, planning for and navigating potentially risky situations, including issues relating to consent and alcohol/drug use;
 - Addressing societal views and expectations around sex, including gendered norms for acceptable behaviour.
- Providing opportunities for young people to learn from the experiences of role models, scenarios or role play of situations to which they can relate.
- Raising awareness of places young people can go to for further support outside of and within school, including increased promotion of the availability of school nurses (where relevant).
- Supporting young people to develop critical thinking skills to evaluate and counteract information and material they access online and via social media. This may include:
 - How to evaluate the reliability and trustworthiness of information about sex and condom use;
 - Providing examples of what 'normal' sexual behaviour can look like across different communities;
 - Counteracting negative messaging about women and condom use.

Health services

- Consider the range of accessibility needs of young people living within specific communities (e.g. rural, certain ethnic minority, conservative religious) in relation to accessing free condoms and sexual health advice. Issues to consider may include:
 - Access to private spaces and technology to access online appointments or text messages;
 - Transport networks and costs for those living in rural communities;
 - Promoting a range of condom delivery options, such as private pick-up rooms within health service settings or delivery to home or locker.

- Ensure clear guidance on how to use condoms is included alongside free condoms and where young people can go to access further advice. Free condom schemes should also encompass provision of internal condoms and dental dams.
- Consider how best to advertise sexual health service availability to young people, including relevant social media sites and school nurses, depending on the individual needs and context of the young people within those settings.
- Develop an online national ‘go-to’ resource for advice and support on sexual health issues. Content should be up to date, friendly and fun, and accessible, with labelling of content which may be too sexually explicit for younger audiences. Young people may appreciate opportunities to learn from other people’s experiences to which they can relate.
- Consider of how best to engage with communities who may distrust or find it hard to access health services e.g. some ethnic minority or traveller communities.

Future research

- Further qualitative research to explore the experiences and support needs of all groups within LGBTQ+ communities and in relation to managing healthy relationships and sexual-health.
- Further qualitative research to consider of the specific needs of sex-workers in managing their sexual health.
- Qualitative and quantitative research to develop and evaluate interventions to promote condom use as a typical part of enacting a healthy masculine identity.
- Consider how participant age may contribute towards their likelihood and experiences of using condoms.

Conclusions

This is the first systematic review to synthesise qualitative evidence from the UK on young people’s attitudes towards condom use. Our synthesis identifies factors at the policy, institutional, inter- and intra-personal level which may influence reported condom use in young people and provide opportunity for intervention. We highlight how these factors may disproportionately impact the condom use behaviour of certain groups of young people, potentially increasing their risk of unwanted pregnancy and STIs. Whilst the factors influencing condom use are likely to vary between different groups of young people, our findings highlight the importance of addressing stigma surrounding sexual behaviour in young people and the

difficulties young people experience related to the differences in acceptable sexual behaviour between young men and women.

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Appendix 1: Search report

Bibliographic database searches

Database: APA PsycInfo

Host: Ovid

Issue: 1806 to September 2025 Week 1

Date Searched: 10th September 2025

Searcher: SB

Hits: 3098

Strategy:

1. (condom* or femidom*).tw.
2. condoms/
3. ((unprotected or unsafe) adj2 (sex* or intercourse)).tw.
4. (risk* adj3 ("sexual behaviour*" or "sexual behavior*")).tw.
5. sexual risk taking/
6. safe sex/
7. or/1-6
8. (young adj2 (adult* or person* or individual* or people* or population* or man or men or "sexually active" or wom?n)).tw.
9. (teen* or youth* or adolescen* or juvenile*).tw.
10. ("high school*" or "secondary school*" or education or university or student* or "school age").tw.
11. (("15" or "16" or "17" or "18" or "19" or "20" or "21" or "22" or "23" or "24" or "25" or fifteen or sixteen or seventeen or eighteen or nineteen or twenty or "twenty one" or "twenty two" or "twenty three" or "twenty four" or "twenty five") adj3 year*).tw.
12. emerging adulthood/
13. adolescent attitudes/
14. adolescent behavior/
15. or/8-14
16. (qualitative or interview* or experience or experiences or perspective* or view*).tw.
17. exp qualitative methods/
18. ("focus group" or survey* or questionnaire*).tw.
19. questionnaires/
20. exp surveys/
21. or/16-20
22. 7 and 15 and 21
23. limit 22 to (english language and yr="2014 -Current")

Database: CINAHL

Host: EBSCO

Issue: n/a

Date Searched: 10th September 2025

Searcher: SB

Hits: 3426

Strategy:

1. TI (condom* OR femidom*) OR AB (condom* OR femidom*)
2. (MH "Condoms+")

3. TI ((unprotected or unsafe) n1 (sex* or intercourse)) OR AB ((unprotected or unsafe) n1 (sex* or intercourse))
4. TI (risk* n2 ("sexual behaviour*" or "sexual behavior*")) OR AB (risk* n2 ("sexual behaviour*" or "sexual behavior*"))
5. (MH "Unsafe Sex")
6. S1 OR S2 OR S3 OR S4 OR S5
7. TI (young n1 (adult* or person* or individual* or people* or population* or man or men or "sexually active" or wom?n)) OR AB (young n1 (adult* or person* or individual* or people* or population* or man or men or "sexually active" or wom?n))
8. TI ((teen* or youth* or adolescen* or juvenile*)) OR AB ((teen* or youth* or adolescen* or juvenile*))
9. TI (("high school*" or "secondary school*" or education or university or student* or "school age")) OR AB (("high school*" or "secondary school*" or education or university or student* or "school age"))
10. TI ((("15" or "16" or "17" or "18" or "19" or "20" or "21" or "22" or "23" or "24" or "25" or fifteen or sixteen or seventeen or eighteen or nineteen or twenty or "twenty one" or "twenty two" or "twenty three" or "twenty four" or "twenty five") n2 year*)) OR AB ((("15" or "16" or "17" or "18" or "19" or "20" or "21" or "22" or "23" or "24" or "25" or fifteen or sixteen or seventeen or eighteen or nineteen or twenty or "twenty one" or "twenty two" or "twenty three" or "twenty four" or "twenty five") n2 year*))
11. (MH "Young Adult")
12. (MH "Adolescence")
13. S7 OR S8 OR S9 OR S10 OR S11 OR S12
14. TI (qualitative or interview* or experience or experiences or perspective* or view*) OR AB (qualitative or interview* or experience or experiences or perspective* or view*)
15. (MH "Qualitative Studies+")
16. TI ("focus group" or survey* or questionnaire*) OR AB ("focus group" or survey* or questionnaire*)
17. (MH "Survey Research")
18. S14 OR S15 OR S16 OR S17
19. S6 AND S13 AND S18

Notes: Limiters - Publication Date: 20140101-20251231; Narrow by Language: - english

Database: Embase

Host: Ovid

Issue: 1974 to 2025 September 08

Date Searched: 10th September 2025

Searcher: SB

Hits: 973

Strategy:

1. exp United Kingdom/
2. (national health service* or nhs*).ti,ab,in,ad.
3. (english not ((published or publication* or translat* or written or language* or speak* or literature or citation*) adj5 english)).ti,ab.
4. (gb or "g.b." or britain* or (british* not "british columbia") or uk or "u.k." or united kingdom* or (england* not "new england") or northern ireland* or northern irish* or scotland* or scottish* or ((wales or "south wales") not "new south wales") or welsh*).ti,ab,jx,in,ad.
5. (bath or "bath's" or ((birmingham not alabama*) or ("birmingham's" not alabama*) or bradford or "bradford's" or brighton or "brighton's" or bristol or "bristol's" or carlisle* or "carlisle's" or (cambridge not (massachusetts* or boston* or harvard*)) or ("cambridge's" not (massachusetts* or boston* or harvard*)) or (canterbury not zealand*) or

- ("canterbury's" not zealand*) or chelmsford or "chelmsford's" or chester or "chester's" or chichester or "chichester's" or coventry or "coventry's" or derby or "derby's" or (durham not (carolina* or nc)) or ("durham's" not (carolina* or nc)) or ely or "ely's" or exeter or "exeter's" or gloucester or "gloucester's" or hereford or "hereford's" or hull or "hull's" or lancaster or "lancaster's" or leeds* or leicester or "leicester's" or (lincoln not nebraska*) or ("lincoln's" not nebraska*) or (liverpool not (new south wales* or nsw)) or ("liverpool's" not (new south wales* or nsw)) or ((london not (ontario* or ont or toronto*)) or ("london's" not (ontario* or ont or toronto*)) or manchester or "manchester's" or (newcastle not (new south wales* or nsw)) or ("newcastle's" not (new south wales* or nsw)) or norwich or "norwich's" or nottingham or "nottingham's" or oxford or "oxford's" or peterborough or "peterborough's" or plymouth or "plymouth's" or portsmouth or "portsmouth's" or preston or "preston's" or ripon or "ripon's" or salford or "salford's" or salisbury or "salisbury's" or sheffield or "sheffield's" or southampton or "southampton's" or st albans or stoke or "stoke's" or sunderland or "sunderland's" or truro or "truro's" or wakefield or "wakefield's" or wells or westminster or "westminster's" or winchester or "winchester's" or wolverhampton or "wolverhampton's" or (worcester not (massachusetts* or boston* or harvard*)) or ("worcester's" not (massachusetts* or boston* or harvard*)) or (york not ("new york*" or ny or ontario* or ont or toronto*)) or ("york's" not ("new york*" or ny or ontario* or ont or toronto*))))).ti,ab,in,ad.
6. (bangor or "bangor's" or cardiff or "cardiff's" or newport or "newport's" or st asaph or "st asaph's" or st davids or swansea or "swansea's").ti,ab,in,ad.
 7. (aberdeen or "aberdeen's" or dundee or "dundee's" or edinburgh or "edinburgh's" or glasgow or "glasgow's" or inverness or (perth not australia*) or ("perth's" not australia*) or stirling or "stirling's").ti,ab,in,ad.
 8. (armagh or "armagh's" or belfast or "belfast's" or lisburn or "lisburn's" or londonderry or "londonderry's" or derry or "derry's" or newry or "newry's").ti,ab,in,ad.
 9. or/1-8
 10. (exp "arctic and antarctic"/ or exp oceanic regions/ or exp western hemisphere/ or exp africa/ or exp asia/ or exp "australia and new zealand"/) not (exp united kingdom/ or europe/)
 11. 9 not 10
 12. (condom* or femidom*).tw.
 13. condom/
 14. female condom/
 15. "condom use"/
 16. ((unprotected or unsafe) adj2 (sex* or intercourse)).tw.
 17. (risk* adj3 ("sexual behaviour*" or "sexual behavior*")).tw.
 18. exp unsafe sex/
 19. or/12-18
 20. (young adj2 (adult* or person* or individual* or people* or population* or man or men or "sexually active" or wom?n)).tw.
 21. (teen* or youth* or adolescen* or juvenile*).tw.
 22. ("high school*" or "secondary school*" or education or university or student* or "school age").tw.
 23. (("15" or "16" or "17" or "18" or "19" or "20" or "21" or "22" or "23" or "24" or "25" or fifteen or sixteen or seventeen or eighteen or nineteen or twenty or "twenty one" or "twenty two" or "twenty three" or "twenty four" or "twenty five") adj3 year*).tw.
 24. adult child/
 25. adolescent/
 26. young adult/
 27. or/20-26

28. 11 and 19 and 27
29. limit 28 to (english language and yr="2014 -Current")

Database: MEDLINE

Host: Ovid

Issue: 1946 to September 09, 2025

Date Searched: 10th September 2025

Searcher: SB

Hits: 622

Strategy:

1. exp United Kingdom/
2. (national health service* or nhs*).ti,ab,in.
3. (english not ((published or publication* or translat* or written or language* or speak* or literature or citation*) adj5 english)).ti,ab.
4. (gb or "g.b." or britain* or (british* not "british columbia") or uk or "u.k." or united kingdom* or (england* not "new england") or northern ireland* or northern irish* or scotland* or scottish* or ((wales or "south wales") not "new south wales") or welsh*).ti,ab,jw,in.
5. (bath or "bath's" or ((birmingham not alabama*) or ("birmingham's" not alabama*) or bradford or "bradford's" or brighton or "brighton's" or bristol or "bristol's" or Carlisle* or "Carlisle's" or (cambridge not (massachusetts* or boston* or harvard*)) or ("cambridge's" not (massachusetts* or boston* or harvard*)) or (canterbury not zealand*) or ("canterbury's" not zealand*) or chelmsford or "chelmsford's" or chester or "chester's" or chichester or "chichester's" or coventry or "coventry's" or derby or "derby's" or (durham not (carolina* or nc)) or ("durham's" not (carolina* or nc)) or ely or "ely's" or exeter or "exeter's" or gloucester or "gloucester's" or hereford or "hereford's" or hull or "hull's" or lancaster or "lancaster's" or leeds* or leicester or "leicester's" or (lincoln not nebraska*) or ("lincoln's" not nebraska*) or (liverpool not (new south wales* or nsw)) or ("liverpool's" not (new south wales* or nsw)) or ((london not (ontario* or ont or toronto*)) or ("london's" not (ontario* or ont or toronto*)) or manchester or "manchester's" or (newcastle not (new south wales* or nsw)) or ("newcastle's" not (new south wales* or nsw)) or norwich or "norwich's" or nottingham or "nottingham's" or oxford or "oxford's" or peterborough or "peterborough's" or plymouth or "plymouth's" or portsmouth or "portsmouth's" or preston or "preston's" or ripon or "ripon's" or salford or "salford's" or salisbury or "salisbury's" or sheffield or "sheffield's" or southampton or "southampton's" or st albans or stoke or "stoke's" or sunderland or "sunderland's" or truro or "truro's" or wakefield or "wakefield's" or wells or westminster or "westminster's" or winchester or "winchester's" or wolverhampton or "wolverhampton's" or (worcester not (massachusetts* or boston* or harvard*)) or ("worcester's" not (massachusetts* or boston* or harvard*)) or (york not ("new york*" or ny or ontario* or ont or toronto*)) or ("york's" not ("new york*" or ny or ontario* or ont or toronto*))))).ti,ab,in.
6. (bangor or "bangor's" or cardiff or "cardiff's" or newport or "newport's" or st asaph or "st asaph's" or st davids or swansea or "swansea's").ti,ab,in.
7. (aberdeen or "aberdeen's" or dundee or "dundee's" or edinburgh or "edinburgh's" or glasgow or "glasgow's" or inverness or (perth not australia*) or ("perth's" not australia*) or stirling or "stirling's").ti,ab,in.
8. (armagh or "armagh's" or belfast or "belfast's" or lisburn or "lisburn's" or londonderry or "londonderry's" or derry or "derry's" or newry or "newry's").ti,ab,in.
9. or/1-8
10. (exp africa/ or exp americas/ or exp antarctic regions/ or exp arctic regions/ or exp asia/ or exp australia/ or exp oceania/) not (exp United Kingdom/ or europe/)
11. 9 not 10

12. (condom* or femidom*).tw,kw.
13. Condoms/
14. Single-Use Internal Condom/
15. ((unprotected or unsafe) adj2 (sex* or intercourse)).tw.
16. (risk* adj3 ("sexual behaviour*" or "sexual behavior*")).tw.
17. Unsafe Sex/
18. or/12-17
19. (young adj2 (adult* or person* or individual* or people* or population* or man or men or "sexually active" or wom?n)).tw.
20. (teen* or youth* or adolescen* or juvenile*).tw.
21. ("high school*" or "secondary school*" or education or university or student* or "school age").tw.
22. (("15" or "16" or "17" or "18" or "19" or "20" or "21" or "22" or "23" or "24" or "25" or fifteen or sixteen or seventeen or eighteen or nineteen or twenty or "twenty one" or "twenty two" or "twenty three" or "twenty four" or "twenty five") adj3 year*).tw.
23. adult children/
24. adolescent/
25. young adult/
26. or/19-25
27. 11 and 18 and 26
28. limit 27 to (english language and yr="2014 -Current")

Table A1. Bibliographic database search results

Database	Hits
APA PsycInfo	3098
CINAHL	3426
Embase	973
MEDLINE	622
Total results	8119
Duplicate results	1822
Unique results	6297

Web searching

Websites

Organisation: Brook

URL: <https://www.brook.org.uk/>

Date Searched: 26th September 2025

Searcher: SB

Pages browsed: <https://www.brook.org.uk/about-brook/our-publications-and-reports/>

Organisation: NATSAL

URL: <https://www.natsal.ac.uk/>

Date Searched: 26th September 2025

Searcher: SB

Pages browsed: <https://www.natsal.ac.uk/outputs/publications/>;

<https://www.natsal.ac.uk/outputs/reports/>

Web reports recommended by stakeholders

Education, Access, Stigma and Young People (EASY) – Attitudes to contraception, condoms and sexual health (*Brook, May 2024*): [EASY Summary Report.indd \(brook.org.uk\)](#)

Digital Condom Distribution – Our research into how digital can deliver a better condom distribution scheme – (*Brook, Feb 2024*): [Digital-condom-distribution-report-2024.pdf \(brook.org.uk\)](#)

Understanding young people’s use and non-use of condoms and contraception (*Scottish Government, NHS and Social and Public Health Sciences Unit, March 2021*): [Microsoft Word - CONUNDRUM Final Report_SPHSU v2.docx](#)

The prevalence of sexually transmitted infections in young people and other high risk groups (*Women and Equalities Committee, March 2024*) [Prevalence of STIs among young people \(parliament.uk\)](#)

UK 5-year action plan for antimicrobial resistance 2024-2029 (*UK Government, 2024*) [UK 5-year action plan for antimicrobial resistance 2024 to 2029 - GOV.UK](#)

The National Survey of Sexual Attitudes and Lifestyles (*NATSAL, 2025*) [NATSAL – The National Survey of Sexual Attitudes and Lifestyles](#)

Appendix 2: Excluded full-texts with reasons for exclusion

Table A2. Excluded full-texts with reasons for exclusion

#	Study (total n=85)
Conference abstract (n=18)	
1.	Burnett L, Douglas K. Sexual health for young people undergoing haematopoietic stem cell transplantation. <i>Bone Marrow Transplantation</i> . 2020;55:725.
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Appendix 3. Key characteristics of included studies

Table A3. Key characteristics of included studies

Study, (Format)	Location	Data collection method (year of data collection)	Target population	Participants, n (male, %)	Mean age (SD) [range]*	Ethnicity, n (%)	Sexual orientation, n (%)
<i>No intervention (n=15 studies [17 study reports])</i>							
Alam (JAP)(16)	2021, London	Semi-structured interviews (NR)	Sexually active heterosexual university students	9 (3, 33.33%)	22.6 (NR) [20-25]	NR	Heterosexual
Aranda (JAP)(17)	2018, England	Focus groups; interviews; interactive activities (2015)	Students/pupils	Whole sample: 74 (43, 58.12%); Sexual health improvement topic area only: 39 (22, 56.4%)	Whole sample: NR (NR) [11-19]; Sexual health improvement topic area only: 11-13 yrs: n=2 (5.1%); 14-15 yrs: n=26 (66.7%); 16-17 yrs: n=10	Total sample: White British: 68 (91.89%); White Irish: 1(1.35%); White and Asian: 2 (2.70%); White and Caribbean: 2 (2.70%); White and Black: 1 (1.35%); African: 1 (1.35%)	NR

						(25.6%); 18-19 yrs: n=1 (2.6%)		
Boso Perez 2023, England, Scotland and Wales (JAP)(20)	Semi-structured interviews (2020)	Users of sexual and reproductive health services (specifically, with unmet need)	20 (6, 30%)	18-29 yrs: n=3 (15%); 30-39 yrs n=10 (50%); 40-49 yrs: n=7 (35%)	White: 16 (80%); Asian: 3 (15%); Mixed: 1 (5%)	Homosexual/gay: 2 (10%); Heterosexual/straight: 15 (75%); Omnisexual: 1 (5%); Not reported: 2 (20%)		
Buston 2014, Scotland (JAP)(22)	Part 1: self-complete questionnaire; part 2: semi-structured interviews (2008)	Young male offenders reaching end of long term sentences	Questionnaire: 66 (66, 100%); Interview: 40 (40, 100%)	Questionnaire: NR (NR) [16-21]; Interview sample: Low users: 18.6 (NR) [NR]; high users: 17.9 (NR) [NR]†	Low users: White British: 17 (100%); High users: White British: 13 (92.9%); Other: 1 (7.1%)**	NR		
Chanakira 2014, North of England (JAP)(23)	Semi-structured interviews (2008-2009)	University students	20 (10, 50%)	18-19 yrs: n=2 (10%); 20-24 yrs: n=8 (40%); 25-34 yrs: n=7 (35%); 35-44 yrs: n=1 (5%); 45+ yrs: n=2 (10%)	NR	NR		

Greenhalgh London (JAP)(27)	2016,	Semi-structured interviews (NR)	Young adults with perinatally acquired HIV	7 (2, 28.6%)	21.4 (NR) [18- 23]	Black African: 6 (85.7%); White British: 1 (14.3%)	NR
Jaspal Midlands (JAP)(28)	2020, East	Semi-structured interviews (NR)	First year university students	16 (7, 43.25%)	20.1 (2.4) [18- 26]	White British: 12 (75%); British South Asian: 4 (25%)	Heterosexual
Limmer West of England (JAP)(35)	2016, North	Focus groups and semi-structured interviews (2007- 2008)	Young men aged 15 to 17 years living in NW England	46 (46, 100%)	NR (NR) [15-17]	White British (100%)	Heterosexual
MacGilleathain Outer Hebrides (JAP)(36)	2023,	Survey (quantitative) and focus groups (2022)	Young people (aged 13-18 years)	Survey: 473 (NR); Focus groups: 16 (6, 37.5%)	Survey: NR; Focus groups: NR (NR) [15-17]		Heterosexual: 77%; Bisexual: 7%; Gay: 5%; Lesbian: 2%; Pansexual: 4%; Asexual <1%; Don't know: 4%
Mahendru West London (JAP)(37)	2020, South	Conversational interviews and ethnography (NR)	Heterosexual young British Sikh women	12 (6, 50%)	NR (NR) [18-20]	Indian origin but educated in UK since age 9 or younger	Heterosexual
Morrison-Beedy Scotland (JAP)(38)	2019,	Focus groups (2017)	Scottish teenagers	18 (11, 61.11%)	17.2 (NR) [16-19]	Race: White: 16 (88.88%); Black: 2 (1.11%);	Heterosexual

						Ethnicity: Hispanic: 2 (1.11%); non-Hispanic: 16 (88.88%)	
Nwaosu (Thesis)(40); 2025, London (JAP)(41)	2023	Semi-structured interviews (2020- 2021)	Black heterosexual men with experience of higher-risk sexual behaviours living in London	10 (10, 100%)	36 (NR) [18-58 years]	Black African (n = 4), Black Caribbean (n = 3), mixed Black African, and Caribbean (n = 1) and Black British (n = 2). (one born in Kenya, others all born in London)	Heterosexual
Wayal and (JAP)(43)	2020, London and Birmingham	In-depth interviews and focus groups (2014-2015)	People aged ≥15 years, who could read and speak English, and who identified as having a black Caribbean heritage	59 (24, 40.68%)	Total age range: 15-70 yrs. Focus groups: Focus group 1: 15-24 yrs; Focus group 2: 15-24 yrs; Focus group 3: 35-48 yrs; Focus group 4: Over 48 yrs. Interviews: 15- 24 yrs: n=11, 25-	All the in-depth interview participants identified as black Caribbean; some focus group discussion participants identified as being black British or mixed ethnic background	Heterosexual (study reports that none of the participants identified as gay or bisexual)

				35 yrs: n=10, >35 yrs: n=10		
Winters 2024, England and Wales (Report)(44)	Open and closed survey questions (2023-2024); small group discussions; interviews (NR)	Young people living in Scotland during COVID	Survey 1: 2387 (NR); Follow up survey: 330 (NR); Qualitative: 16 (6, 37.5%)	Qualitative: 20.19 (NR) [18-25]	NR	Heterosexual: 54.33%; Bisexual: 32.39%; Other description: 6.77%; Gay: 2.90%; Lesbian: 2.27%; Prefer not to say: 1.45%
<i>CONUNDRUM study (n=2 study reports)</i>						
Lewis 2021a, Scotland (Report)(33)	Workshops; online survey; small group discussions (2019-2020)	Young people living in Scotland during COVID	Workshops: 38 (NR) Discussion groups: 20 (NR)	Workshops: 16-17 yrs: n=13; 16-19 yrs: n=11; 17-24 yrs: 8; n=20-22 yrs: 6; Discussion groups: NR (NR) [16-24]	NR	Workshops: Considerable diversity in terms of participants' gender, sexual identities and sexual experiences; Discussion groups: Participants self reported sexual identities: heterosexual, bisexual, gay and queer.

Lewis 2021b, Scotland (JAP)(34)	Survey (2020)	Young people living in Scotland during COVID	1588 (Male: 649, 40.90% [including trans male]; Women: 880, 55.40% [including trans women]; Identify gender in another way: 59, 3.7%)	16-19 yrs: n=656 (41.3%), 20-24 yrs: n=932 (58.7%)	White Scottish or White British: 1333 (84.00%); White, not Scottish or British: 124 (7.80%); Asian, Asian Scottish or British: 54 (3.40%); Mixed or multiple ethnic groups: 41 (2.60%); Black African, Caribbean, Black or Black British: 20 (1.30%); Other ethnic group: 10 (0.60%); Prefer not to say: 4 (0.30%); Not sure: 1 (0.10%)	Heterosexual: 1021 (64.5%); Bisexual: 264 (16.7%); Multiple sexual identities (includes people who ticked multiple sexual identity categories (e.g. bisexual AND queer; queer AND prefer to self-describe): 90 (5.70%); Gay or lesbian: 65 (4.1%); Pansexual: 45 (2.8%); Asexual: 33 (2.1%); Queer: 22 (1.4%); Not sure: 25 (1.6%); prefer not to say: 9 (0.6%); prefer to self-describe: 8 (0.5%)
<i>With intervention (n=10 studies [12 study reports])</i>						
Bedford 2024, England (JAP)(18)	Semi-structured interviews (2022-2023)	Biological males	25 (25, 100%)	22 (NR) [18-25]	White (British/Irish/Other): 23 (92%); Black	NR

						(Caribbean/African/Mixed): 1 (4%); South Asian: 1 (4%)	
Brook 2024, England and Wales (Report)(21)	Online survey and focus groups (NR)	Young people	Survey: 263 (NR, NR)‡	Survey: 18-25yrs (18 yrs: 28%; 19 yrs:15%, 20 yrs: 15%; 21 yrs: 11%; 22 yrs: 6%; 23 yrs: 11%; 24 yrs: 6%; 25 yrs: 8%); Focus group: NR	NR	22 respondents were men who have sex with men. Most common sexuality was bisexual (44%)	
Cheetham 2014, North East England (JAP)(24)	Interviews (NR)	Young people with C-cards	34 (17, 50%)	NR (NR) [14-18 years]	NR	NR	
Jones 2017, Bournemouth, Poole, Warwickshire and Plymouth (JAP)(29)	Semi-structured interviews (2013)	Young adult GP patients	30 (9, 30%)	NR (NR) [16-24]	NR	NR	
King 2019, Brighton and London (HTA monograph)(30)	WP3: Semi-structured interviews (NR); WP5: group discussion (2017)	Young people (aged 16–25 years), and men who have sex with men.	WP3: 35 (27, 77.14%) WP5: Young people cohort: 16 (NR); MSM: 7 (7, 100%)	WP3: Young people cohort: 16-20 yrs: n=8 (22.86%); Aged 21-25, n=7 (20%); MSM cohort: Aged 16-	WP3: Young people cohort: White British: n=10; White other: n=3; Black African: n=1; Asian British: n=1; MSM: White British: n=11; White other: n=2; Black British: n=2; Black other:	WP3 and WP5: Young people cohort: all heterosexual; also includes separate MSM cohort.	

						25, n=7 (20%); n=1; Chinese: n=1; older than 25, Missing: n=3; MSM cohort: n=13 (37.14%)			White British: n=11; White, other: n=2; Black British: n=2; Black, other: n=1; Chinese: n=1; Missing: n=3
						WP5: Young people cohort: <18 yrs: n=2; 18-21 yrs, n=3; 22-25 yrs: n=4. MSM cohort:<25 yrs: n=3, 25-50 yrs: n=3; >50 yrs: n=1			WP5: Young people cohort: White: n=4; Black: n=2; Asian: n=1; Mixed: n=2. MSM cohort: n=5, Asian: n=1, Other: n=1
Kinsella Bradford (JAP)(31)	2014,	Survey and focus groups (NR)	Young people 19yrs and under	14 (8, 57.14%)	Aged 19 or under	NR		NR	
Knights (JAP)(32)	2021, NR	Interviews (2019-2020)	Women aged 16–25 years in the UK.	10 (0, 0%)	NR (NR) [NR]	NR		Heterosexual: 45 (82 %); Bisexual: 10 (18%)	
Newby (JAP)(39)	2019, Coventry	Think-aloud observation (NR)	16-24 year olds accessing chlamydia self-sampling websites	12 (5, 42%)	NR (NR) [17-24]	NR		NR	
Stone Southampton Coventry (JAP)	2018, and	Semi-structured interviews (NR)	Sexually active young men aged 16–25 years	15 (15, 100%)	19.4 (2.2) [16-25]	White British: 91%		Heterosexual: 84%	
<i>SafeTxt intervention study (n=3 study reports)</i>									

Berendes (JAP)(19)	2023, UK	Open feedback and semi-structured interviews (2020)	People diagnosed at UK sexual health clinic with chlamydia, gonorrhoea or non-specific urethritis	<p>Open feedback: Intervention: 1745 (561, 32.2% [non-binary: 7, 0.4%]); control: 1781 (600, 33.7% [non-binary: 5, 0.3%])</p> <p>Interviews: 18, (4 22.22%)</p>	<p>Open feedback: 16-19 yrs: n=1284 (36.4%); 20-24 yrs n=2242 (63.6%).</p> <p>Interviewees: 18-21 yrs: n=11 (61.11%); 22-24 yrs: n=7 (38.89%)</p>	<p>Open feedback: White: 2783 (78.9%), Black (black British, Caribbean, African, other): 379 (10.8%); Asian British-Bangladeshi, Chinese, Indian, Pakistani, other: 109 (3.1%), Mixed background: 209 (5.9%), Other background: 46 (1.3%).</p> <p>Interviewees: White/British/other white background: 11 (61.11%); Other white background: 1(5.56%); Black/black British-African: 2(11.11%); Mixed background: 2 (1.11%)</p>	<p>Open feedback: Women who have sex with men only: 2161 (61.3%); Men who have sex with women only: 799 (22.7%); women who have sex with women only: 24 (0.7%); men who have sex with men only: 293 (8.3%); women who have sex with men/women: 166 (4.7%); men who have sex with women/men: 69 (2.0); non-binary people who have sex with men only 6 (0.2): 4 (0.1%); non-binary people who have sex with women and men:</p>
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						4(0.1%), Not stated: 2(0.1%).
						Interviewees: Women who have sex with men only: 11 (61.11%); Men who have sex with women only: 2 (1.11%); Men who have sex with men only: 2 (1.11%); Women who have sex with men and women: 3 (16.67%)
Free 2016, South East London, Greater Manchester and rural Cambridge (HTA monograph)(25)	Focus groups (NR); and semi structured interviews (2013- 2014)	Young people attending sexual health clinics	Focus groups: 82 (32, 39%) Open response feedback: 8 (2, 25%) Interviews: Week 2-3: 20 (8,	Focus groups: NR 17§ (NR) [16-24] Open response feedback: 19 (NR) [NR] Interviews: 16- 18 yrs: n=6; 19-		Focus group: Heterosexual: 30 (37%); Bisexual: 3 (4); Gay/lesbian: 1 (1%) No data: 48 (59%) Open response feedback: NR

		40%); 3 months:	21 yrs: n=9; 22-		Interviews: NR
		17 (NR)	24 yrs: n=5		
French 2016, South East London, Greater Manchester and rural Cambridge (JAP)(26)	Focus groups and semi structured interviews (2013-2014)	Young people attending health clinics	20 (7, 35%)	Focus groups: NR 17§ (NR) [16-24]	NR
				Interviews: 16-18 yrs: n=6; 19-21 yrs: n=9; 22-24 yrs: n=5	
Abbreviations:	JAP=journal article paper;	MSM=men who have sex with men;	NW=North West;	WP=work package	
Footnotes:	*=Unless otherwise reported;	†=High and low users of condoms;	‡=72% female, 17% trans;	§=Median	

Appendix 4: Methods table

Table A4. Methods used in included studies

Study	Recruitment method (copy/pasted from paper)	Data collection setting	Data collection method (copy/pasted from paper)	Data analysis method (copy/pasted from paper)
No intervention				
Alam 2021(16)	University students at one outer London university were invited to participate on flyers that were distributed across campus, as well as online, including via Facebook, in the hope of incorporating diverse participants. Students interested in opting into the study emailed the first author, herself a Masters student at the university, and were sent the Participant Information Sheet to read before deciding whether to participate.	Interviews were conducted and audio recorded in the university library	Semi-structured interviews, face to face; also, use of vignettes as a discussion aid by master's student.	Thematic analysis
Aranda 2018(17)	Schools sent letters to parents providing project information + giving opportunity to "opt-out" via a slip that could be returned to school. Other schools explicitly required parents to "opt-in" by returning signed slip to school. Youth	School, youth clubs/centres	15xfocus groups conducted by 2 researchers. Sample segregated by gender and age. Structured topic guide used. Also reference to interviews and interactive activities.	Interviews/focus groups: thematic analysis. Data from kites and balloons activities (e.g., post-it notes from interactive activities): Content analysis

	groups and recruitment sites: same procedures followed, with youth leader/equivalent acting as gatekeeper and locus parentis. Young people: explicit “opt-in” always required. First, young people indicated to gatekeepers whether they wanted to be involved			
Boso Perez 2023(20)	Participants sampled from the Natsal - COVID study	Telephone	Semi-structured telephone interviews conducted by trained qualitative interviewers. Fieldnotes recorded after interviews.	Thematic analysis
Buston 2014(22)	Questionnaires administered to inmates, specifically, new admissions and those in contact with a prisoner officer with a youth support remit. Secondly, a subset (n=40) were purposively sampled based on answers to questionnaire to participate in semi-structured interviews.	Young offenders institution	Part 1: self-complete questionnaires; Part 2: semi-structured interviews	Framework analysis
Chanakira 2014(23)	All students registered at a university in the north of England were sent an email inviting them to voluntarily take	Telephone	Semi-structured telephone interviews conducted by PhD researcher in 2 phases: 1st	Framework analysis, triangulated with previous survey data

part in the study. Approximately 24,000 students were registered that year and 273 volunteered to participate. Random purposive sampling used to identify participants (by classifying all cases with similar characteristics in terms of gender (male/female), age group (18–19; 20–24; 25–34; 35–44; over 45), level of study (undergraduate, postgraduate taught and research) and year of study (1st; 2nd; 3rd; 4th). Fourteen groups were identified and all cases in each group were then assigned a number and were drawn in turn using a computer generated random number generator).

phase: Dec 2008, Second phase: April-June 2009. Fieldnotes.

Greenhalgh 2016(27)	Participants were recruited from a multidisciplinary London National Health Service (NHS) clinic for 16–25-year olds, with a caseload of approximately 65 individuals with PAH. Clinicians identified clients who met inclusion criteria and introduced the study to them.	Clinic setting	Semi-structured interviews, face to face with researcher.	Interpretative phenomenological analysis
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Jaspal 2016(28)	Using a convenience sampling strategy, 16 first-year students were recruited to participate in a study of sexual behaviour and sexual health.	Likely on campus, but not clear	Semi-structured interviews conducted by UGRA.	Qualitative content analysis
Limmer 2016(35)	Participants purposively selected on basis of extent of engagement in education; residence in particularly affluent or deprived areas of town; and involvement or otherwise in the criminal justice system. Participants recruited through local schools, youth services, and the Youth Offending Team (a statutory service in the United Kingdom providing alternatives to custody for young offenders). Initial information was provided to participants through health or youth workers in the target organizations and those interested were contacted directly by the researcher.	NR	The participants took part first in focus groups (n = 5, see Table 1) and subsequently in semi-structured, in-depth interviews (n = 41). Focus groups included: drama...specifically commissioned, written, and performed as a monologue enacting the experience of a 17-year-old young man reflecting on sex, young women, pregnancy, sexually transmitted infections, and the pressure to accord with the sense of masculinities that were valued by himself and his peers. The piece was performed live at the beginning of the focus group and was used to initiate discussions on masculinities in the context of the groups	Transcripts coded using combination of a priori and emergent codes. Coding tree constructed based on emerging theories and those identified in existing literature.

			approval or otherwise of the characters actions and attitudes.
MacGilleathain 2023(36)	Cluster sampling was used to generate a purposive sample for the research. A letter outlining the purpose of the study was sent to parents/guardians via the schools. Contact details for the researcher were provided with the option to contact the researcher should they wish to withdraw their young person from participation. An information sheet detailing the study procedure with an invitation to take part was given to all young people identified as possible participants, with the options to indicate to teachers or the researcher if they chose not to participate. It was made clear that participation in the research was voluntary, and that they could withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason. Before attending data collection sessions in school, participants were informed that the	School setting	Survey (quant only); Focus groups. Qualitative data were analysed thematically using Braun and Clarke's method. Two authors independently read and familiarised themselves with the data, coded the data, met to discuss and, following consensual agreement, themes were defined and named.

	<p>study was being conducted and were given the option not to attend. At the end of the survey sessions participants were invited to take part in focus groups. Focus group participants indicated their interest in taking part to the researcher and guidance teachers.</p>		
Mahendru 2020(37)	<p>Participants were recruited with the help of gatekeepers from three sites, firstly, a student union at a University in London, secondly, through a youth worker in a youth club in West London, and thirdly through a professional contact in a sexual health organisation in South-West London.</p>	NR	<p>Conversational interviews and participant observation were used with young people in order to gain a 'thick' description, as formulated by Geertz.</p>
Morrison-Beedy 2019(38)	<p>We recruited teen participants during the summer of 2017 from an urban youth community cafe located in downtown Edinburgh, Scotland. The cafe was similar to a community-youth agency site in the United States which serves area teens with after-school programs and activities and a place for teens to connect in a teen-friendly site.</p>	Cafe	<p>We conducted focus groups weekly until data saturation occurred, which was at the end of Group 3. Following common procedures, a semi-structured interview script was used to guide the focus group discussions. We used the Information Motivation-</p> <p>Using conventional thematic analyses focusing on intentions, meaning, and context, we used an open-coding scheme that allowed the identification of themes, which were coded manually.</p>

The cafe serves downtown Edinburgh with 6–20 youth, ages 12–20 years, and predominantly from impoverished areas, served daily.

Behavioural Skills Model to guide our approach to focus group questions. Open ended questions addressed major theoretical constructs of information, motivation, and skills because they related to risk and protective behaviours. We also asked about recruitment and retention strategies for future intervention studies. The use of the IMB model was fluid, and participants were given opportunities to share opinions and experiences beyond the IMB constructs. We began with broader questions and added probes (e.g., help me understand that better) to elicit more in depth responses as appropriate. Transcription data integrated with field notes

Nwaosu 2023(40); Nwaosu 2025(41)	<p>Combination of snowball and purposive sampling strategies. We avoided recruiting from sexual health clinics to ensure the experiences of those who may have disengaged from mainstream services could be captured. Consequently, barbershops were chosen as the recruitment location as their integral and cultural value within the Black community provided access to Black men who may not be accessed at mainstream health services like sexual health clinics or commercial and social venues like nightclubs and social gatherings. Initially, three barbershops (one in South London, one in East London and one in West London) with large customer bases and social media followings were identified as recruitment locations. Barbershops were contacted and asked to display the recruitment poster in a visible location within their shop. Barbers were also asked to alert eligible customers of the</p>	Remote	<p>Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 10 participants. Interviews were conducted between September 2020 and March 2021 by an experienced sexual health practitioner and researcher educated to Master’s degree level and undertaking a doctoral qualification. Microsoft Teams was used to conduct and record all interviews due to government-imposed coronavirus restrictions on household mixing. Interviews ranged between 1 hour 1 minute and 2 hours 2 minutes. was used to conduct and record all interviews due to government-imposed coronavirus restrictions on household mixing.</p>	<p>A reflexive thematic analysis was conducted to explore and identify patterns, and draw interpretations from the data. Data analysis was conducted by a doctoral student supervised by two experienced qualitative researchers.</p>
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study. The poster contained a barcode which took participants directly to the study registration page when scanned, where participants could access the study information sheet and privacy notice, register interest in participating, complete a consent form and schedule an initial telephone consultation. As coronavirus restrictions resulted in the closure of barbershops for significant periods, a change in recruitment strategy was enforced. Barbershops were subsequently asked to share an image format of the poster on their respective social media platforms accompanied by a website link to the study registration page to enable customers to express an interest in participation. Subsequently, individuals who registered to participate were contacted for an initial telephone consultation to determine eligibility, obtain informed consent, agree an

	interview date and time, and obtain demographic information.			
Wayal 2020(43)	Convenience sampling was used to recruit participants from five sexual health clinics and community settings such as colleges; with the help of community-based organisations working with black Caribbean communities on a range of issues such as depression, unemployment, teenage pregnancy, youth groups, and condom promotion. Posters with contact details of the researchers were used to advertise the study in the sexual health clinics, community-based organisations and on Twitter so potential participants could directly contact the researcher. Black Caribbean community oriented commercial enterprises. such as supermarkets, restaurants/take-away shops etc. were approached directly by researchers or targeted via Twitter (if they had a Twitter presence).	City of their residence in a quiet place at either participating sexual health clinic or community-based organisation office	Face-to-face focus groups and in-depth interviews facilitated by female researchers with qualitative methods expertise - topic guides used.	Framework analysis

Additionally, sexual health clinic and community-based organisation staff approached potential participants about the study, and passed their contact details to the research team.

Winters 2024(44)	<p>Survey: Survey was live from June to July 2023 and shared with young people via social media, at Brook clinics and by partner organisations. The survey was also promoted through paid social media advertising and by sexual health influencers. Due to low uptake of respondents assigned male at birth (AMAB), a shorter targeted survey was promoted in January 2024 using paid social media advertising, a micro influencer and through partner organisations. 330 AMAB young people responded to the 2024 survey.</p> <p>Qualitative research: Recruited through targeted advertising at educational institutions and charities working with young people.</p>	<p>Mainly online; 1xfocus group face-to-face</p>	<p>Open and closed survey questions. 4x90min small online group discussions, 2x60min one-to-one interviews, led by researcher and supported by note taker. Feedback on recommendations from participants at event.</p>	<p>Free text survey questions: coding structure. SGD/interviews: thematic analysis</p>
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CONUNDRUM

Lewis 2021a(33); Workshops: Young people were recruited through youth organisations in three health board areas: Castlemilk youth complex, I Youth zone LGBTQ+ Group (Greenock), sexspression Glasgow, Hype Youth CLD (Livenston), 6VT youth care (Edinburgh), Landed peer education project. Discussion groups: Given the timing of the SGDs(e.g. during the initial months of the COVID-19 pandemic) and the sensitivity of the topic, we decided to prioritise recruitment of friendship groups in order to maximise young people’s comfort participating in a digital SGD. Young people were recruited via youth organisations, higher education settings and existing contacts within the research team.

Lewis 2021b(34) Workshops: held in youth groups’ usual meeting place or alternative local community venue, online discussion due to pandemic; Online survey

6xface-face workshops with young people moderated by 2 members of research team: identity using drawing activities to generate discussion, Online survey (quant data), 5xsmall group discussions moderated by researchers.

Interventions

Bedford 2024(18) **Intervention:** via two pathways: the sexual health clinic route (clinic team over Microsoft teams Interviews conducted One-to-one semi-structured Thematic analysis: interviews based on Process- development of a codebook of

referral) or the community route (self-referral). Clinic referral involved eight participating National Health Service (NHS) Trusts across England. introduced Participant Identification Centers (PICs) in the form of General Practitioners surgeries to access participants outside the clinic catchment area. PICs sent a text message to eligible young men with a link to the study sign-up page.

(telephone/face-to-face)

Evaluation framework. deductive codes and categories
Conducted by first/second based on the study aims.
authors via Microsoft teams. Applied deductively to data,
Audio-recorded via Microsoft also incorporating inductive
Teams. codes

Qualitative evaluation: At the six-month follow-up period, the participants were asked whether they would be willing to be contacted (via Lifeguide1) by the research team to participate in a short interview remotely via Teams (either telephone or face-to-face) about their involvement in the study. The research team were notified of interested participants via email and participants were purposively

	sampled based on characteristics such as referral route and trial arm to ensure a range of participants were represented. Selected participants were sent an email invitation including a Calendly link to book a suitable time slot for the interview			
Brook 2024(21)	Survey circulated through Brook's social media channels, also gathered supplementary data following our initial research and have updated our report with findings from: - Condoms and Contraception Survey 2024, and - Brook's online contraception tool data	Online survey	Survey; 1xfocus group	NR
Cheetham 2014(24)	Recruited by the author, with support from youth and health workers.	The interviews took place on site of services	Face to face interview	Framework analysis
Jones 2017(29)	Practices provided researchers with an anonymised list of patients within the 16–24 age bracket attending the surgery that day and their appointment time, in	NR	Semi-structured interviews, face to face carried out by three researchers.	Thematic analysis

order to assist researchers in identifying potential participants. Researchers approached patients in the waiting area of 11 general practices (irrespective of their reason for attendance) from March to June 2013 and invited them to participate in a face-to-face interview in private...When researchers approached potential participants, they introduced themselves and explained the nature of the study

King 2019(30)

WP3: We purposively sampled young men and women and MSM who were attending NHS SH services. The recruitment framework categorised MSM by age and young people by age and gender, with equal recruitment across two clinic sites.

WP5: We sampled young men and women and MSM who were attending SH services and completed the triage process. We sequentially recruited service users who scored as 'high risk',

WP3: Within the clinical setting

WP5: Interviews: telephone; group discussions: clinical setting

WP3: Semi-structured interviews in person

WP5: Interviews were by telephone and group discussions were conducted within the clinical setting. Interviews were designed to last 20 minutes, and the group discussions 45 minutes.

Framework analysis

aiming to recruit 24 service users across two clinics. HCPs were purposefully recruited from participating clinics to represent both HAs and other clinical staff, with two focus group discussions planned for each participating site. Service user participants were recruited from participating clinics. They were approached in the clinic waiting room and given a study information sheet to read before deciding to take part.

Kinsella 2014(31)	<p>Convenience sampling methods were used because it was important that young people were offered the opportunity to get involved in the evaluation of the scheme. Two members of C-Card staff working at different organisations helped to recruit young people to the focus groups but they did not attend the groups themselves. These staff members promoted the focus group among the young people in their organisation through word of mouth and provided</p>	<p>School and children's care home</p>	<p>Survey (quant) and 2 mixed-gender focus groups. Latter facilitated by members of evaluation team and used an interview schedule.</p>	<p>Focus groups: Framework analysis. Combined with findings from questionnaire data.</p>
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them with an information leaflet explaining the research. They then collected the names of any individuals who were interested in taking part in the focus group. These participants were then contacted and invited to take part in the focus group.

Knights 2021(32)	Recruited from HERS pilot trial.	NR	Interviews	Thematic analysis
Newby 2019(39)	Chlamydia self-sampling website freetest.me	Participants met virtually with a researcher via Skype for one-on-one interviews. At the start of the interview, participants were provided with the URL for Wrapped and asked to load the website. They were then asked to share their screen via Skype.	Each participant was asked to work through the content, as they would if browsing in their own time, and to “think aloud” as they did so, verbalizing thoughts on the look, feel, content, and ease of use and navigation. Prompts were used to encourage participants to “think aloud” and to provide feedback on particular aspects. Due to the personal nature of component 6, participants were asked to view the video content in their own time and provide written	Content analysis was used to organize the data into themes.

feedback after the interview via email. At relevant points during the interview, participants were instructed to open the appropriate items that had been posted to them. First impressions and thoughts on whether these would be used and how they could be improved were then collected. Multimedia Appendix 2 provides the interview schedule for the think-aloud interviews.

Stone 2018(42)	Following completion of data collection activities, young men who participated in the study and health promotion professionals involved in recruitment were invited to participate in a follow-up process evaluation interview	Telephone	Semi-structured telephone interview schedule informed by Saunders et al. Interviews "semi-transcribed".	Framework analysis
<i>SafeTxt</i>				
Berendes 2023(19); Free 2016(25); French 2016(26)	Testing and refining messages focus groups: Clinic staff invited patients attending community sexual and	Testing and refining messages: NR	Testing and refining messages: Focus group	Thematic analysis. Results from open feedback comments and interviews triangulated with

reproductive health services in an inner city in the south of England (south-east London), a city in the north of England (Greater Manchester) and a rural area (Cambridgeshire) to participate

Feedback on intervention after delivered to phones: Seven days after enrolment, OM contacted the participants by phone and asked them for further feedback regarding intervention

Qualitative interviews post-pilot trial: main trial consent form included a tick box asking if participants would be willing to be contacted about participating in an interview. Of those indicating that they were willing to be contacted, we purposively sampled participants to ensure variation according to age, sex, STI test result at enrolment and treatment group. Control

Feedback: telephone
Qualitative interviews: telephone

Feedback: Telephone interview
Qualitative interviews: Semi-structured telephone interviews by two researchers between Oct 13-Jan 14 2-3 weeks after enrolment. Follow-up interviews: 3 months after sending postal testing kits.

quantitative trial data (including primary, secondary and intermediate outcomes) and data from telephone interviews conducted as part of 2013 feasibility trial 2–3 weeks after starting messages¹⁷ looking for consistencies and inconsistencies across the different data sources and searching for deviant cases.

group participants were included as we wanted to explore young people's experiences of participation in the pilot trial.

Appendix 5: Key characteristics of interventions in included studies

Table A5. Key characteristics of interventions

Study	Intervention name	Aim (copy/pasted from paper)	Brief summary (copy/pasted from paper)	How accessed (Who delivers)
<i>Category: Access improvement</i>				
Brook 2024(21); Cheetham 2014(24); Kinsella 2014(31)	C-Card scheme	Increase availability and accessibility of condoms to young people; increase the numbers of young men accessing sexual health services; reach young people living in deprived communities; raise young people's awareness of sexual safety; increase condom use and decrease embarrassment; develop and enhance the skills of workers	C-Cards can be used by young people to access free condoms and sexual health advice at different community-based outlets. A C-Card is a credit card-style membership card issued to a young person who registers with the scheme by appropriately trained healthcare professionals and youth workers following a C-Card induction process. The induction includes discussion about sex and relationships, a practical demonstration of how to use a condom and an opportunity to ask questions. Many young people hear about the scheme from their peers, and choose to register for a C-Card with their friends	Community based outlets (Trained health care professionals and youth workers)
<i>Category: Behaviour change</i>				
Berendes 2023(19); Free 2016(25);	SafeTxt	Reduce STIs in young people by supporting them in telling a partner about an infection, using condoms and	A text message-based intervention designed to promote safer sex behaviours, such as correct and consistent condom use, informing partners about STIs, and testing for STIs prior to condomless sex with a new	Text message intervention (automated)

French 2016(26)	obtaining testing before condomless sex with a new partner	partner [18]. The intervention employed educational, enabling, and incentivizing behaviour change functions and identified the following twelve behaviour change techniques in effective face-to-face safer sex interventions: (1) information about health consequences of behaviour, (2) instruction on how to carry out the behaviour, (3) demonstrations of risk reduction behaviour, (4) social support, (5) emotional support, (6) social rewards, (7) non-specific incentives, (8) encouragement to add objects to the environment, (9) anticipated regret, (10) problem solving, (11) action planning techniques, and (12) reframing. Intervention: messages that support correct STI treatment (taking the treatment, informing partners of the infection, abstaining from sex for one week after you and your partners are treated), and promote safer sex behaviours.
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<i>Category: Educational</i>					
Bedford 2024(18); Stone 2018(42)	The Based Intervention Strategy UK)	Home- (HIS- alone in a “low pressure” environment	Increase condom use and enjoyment by enhancing fit and feel through the practice of applying, using and removing a range of different condoms and lubricants alone in a “low pressure” environment	Participants were provided with a condom kit containing a wide range of condoms of different brands, shapes and sizes, lubricants (24 condoms and 12 lubricants in total), a condom guide, and a condom “fit kit”. Supplying individuals with a large array of different condoms is a valuable teaching tool to educate about	Clinic or self-referral (Health professional)

			condom fit-and-feel. Participants were asked to complete a two-week self-practice testing period with the kit, focusing on pleasurable sensations, and to rate the condoms in terms of fit-and-feel after each condom practice session on an online form. Participants had further opportunities to order more supplies of the condoms and lubricants of their choice each month for up to twelve months.	
Knights 2021(32)	Home-based Exercises for Responsible Sex (HERS)	The objective of HERS-UK was to improve the sexual experience of using condoms for young women, address negative attitudes towards condoms, increase self-efficacy and skill to use condoms and ultimately, increase motivation to use condoms	Based on information-motivation-behaviour skills (IBM) model. Firstly, providing information helps the individual decide whether to engage in a particular health behaviour. Personal motivation involves addressing attitudes that may influence the individual's likelihood of engaging in that behaviour, and social motivation involves increasing social support, i.e. normalisation of the behaviour within a social group. Finally, behavioural skills include perceived and objective skills as well as confidence (i.e. self-efficacy) for carrying out the behaviour. Intervention incorporates core training to increase condom skills and self-efficacy, with home-based practice using a range of different condoms and lubricants. Young women are asked to rate the condoms and lubricants practised with, on various dimensions, including how pleasurable	In community settings (trained motivational interviewer)

the experience was. Components: teaching session drawing on motivational interviewing approach to support and enable behaviour change purpose of the session was to provide information about condoms and lubricants, with an emphasis on maximising pleasure and reducing discomfort and interruption to improve the sexual experience, and thereby change attitudes towards condoms. Information was provided about condom and lube use within the context of vaginal, anal and oral sex. The second aim of the core training session was to develop skills in using condoms correctly, thus reducing errors and problems and increasing self-efficacy, and positive condom attitudes and experiences. The researcher demonstrated how to apply a condom correctly using a realistic size dildo, and young women had the opportunity to practise themselves, and receive feedback. An instruction and information leaflet was also provided with instructions on how to apply a condom correctly, so young women could refer to this when practising at home. In addition, the leaflet contained information about different types of condoms and lubes, tips on how

to make condom use more pleasurable, and condom testing and rating instructions, so participants were clear about what they were being asked to do. Participants were also told about novel ways of applying condoms (such as by mouth) in the session. Along with the instruction and information leaflet, participants received a condom kit to take home. Participants were also informed about different sizes of condoms, and provided with a size guide, 3 weeks to test and try out a range of condoms and lubricants. The kit contained 10 different condoms (two of each type, 20 in total) designed for women's pleasure and comfort, such as textured, flavoured, coloured, extra sensitive, non-latex and coated with stimulating gel. In addition, a condom designed for women, with a clean smell and attractive packaging was included, and one that came in fun, unique packaging. The researcher discussed the different attributes of each condom with the participant. In addition, a selection of water and silicone-based lubes were included and a realistic-sized dildo. Each kit contained two of each type of condom(20 in total), so that young women could

			experiment with the condom alone using the dildo, and/or with a sexual partner.	
Newby 2019(39)	Wrapped	<p>Reduce incidence of STIs in at-risk population by increasing correct and consistent condom use with sexual partners. The agreed upon performance objectives were as follows:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Decide to use condoms for vaginal or anal sex 2. Obtain condoms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify where and how to access condoms • Select preferred type of condom • Buy or request condoms • Maintain supply of condoms 3. Make condoms available at all times 4. Make partner aware of intention to use condoms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify when to make intention to use condoms known • Have plan for what one will say and do to make 	<p>The ideas generated by the workshop led to the development of six specific intervention components. These evolved and were refined through an iterative process that involved considerable input from young people and experts as described within the Methods section. The finalized components are briefly described in the following sections. Please refer to Multimedia Appendix 6 for a detailed description.</p> <p>Component 1: Sample Pack The sample pack is a box containing 12 condoms and two sachets of lubricant. This component aims to help young people to identify their preferred type of condom and lubricant; to help them overcome any issues around the smell, fit, and feel of condoms; and to make positive associations between condoms and pleasure (see Multimedia Appendices 7 and 8).</p> <p>Component 2: Order Condoms Young people are able to order condoms via a free mail-order condom distribution service. This component aims to make condoms more accessible (i.e.,</p>	Website (automated)

intention to use condoms known

- Have plan for how to deal with, and pose solutions to,

partner's disagreement or refusal to use condoms

5. Correctly use condoms

affordable and obtainable) to young people (see Multimedia Appendix 9).

Component 3: Condom Carrier

The carrier is a small headphone case that has a hidden compartment for storing condoms and lubricant. This aims to increase condom availability (see Multimedia Appendix 10).

Component 4: Using Condoms

This video provides step-by-step instructions on how to put on a condom using a demonstrator. As well as practical tips, advice is given on how to make this part of the flow of sex. This aims to increase young people's self-efficacy for condom use.

Component 5: Discussing Condoms

This is a series of seven videos where young people talk about ways in which they have brought up condom use with partners

in the past and introduced them into sex. The aim is to help users plan the best time to bring up condom use with their partner and what to do or say if they resist (see Multimedia Appendix 12).

Component 6: Real Life

This is a series of three videos featuring three real couples aged 18-24 years who talk about and

demonstrate condom use: who does it, techniques, how to make their use part of sex. The aim is to build positive associations between condom use and pleasure (see Multimedia Appendix 13).

Category: Screening

Jones 2017(29)	3Cs and HIV	Chlamydia and HIV testing, contraception advice, and free condoms offered in general practice	<p>A complex intervention carried out by Public Health England (PHE) in 2010 (the Chlamydia Intervention Randomised Trial [CIRT]) aimed at increasing opportunistic chlamydia testing in GP practices. It used the theory of planned behaviour to influence attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control, and proved successful (success was measured by a sustained change in chlamydia screening and diagnosis).⁹ Therefore, an updated intervention was planned by PHE to include a broader opportunistic sexual health offer including chlamydia testing, contraception advice, sign-posting to free condoms, and HIV testing where appropriate — this is referred to as 3Cs and HIV. The authors aimed to expand on the previous research and use qualitative methods to explore patients’ attitudes to this wider 3Cs and HIV offer, using theory of planned behaviour to provide understanding of potential facilitators/barriers to implementing intervention.</p>	GP (GP)
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King 2019(30)	Triage tool	<p>Identify individuals at high risk of STI. The triage tool was set to a risk referral threshold that we had planned would identify 5% of young people and 15% of MSM to be at high risk, based on the model performance from WP2.</p>	<p>Three-part intervention package – (1) Triage tool to score patients as being at high or low STI risk using routine data, (2) study-designed web page with tailored SH information for all patients, regardless of risk and (3) brief one-to-one session based on motivational interviewing for high-risk patients. Participants triaged based on risk score and were eligible to be offered one or both interventions. High intensity intervention: brief one to one session. Low intensity: offered to all patients: web page containing SH information. Android tablet-based system using opensource software. This altered the patient pathway from that originally proposed: the triage tool was self-completed by patients prior to their appointment, rather than being conducted as part of the consultation with HCP. This system was in place for 1 month before pilot so could be integrated into clinic and to allow providers to become familiar with study protocol. This was followed by one to one session</p>	<p>In clinic, prior to appointment (triage tool self-completed, followed by 1:1 session with HCP)</p>
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Appendix 6. Quality appraisal table

Table A6. Quality appraisal scores for individual studies

Study	Is the research question clear?	Is the theoretical or ideological perspective of the author (or funder) explicit?	Has this influenced the study design, methods or research findings?	Is the study design appropriate to answer the question?	Is the context or setting adequately described?	Is the sample adequate to explore the range of subjects and settings, and from an appropriate population?	Was the data collection adequately described?	Was data collection rigorously conducted to ensure confidence in the findings?	Was there evidence that the data analysis was rigorously conducted to ensure confidence in the findings?	Are the findings substantiated by the data?	Has consideration been given to any limitations of the methods or data that may have affected the results?	Do any claims to generalisability follow logically and theoretically from the data?	Have ethical issues been addressed and confidentiality respected?	Are the interventions of interest clearly described?
<i>No intervention</i>														
Alam 2021(16)	Yes	Yes	Yes	CT	No	No	Yes	CT	CT	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	n/a
Aranda 2018(17)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	n/a
Boso Perez 2023(20)	Yes	No	CT	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	n/a
Buston 2014(22)	Yes	No	CT	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	n/a
Chanakira 2014(23)	Yes	No	CT	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	n/a
Greenhalgh 2016(27)	Yes	No	CT	Yes	Yes	N	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	n/a

Study	Is the research question clear?	Is the theoretical or ideological perspective of the author (or funder) explicit?	Has this influenced the study design, methods or research findings?	Is the study design appropriate to answer the question?	Is the context or setting adequately described?	Is the sample adequate to explore the range of subjects and settings, and from an appropriate population?	Was the data collection adequately described?	Was data collection rigorously conducted to ensure confidence in the findings?	Was there evidence that the data analysis was rigorously conducted to ensure confidence in the findings?	Are the findings substantiated by the data?	Has consideration been given to any limitations of the methods or data that may have affected the results?	Do any claims to generalisability follow logically and theoretically from the data?	Have ethical issues been addressed and confidentiality respected?	Are the interventions of interest clearly described?
Jaspal 2016(28)	Yes	No	CT	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	n/a
Limmer 2016(35)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	yes	Yes	n/a
MacGilleathain 2023(36)	Yes	No	CT	Yes	No	Yes	No	CT	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	n/a
Mahendru 2020(37)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	CT	CT	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	n/a
Morrison-Beedy 2019(38)	Yes	No	CT	Yes	Yes	Yes	CT	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	n/a
Nwaosu 2023(40); Nwaosu 2025(41)	Yes	No	CT	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	n/a
Wayal 2020(43)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	n/a

Study	Is the research question clear?	Is the theoretical or ideological perspective of the author (or funder) explicit?	Has this influenced the study design, methods or research findings?	Is the study design appropriate to answer the question?	Is the context or setting adequately described?	Is the sample adequate to explore the range of subjects and settings, and from an appropriate population?	Was the data collection adequately described?	Was data collection rigorously conducted to ensure confidence in the findings?	Was there evidence that the data analysis was rigorously conducted to ensure confidence in the findings?	Are the findings substantiated by the data?	Has consideration been given to any limitations of the methods or data that may have affected the results?	Do any claims to generalisability follow logically and theoretically from the data?	Have ethical issues been addressed and confidentiality respected?	Are the interventions of interest clearly described?
Winters 2024(44)	Yes	No	CT	Yes	Yes	CT	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	CT	n/a
<i>CONUNDRUM</i>														
Lewis 2021a(33); Lewis 2021b(34)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	CT	CT	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	n/a
<i>Interventions</i>														
Bedford 2024(18)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	N	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Brook 2024(21)	Yes	No	CT	Yes	No	CT	No	CT	CT	Yes	No	No	CT	Yes
Cheetham 2014(24)	Yes	No	CT	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	CT	CT	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Jones 2017(29)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
King 2019(30)	Yes	No	CT	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Study	Is the research question clear?	Is the theoretical or ideological perspective of the author (or funder) explicit?	Has this influenced the study design, methods or research findings?	Is the study design appropriate to answer the question?	Is the context or setting adequately described?	Is the sample adequate to explore the range of subjects and settings, and from an appropriate population?	Was the data collection adequately described?	Was data collection rigorously conducted to ensure confidence in the findings?	Was there evidence that the data analysis was rigorously conducted to ensure confidence in the findings?	Are the findings substantiated by the data?	Has consideration been given to any limitations of the methods or data that may have affected the results?	Do any claims to generalisability follow logically and theoretically from the data?	Have ethical issues been addressed and confidentiality respected?	Are the interventions of interest clearly described?
Kinsella 2014(31)	Yes	No	CT	Yes	Yes	CT	Yes	CT	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Knights 2021(32)	Yes	No	CT	Yes	No	CT	No	CT	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Newby 2019(39)	Yes	No	CT	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Stone 2018(42)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	CT	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>SafeTxt</i>														
Berendes 2023(19); Free 2016(25); French 2016(26)	Yes	No	CT	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

CT=Can't Tell

Appendix 7: Studies supporting implications for policy, practice and research

Stated implication in Discussion	Supporting theme or subtheme: Supporting factors or concepts(n studies)
Implications for policy	
<p>Our findings highlight how factors influencing condom use may vary across different groups of young people, meaning approaches to support condom use in young people will need to consider the needs of different population groups.</p>	<p>This recommendation is based on the section: Relation of findings to specific population groups, where specific consideration is given to groups based on PROGRESS-PLUS criteria, with reference to the limited evidence-base which may impact generalisability of findings.</p>
<p>Government policy to encourage condom use will need to consider all socio-ecological factors presented in this review.</p>	
<p>Our synthesis highlights how condom use, or non-use, may be heavily influenced by society and gender norms around sexual behaviour which may disproportionately impact on certain communities, including socially excluded young men or those from some religious and/or ethnic minority communities.</p>	<p>Theme 1 (all subthemes): Societal and community norms (20 studies, 21 articles)(16-19, 22-24, 28, 29, 31-33, 35-38, 40-44)</p> <p>Particularly relevant factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stigmatisation of sex (n=9)(16-18, 22, 28, 36-38, 40, 41) • Female sexual pleasure: Knowledge and skills re: condom use, empowerment (n=2)(see also 1.0: Intrapersonal factors)(32, 37) • Fears over young people’s sexuality (n=3)(17, 36, 37) <p>Factors relevant to socially excluded men and/or ethnic minority groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethnicity (n=1)(42) • Religion (n=5)(23, 29, 33, 37, 44) Particularly concept: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exclusion of educational content in faith-based schools(33, 37, 44) • Ethnicity/culture (n=4)(23, 28, 37, 43) • Disparity in gender norms (n=11)(16, 22, 23, 28, 31-33, 35, 37, 40, 43) Inclusive of the following concepts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sex with a number of partners perceived more positively in men(16, 28, 31, 32, 35, 43)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Protecting, challenging and reinforcing masculine and feminine identities (28, 35, 37, 40, 43) - Culture of non-condom use(22, 23, 35, 38) - Defining acceptable behavioural norms when it comes to sex (24, 35, 43) - Dehumanisation of women (22, 35, 40) • Media <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pornography (n=3)(33, 35, 40) - Exposure to/reinforcement of societal norms (n=3)(23, 40, 41, 43) - Exposure to relatable experiences (n=2)(41, 44) <p>Other relevant concepts from Theme 1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reinforcement of masculine identity through derogation of women and/or MSM (n=2)(22, 35) - Acceptability of concurrent relationship-use of condoms in casual/side relationships(n=1) (43) - Denigration of women seen as “promiscuous” Perception of risk (n=1)(35) - Masculine values and source of sexual educators and role models (n=4) (22, 35, 38, 41) - Culture of non-condom use (n=4) (22, 23, 35, 38) <p>Theme 3 (all subthemes): Inter-personal factors between sexual partners (15 studies, 17 articles)(16, 19, 21, 22, 25, 27, 28, 30, 32, 33, 35, 37, 38, 40, 41, 43, 44)</p> <p>For relevant factors: see all listed in Tables 7-9.</p>
<p>Government policy can encourage development of strategies to support health and social care services deliver sexual health care which promotes sex within healthy, consenting relationships (whether casual or otherwise).</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Acknowledgement of the role sex plays in young men’s developing sexual identity and status among peers is needed....</p>	<p>Factors identified within theme 1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disparity in gender norms (n=11)(16, 22, 23, 28, 31-33, 35, 37, 40, 43) Inclusive of the following concepts:

<p>.... with further consideration of how their views of sex and relationships can be changed to support male responsibility for their own and their partner’s sexual health, including condom use and respect of their partners needs/wishes, as a normal part of healthy masculine identity.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Protecting, challenging and reinforcing masculine and feminine identities (28, 35, 37, 40, 43) - Defining acceptable behavioural norms when it comes to sex (24, 35, 43) - Dehumanisation of women (22, 35, 40) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peer group views (n=11)(16, 19, 22-24, 31, 33, 38, 41, 43, 44) • Social inclusion/exclusion (n=7)(16, 24, 35-37, 41, 43) <p>Factors identified within theme 4.1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preserving masculine identities (n=6)(17, 22, 24, 28, 33, 35) <p>Related factors:</p> <p>Subtheme 3.1 Heteronormative gender dynamics (supported by 13 studies, 14 articles).(16, 21, 22, 27, 28, 32, 33, 35, 37, 38, 40, 41, 43, 44). Relevant factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stereotypical gender roles (n=5)(21, 22, 33, 38, 44) • Power imbalance (n=12)(16, 22, 27, 28, 32, 33, 35, 37, 38, 40, 41, 43, 44) <p>Subtheme 3.2: Spectrum of communication (supported by 11 studies, 12 articles).(16, 19, 25, 27, 30, 33, 35, 37, 38, 40, 43, 44) Relevant factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard to talk about sex and condoms (n=8)(16, 19, 25, 30, 32, 35, 37, 38, 44) • Coercion (n=5)(16, 25, 33, 37, 43) • Trust violation (n=8)(16, 27, 33, 35, 37, 38, 40, 43)
<p>Policy can also play a role in supporting and empowering women to access sexual health services and within their sexual relationships to ensure they can access</p>	<p>Theme 1: detailed above</p> <p>Relevant concepts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Female knowledge and skills re: condom use, empowerment (n=2)(32, 37) • Unequal burden of contraception on women(n=1)(33)

<p>the care they need and have their wishes respected.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Negotiating safe sex (n=2)(23, 37) • Knowledge of safe sex (n=3)(23, 28, 37) • Knowledge of own preferences (n=1)(37) <p>Theme 2: Institutional factors (supported by 19 studies, 24 articles).(16-19, 21, 23-26, 28-34, 36-42, 44)</p> <p>Relevant factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safe service environment (n=14)(17, 21, 23-26, 28, 30-34, 36, 40, 41, 44) • Current sexual health education not comprehensive enough (n=11)(16-19, 31, 33, 36-38, 40, 41, 44) <p>Theme 3: see above</p> <p>Theme 4: Behavioural capability knowledge and skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-knowledge Relevant factors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Familiarity with own needs and desires (n=2)(33, 37) • What is acceptable to me-behaviour from others (n=2)(16, 37) • Learning new skills (n=6)(17-19, 26, 31, 32, 42) Relevant concepts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identifying and managing unsafe situations (n=1)(38) • Self-efficacy/ Empowerment (n=7)(16, 17, 19, 25, 26, 32, 33, 37, 44) Relevant concepts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Confidence negotiating condom use with partner (n=2)(19, 25, 26, 37)
<p>Consideration of the needs of young people from certain ethnic minority and religious communities is required to ensure their educational and service access needs are met.</p>	<p>Subtheme 1.1.</p> <p>Factor: Religion (n=5).(23, 29, 33, 37, 44). Associated concepts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Protective factor against engaging in risky sex(23) - Knowledge and skills relating to sex and condom use(23) - Engagement with health/educational services(29) - Exclusion of educational content in faith-based schools(33, 37, 44) <p>Other concepts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acceptability of accessing learning opportunities regarding condom use(42)

	<p>Subtheme 2.2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impact of religion (n=3)(33, 37, 44)
<p>Policies impacting on health and education provision within religious and cultural communities which encourage an abstinence focused sexual-risk reduction approach needs to be carefully considered, to ensure that young people can access comprehensive education and health services whilst still respecting their religious and cultural views/background.</p>	<p>See above.</p>
<p>Implications for school education and health services</p>	
<p>Consideration of the environment young people need to be able to engage with learning about sexual health and condom use. Factors to consider may include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunities to access to a private space to seek support or discuss issues relating to sexual health with same-gendered peers. • Delivery by a person knowledgeable about sexual health, who is non-judgemental and seen as 'separate' from the teachers delivering their education. • Tailoring of components delivered jointly across all genders, and topics delivered in separate gender groups 	<p>Theme 2.0: Institutional factors.</p> <p>Subtheme 2.2: Inadequate school education</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Need for a safe space (n=7)(17, 18, 31, 33, 36, 38, 44) <p>Subtheme 2.2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Need for safe space: see above <p>Subtheme 2.2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Need for safe space: see above ○ Current sexual health education not comprehensive enough (n=11) (16-19, 31, 33, 36-38, 40, 41, 44)

<p>queer/questioning, intersex and asexual.</p> <p>o Going beyond an abstinence or risk prevention approach, to incorporate learning and discussion on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How sex can be a pleasurable activity; • Encouraging young people to talk about sex, condoms and other contraceptive methods with their sexual partners through role play; • Identifying, planning for and navigating potentially risky situations, including issues relating to consent and alcohol/drug use; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addressing societal views and expectations around sex, including gendered norms for acceptable behaviour. 	<p>Subtheme 2.2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current sexual health education not comprehensive enough (see above) Relevant concepts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overlooking STIs (n=1)(16) - Issues relating to consent/legalities (n=1)(17) - ‘Facts based’: Relationship issues not covered (n=3)(18, 33, 38) - Information on condom use basic (n=1)(33) - Abstinence focused (n=1)(36) - Need for information on managing situations where young person at risk of engaging in unsafe or unwanted sex, including need for ‘real life’ examples (n=3)(19, 37, 38) - Counteracts messages black men receive from media (n=1)(40) • Other issues affecting acceptability to young people (n=4)(17, 18, 33, 36) Relevant concepts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased focus on pleasure requested (n=2)(18, 33) <p>Subtheme 4:2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning new skills - Identifying and managing unsafe situations (n=1)(38) <p>Theme 1: All subthemes, see Table 1</p>
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<p>o Providing opportunities for young people to learn from the experiences of role models, scenarios or role play of situations to which they can relate.</p>	<p>Subtheme 2.2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current sexual health education not comprehensive enough (see above) Relevant concepts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Desire to develop skills via role play (n=1)(38) - Need for information on managing situations where young person at risk of engaging in unsafe or unwanted sex, including need for ‘real life’ examples (n=3)(19, 37, 38) • Heteronormative focus to contraceptive education (n=6)(17, 19, 33, 36, 37, 44) Relevant concepts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Challenges to women in negotiating safe sex: need for real life examples (n=1)(37) <p>Subtheme 2.1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health services a trustworthy source of information (n=5)(21, 25, 33, 34, 38, 39)
<p>o Raising awareness of places young people can go to for further support outside of and within school, including increased promotion of the availability of school nurses (where relevant).</p>	<p>Subtheme 2.2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current sexual health education not comprehensive enough (see above) Relevant concepts <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signposting to alternative information/resources/services (n=3)(17, 31, 44) - Visible source of external and knowledgeable support (n=4)(17, 31, 36, 44) <p>Subtheme 4.2: Behavioural capacity, knowledge and skills (n=18)(16-19, 21, 25, 26, 28-34, 36-40, 42, 44) Relevant concepts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased awareness of sexual health services needed (n=7)(17, 21, 28, 29, 31, 33, 34, 36, 44) - Supporting young people to find and navigate new knowledge (n=4)(16, 17, 33, 44) </p>

<p>o Supporting young people to develop critical thinking skills to evaluate and counteract information and material they access online and via social media. This may include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to evaluate the reliability and trustworthiness of information about sex and condom use; • Providing examples of what ‘normal’ sexual behaviour can look like across different communities; • Counteracting negative messaging about women and condom use. 	<p>Subtheme 1.4: Media. See Table 4 Subtheme 3.1: Heteronormative gender dynamics. See Table 7</p> <p>Other relevant concepts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Subtheme 2.2: Current sexual health education not comprehensive enough (see above). Concept: Counteracts messages black men receive from media (n=1) (40) - Subtheme 4.2: Supporting young people to find and navigate new knowledge (n=4)(16, 17, 33, 44) <p>Subtheme 4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning new skills (n=6)(17-19, 26, 31, 32, 42) <p>Relevant concepts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supporting young people to find and navigate new knowledge (n=4)(16, 17, 33, 44)
<p>Health services</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider the range of accessibility needs of young people living within specific communities in relation to accessing free condoms and sexual health advice. Issues to consider may include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Access to private spaces and technology to access online appointments or text messages; o Transport networks and costs for those living in rural communities; o Promoting a range of condom delivery options, such as private pick-up rooms within 	<p>Subtheme 2.1: Health services</p> <p>Factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safe service environment (n=14)(17, 21, 23-26, 28, 30-34, 36, 40, 41, 44) <p>Relevant concepts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Desire for privacy and anonymity (n=3)(17, 21, 33, 34) - Confidentiality (n=5)(23, 25, 26, 28, 31, 36) - Online technology issues (n=1)(44) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service access issues (n=11)(18, 21, 25, 29-31, 33, 34, 36, 39, 42, 44) <p>Relevant concepts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regional variation in service provision (n=1)(21, 44) - Young people’s need for convenience (e.g. access to free condoms, appointment time (n=6)(18, 21, 25, 29-31) - Consideration needed of people with specific access needs (n=3)(18, 21, 42)

<p>health service settings or delivery to home or locker.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure clear guidance on how to use condoms is included alongside free condoms and where young people can go to access further advice. Free condom schemes should also encompass provision of femidoms and dental dams. • How best to advertise sexual health service availability to young people, including relevant social media sites and schools. • Developing an online national 'go-to' resource for advice and support on sexual health issues. Content should be up to date, friendly and fun, and accessible, with labelling of content which may be too sexually explicit for younger audiences. Young people may appreciate opportunities to learn from other people's experiences to which they can relate. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of free condoms (n=8)(18, 21, 29, 31-34, 42, 44) Relevant concepts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of diversity in condoms and lube provided/associated information (n=1)(21) • Health services a trustworthy source of information: See above. Relevant concepts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consideration of needs of specific groups (n=3)(21, 25, 33, 34) - Include development of skills (n=2)(38, 39) • Service access issues (n=11)(18, 21, 25, 29-31, 33, 34, 36, 39, 42, 44) Relevant concepts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need to provide up to date and accessible service information online (n=2){Brook, 2024 #58;Newby, 2019 #51 • Self-efficacy/ Empowerment (n=7){Alam, 2021 #30;Aranda, 2018 #31;Berendes, 2023 #33;Free, 2016 #37;French, 2016 #38;Knights, 2021 #44;Lewis, 2021 #45;Mahendru, 2019 #49;Winters, 2024 #57} Relevant factors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need for a trustworthy, national source of information (n=1)(33) <p>Subtheme 4.2: Behavioural capability, knowledge and skills</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness of services/ products (n=12)(17, 18, 21, 28-34, 36, 39, 44) <p>Theme 2: Institutional factors Relevant concepts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fear of racism (n=1)(40, 41) - Consideration needed of people with specific access needs (n=3)(18, 21, 42) - Consideration of needs of specific groups (n=3)(21, 25, 33, 34)
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consideration of how best to engage with communities who may distrust or find it hard to access health services e.g. some ethnic minority or traveller communities. 	
Implications for research	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Further qualitative research to explore the experiences and support needs of all groups within LGBTQ+ communities and in relation to managing healthy relationships and sexual-health. • Further qualitative research to consider of the specific needs of sex-workers in managing their sexual health. 	<p>These recommendations are based on the absence of primary qualitative evidence exploring experiences of condom use within young people from these populations</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualitative and quantitative research to develop and evaluate interventions to promote condom use as a typical part of enacting a healthy masculine identity. 	<p>This recommendation is based on a) the observation that findings from this review may support developing interventions to promote condom use in young people within the UK and b) the relatively few studies evaluating young people’s experiences of interventions to promote condom use eligible for inclusion within this review.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider how participant age may contribute towards their likelihood and experiences of using condoms. 	<p>This recommendation is based on the observation that it was difficult to determine the impact participant age on findings from the synthesis and thus whether/how factors related to condom use may vary according to the young person/s age.</p>